

ANALYSING CURRENT STATUS OF BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY: ASSESSING ADVANCEMENT FROM FIELD TO EXPORT

DOCTOR OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION (DBA) THESIS

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DECLARATION

It is to be declared here that current research work has not been submitted anywhere else for any other academic award. It is my own work and not been presented previously for other degree awards.

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ABSTRACT

Jute is increasingly recognized as a viable natural fiber, addressing the growing global demand for sustainable alternatives to synthetic fibers. This trend offers a significant opportunity for Bangladesh, a leading producer of jute, to rejuvenate its presence in the international market. Recent research suggests that the country's jute sector has the potential for significant growth if it embraces advancements in production and processing strategies. While existing literature discusses the opportunities and challenges within the country's jute industry, it often fails to consider the sector's evolution in relation to global market trends. To address this gap, the current study aims to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the present status and advancements of Bangladesh's jute industry, with a particular focus on three critical areas: production, processing, and marketing. The findings seek to contribute to existing academic discourse by providing a comprehensive understanding of the industry's development and offering a strategic action model designed to inform stakeholders and policymakers in guiding future initiatives within the sector.

To achieve these objectives, semi-structured interviews were conducted with industry experts—including professionals from industrial sectors, agricultural experts, jute researchers, and marketing personnel—within Bangladesh's jute industry. The qualitative data collected through these interviews were analyzed thematically to provide insights into the industry's current scenario and dynamics.

The findings of the research revealed that the jute industry in Bangladesh is undergoing significant advancements compared to its previous condition. Notable improvements include better variety use in the fields, considerable progress in seed center development, a shift towards advanced retting techniques, the strategic implementation of low-cost production approaches, advancements in the private sector—particularly in technology and diversified jute products—a competitive pricing strategy, and improvements in trading ports and transport facilities. Despite these advancements, participants identified several areas in need of further attention and enhancement. Based on the findings, an inclusive action model has been developed to guide future improvements and address the identified challenges within the industry.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION.....	ii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	iii
ABSTRACT	iv
TABLE OF CONTENTS	v
LIST OF FIGURES	ix
LIST OF TABLES.....	ix
ABBREVIATION.....	x
CHAPTER 1	1
INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY AND ITS COMPETITIVE GLOBAL POSITION.....	1
1.2 INCREASE IN GLOBAL JUTE DEMAND AND PROSPECT OF BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY	4
1.3 OPPORTUNITIES FOR ADVANCEMENTS IN BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY.....	7
1.3.1 Cultivation and Production Advancement	7
1.3.2 Jute industries and their processing strategy	8
1.3.3 Advancement in marketing policy	10
1.4 RESEARCH PROBLEM, RATIONALE AND IMPLICATION OF CURRENT RESEARCH	11
1.5 RESEARCH AIM, OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS	12
1.5.1 Research aim.....	12
1.5.2 Research Objectives	12
1.5.3 Research questions	13
1.6 CHAPTER ARRANGEMENTS.....	13
CHAPTER 2	15
LITERATURE REVIEW	15
2.1 INDUSTRIAL ADVANCEMENT AND UNDERPINNING CONCEPTS.....	16
2.1.1 Importance of industrial advancement and its assessment	17
2.1.2 Industrial advancement in response to global demand	19
2.1.3 Demand and advancement assessment in Bangladesh jute industry.....	21
2.2 RELATED THEORIES	23
2.2.1 Value chain theory	24
2.2.2 Strategic management theory	26
2.3 INDUSTRIAL DOMAIN TO EXPERIENCE THE ADVANCEMENT	31
2.3.1 Production domain of the manufacturing industry	32
2.3.2 Industrial processing domain	38

2.3.3 Industrial marketing domain	44
2.4 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK.....	49
2.5 SUMMARY OF THE CHAPTER AND RESEARCH GAP	51
CHAPTER 3	60
METHODOLOGY	60
3.1 CONCEPT OF RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	60
3.3 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY	63
3.3.1 Justification for selecting current research philosophy	64
3.3.2 Selection of research paradigm and justification	66
3.4 RESEARCH APPROACH	66
3.4.1 Rationale for selecting current research approach	66
3.5 SELECTION AND JUSTIFICATION FOR CURRENT RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	67
3.6 RESEARCH STRATEGY	68
3.6.1 Rationale for interview as selected research strategy	70
3.7 DATA COLLECTION	72
3.7.1 Justification for selected data collection tool	72
3.7.2 Selection of participants and questionnaire development.....	73
3.7.3 Reliability and validity of the questionnaire	75
3.7.4 Sampling and justification for selected sampling strategy	76
3.7.5 Conducting the interview	77
3.7.6 Justification for the sample size	78
3.7.7 Validity and reliability of data.....	78
3.8 DATA PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS	79
3.8.1 Thematic data analysis	80
3.9 MANAGING BIASES IN PROCESSING DATA.....	84
3.10 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS.....	84
3.11 SUMMARY OF THE CHAPTER	86
CHAPTER 4	87
FINDINGS.....	87
4.1 DEMOGRAPHIC PRESENTATION OF PARTICIPANT	87
4.1.1 Participants age	89
4.1.2 Job position of participants	89
4.1.3 Participant’s year of experience	89
4.1.4 Participant’s Institute.....	89
4.1.5 Gender of participants	90

4.2 PARTICIPANT’S RESPONSE FROM INTERVIEW	90
4.3 DATA FROM THEMATIC ANALYSIS.....	104
4.3.1 Strategic advancement	108
4.3.2 Processing strategy	112
4.3.3 Marketing strategy	115
4.3.2 Advancement in diversified jute product	116
4.3.3 Governmental assistance in advancement	117
4.3.4 Future recommendation	120
4.4 THEMATIC MAP	125
4.5 CHAPTER SUMMARY.....	125
CHAPTER 5	127
DISCUSSION.....	127
5.1 RESEARCH QUESTION 1: HOW IS BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY WORKING TO INCREASE THEIR JUTE PRODUCTION (YIELD)?.....	128
5.1.1 Improved variety advancement and production expansion.....	128
5.1.2 Advancement in retting approach.....	129
5.2 RESEARCH QUESTION 2: HOW IS BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY PROCESSING THEIR PRODUCT TO SATISFY GLOBAL DEMAND?	131
5.2.1 Industrial processing strategy	132
5.2.2 Technological advancement in industrial processing.....	132
5.2.3 Sustainable processing of jute	133
5.2.4 Advancement in diversified jute product	134
5.3 RESEARCH QUESTION 3: WHAT COMPETITIVE MARKETING STRATEGIES ARE THEY ADOPTING?.....	135
5.3.1 Advancement in marketing actions with different training and exhibition facilities	135
5.3.2 Digital marketing	136
5.3.3 Advancement in pricing strategy	137
5.4 RESEARCH QUESTION 4: WHAT GOVERNMENTAL ASSISTANCE ARE THEY RECEIVING IN THEIR ADVANCEMENT?	138
5.4.1 Advancement in policies and regulation	138
5.4.2 Governmental funding and financial support	139
5.4.3 Advancement in resolving trading barriers.....	139
5.5 MAIN RESEARCH QUESTION: HOW IS BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY WORKING TOWARDS ITS ADVANCEMENT (AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION, INDUSTRIAL PROCESSING AND MARKETING) TO MEET GLOBAL DEMAND?	141
5.6 FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS.....	142
5.6.1 Strategic advancement	146

5.6.2 Governmental assistance.....	150
5.6.3 Research and education.....	151
5.7 CHAPTER SUMMARY.....	152
CHAPTER 6.....	154
CONCLUSION.....	154
6.1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES.....	154
6.2 RESEARCH SUMMARY AND OUTCOMES.....	155
6.3 RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	158
6.3.1 Theoretical contribution and recommendation.....	158
6.3.2 Knowledge contributions and recommendations.....	158
6.3.3 Practical implications and recommendations.....	159
6.4 LIMITATIONS OF CURRENT RESEARCH AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH.....	163
6.4.1 Research approach.....	163
6.4.2 Absence of questionnaire pilot test.....	164
6.4.3 Manual processing of the data.....	165
6.4.4 Interview language.....	165
6.4.5 Number of participants.....	165
6.5 CHAPTER SUMMARY.....	165
REFERENCES.....	i
APPENDIX I.....	xlvi
APPENDIX II.....	cxxxii

LIST OF FIGURES

Figures	page
Comparable jute production in Bangladesh, India and China	3
Comparable jute yield across Bangladesh, India and China	3
Raw jute export from Bangladesh, India and China	3
Implementation of plastic ban around the world	5
Conceptual framework	50
Research Onion of current study	61
Schematic illustration of research steps	63
Thematic map	125
Proposed action model for the improvement in Bangladesh jute industry	145
Roadmap for action implementation	163

LIST OF TABLES

Tables name	Page
Literature table	52
Research gaps align with research objectives	58
Demographic presentation of participants	88
Data summary obtained from the interview	91
Code, themes and sub-theme	105
Identified facts and issues in the advancement of Bangladesh jute industry following participant's comments	143
Description of the phase in roadmap	162

ABBREVIATION

DJP- Diversified jute product

JDPC- Jute Diversification Promotion Centre

JFSD- Jute Farming Systems Division

BJRI- Bangladesh Jute Research Institute

GDP- Gross domestic product

UNEP- United Nations Environment Programme

OECD- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

TPM- Total Productive Maintenance

UN- United Nations

SWOT- Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats

MT- Metric ton

AD- Anti-dumping

TK- Taka (Bangladeshi currency)

pcs- Pieces

AMA- Advanced market analytics

SME- Small and medium-sized enterprises

ha- hectare

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The chapter will provide the foundation of the current study, outlining its background, purpose, and justification for the research. Discussion of the research background is very important to acknowledge any key issues that cause the conduct of the research. The current chapter will present scenarios based on which the research aims and questions are developed. The research is aimed at analysing the present status of advancement in Bangladesh's jute industry. The industry is currently in high demand to improve its place in the global market. Existing literatures outlined several challenges and opportunities that will lead the industry to identify required advancement. Different actions are also suggested by existing literature accordingly. However, the actual developmental phase of Bangladesh's jute industry is unknown. It is yet unidentified how far the industry has advanced in response to such suggestions. Without this knowledge, it is difficult to make plans for future actions. In this context, it is paramount to assess the current state of advancement in the industry. It will enable researchers and policymakers to work out further required actions and to set plans accordingly. The current chapter presents different facts related to the Bangladesh jute industry to have a broad idea about the industry, its potential contribution to the global market, and the rationale for the research. Following a discussion of pertinent facts, the current chapter presents research questions and the planned structure of the whole research work.

1.1 BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY AND ITS COMPETITIVE GLOBAL POSITION

Jute, a natural fiber, possesses many significant characteristics that offer diverse applications. In the textile industry, jute holds considerable importance, ranking second to cotton in contribution (Islam and Ali, 2018). Bangladesh is recognised as a key player in the global jute market, having established its presence since the early 20th century. During the 1950s, Bangladesh primarily dominated the international jute trade until the emergence of competitors like China, India, Nepal, and Uzbekistan (Rahman *et al.*, 2017). Throughout the 1980s, jute was the primary export commodity

of Bangladesh, substantially contributing to the nation's foreign currency reserves. The economic landscape of Bangladesh, particularly its Gross Domestic Product (GDP), was heavily reliant on jute exports as a principal source of revenue.

However, the dynamics within the export sector have evolved over time. As other export-oriented industries began to develop, they consolidated their presence alongside jute. Currently, jute remains a vital contributor to Bangladesh's economy, representing the second-largest source of foreign revenue after ready-made garments (Islam and Ali, 2017). It ranks as the third most significant export commodity in the country, sharing this status with fish (including shrimp, prawn, and other varieties) and ready-made garments (Chowdhury and Rashed, 2015). Given its economic implications, jute is categorized as an essential cash crop in Bangladesh. The quality and quantity of jute from Bangladesh have always attracted considerable attention across the globe. Even jute was designated as the "Golden fiber of Bangladesh." However, there was a fall in the global jute market with the emergence of cheaper alternatives- polyethylene (Rahman *et al.*, 2017). Plastic bags and packaging replaced several jute products. Consequently, the situation caused a decline in Bangladesh's jute export business. It was a crisis moment (1990s) for jute farmers and industries in Bangladesh. However, the industry came over with time. The highest jute export to date was found in the year of 2012-13 (0.87 million MT). Whereas 0.74 million MT was observed in the later period of 2018-19. So, it can be said that the industry experienced some ups and downs in its exporting history. Nevertheless, the scenario is improving with time to regain its position in the international market.

Bangladesh has been identified as one of the top countries in the world for producing jute, along with China and India. Bangladesh and India have competitive production ranges in terms of the quantity of production. Jahan (2019) mentioned that around 90% of global jute production comes from Bangladesh and India. Between them, India has a higher volume of jute production (figure 1). It has been identified that India has some local jute demand that consumes part of its production, consequently reducing the volume of exports. They need to satisfy the local demand before exporting the jute. On the other hand, Bangladesh's local jute demand is not that high (Sharna and Kamruzzaman, 2020). So, Bangladesh exports most of its produced jute all over the world. The country has been observed to dominate the global raw jute market compared to India and China (figure 3) (Sharna and Kamruzzaman, 2020).

Figure 1: Comparable jute production in Bangladesh, India and China (Sharna and Kamruzzaman, 2020)

Figure 2: Comparable jute yield across Bangladesh, India and China (Sharna and Kamruzzaman, 2020)

Figure 3: Raw jute export from Bangladesh, India and China (Sharna and Kamruzzaman, 2020)

However, China has a higher price per unit of raw jute export than Bangladesh and India. It is because of the quality production, advanced techniques, and competitive strategies that the country follows. China has the highest yield of jute compared to Bangladesh and India (figure 2). With such quality products, China steps ahead in attracting the global market. Besides, China leads the globe in exporting the most high-value, diverse jute products. The export of varied jute products by Bangladesh's jute sector is still lagging here (Azad *et al.*, 2020). Bangladesh is generating some DJP, but not in satisfactory quality to meet demand worldwide (Islam and Xiaoying, 2016). In 2009, Bangladesh exported 85.7% of global raw jute. In contrast, it was only 6% for DJP. The comparative raw jute export from China and India was lower than Bangladesh (figure 3) but higher in terms of high-value jute products. Around 58.1% and 8.5% of high-value jute products were contributed respectively by China and India in that period of the year (Rahman and Khaled, 2011). The statistic shows that Bangladesh dominates the raw jute market with little contribution to the DJP market. Therefore, research suggests that Bangladesh can have a huge opportunity in the future to compete with China and India if they improve the quality of jute production and supply more diversified jute products (DJP) (Akter, 2015). The industry needs considerable advancements in the system to increase the value of products. Recent research by Siraj-UD-Douhah, Hassan and Sukanta (2020) forecasted an increasing trend in Bangladesh jute production by 2026-2027. Considering the global need for jute and the position of Bangladesh in jute production, it was anticipated that the production would be high in the future for the jute industry. However, the industry must prioritise quality production and product advancement to get the desired competitive position in the global market. An elaborate discussion on the rise of global jute demand and its contemporary anticipation for the Bangladesh jute industry is discussed below.

1.2 INCREASE IN GLOBAL JUTE DEMAND AND PROSPECT OF BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY

Consumers in the current era are getting more attracted towards the green products (Boz, Korhonen and Koelsch Sand, 2020). In this concern, the biodegradable and eco-friendly nature of jute is one of the important triggers to increase its market demand. Jute has been labeled as an emerging substitute for plastic (Chowdhury and Rashed, 2015). Pavel and Supinit (2017) stated that around 1 million plastic bags are being

used every minute by the global people. Around 500 billion plastic bags are being used each year globally. The demand for plastic is always increasing as its production. However, most of these plastics end up in landfills and cause environmental problems. The non-degradable nature of plastic and its adverse impact on our earth are now getting major attention. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) reported that about 7 billion tonnes of plastic out of the 9.2 billion tonnes have been turned into landfilled waste. It is causing negative consequences on the global environment (<https://www.unep.org><https://www.unep.org/plastic-pollution>). On the other hand, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) stated that about 22% of plastic waste worldwide remains mismanaged (<https://www.oecd.org/>). Analysing the devastating impact of plastic on many countries have banned the use of plastic (Figure 4). Reportedly, 127 countries worldwide impose different plastic-use regulations, and some even impose a ban on single-use plastic (UN Environment Programme, 2018). For instance, Bangladesh banned the use of plastic bags in 2002, China banned it in 2008, Uganda banned it in 2007, and so on. (Ahmed and Kader, 2014). Such regulations are helping to down-regulate the use of plastic bags all over the world (Adeyanju *et al.*, 2021) and promoting the use of paper or reusable (natural fiber bags) sustainable bags in the global market (Goldsberry, 2020).

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Figure 4: Implementation of plastic ban around the world (The economist, 2019)

Ahmed and Kader (2014) mentioned that around 1200,000 jute shopping bags are exported annually from Bangladesh to other countries. Many world-renowned grocery and chain stores like LiDI use jute bags as a substitute for poly bags (Elmarasi, 2017). Nevertheless, the global demand for usual shopping bags is 500 billion pcs annually. So, the exported amount of jute bags from Bangladesh still has more space to fill. Considering this space, an increase in jute bag demand can be expected. On the other hand, in 2018, the global market value of jute bags was 1.8 billion USD. However, with the rise in its demand, it is also projected that the market value will be 3.1 billion USD by the year 2024. According to the increased use of jute products as a sustainable substitution for polythene, Advanced Market Analytics (AMA) (2020) assumed that jute bags can experience a 9.9% increase in market demand. This prediction can be a great impetus for the jute producer to grab more profits from jute production in forthcoming years.

The researcher also discussed the domestic demand (Local market of Bangladesh) for jute bags (Ahmed and Kader, 2014). It was estimated that Bangladesh uses around 14.1 billion polybags annually from different household perspectives (Ahmed and Kader, 2014). The lower price of plastic bags motivates customers to prefer plastic over jute bags. However, it was predicted that the cheaper supply of jute bags could achieve a demand of about 10 million pcs jute bags/per day. This will reduce the use of poly bags and will alter the use of sustainable jute bags. However, some improvements in the industrial strategy are needed to ensure quality products and to get into the market.

Moreover, the global jute market assessment indicates significant demand for diversified jute products- particularly the jute bag (Akter, Sadekin and Islam, 2020). It has been suggested that the Bangladesh jute industry can prioritize value-added jute products instead of solely exporting raw jute. Being a reputed raw jute exporting country, Bangladesh's jute industry can also focus on expanding its market for other value-added jute products. Therefore, it is high time that Bangladesh's jute industry reintroduced itself in the global jute market with some advancements to satisfy the demand for different jute products. The industry needs to follow recommended improvements in its system that existing literatures and policymakers have guided.

1.3 OPPORTUNITIES FOR ADVANCEMENTS IN BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY

Opportunity assessment is an important part of any development. It directs to the position or fact where the advancement is needed. It is associated with identifying solutions for different challenges and limitations hindering the path to success. Different research has discussed the challenges, limitations, and opportunities for Bangladesh's jute industry where they can bring improvements to meet global demand (Islam and Ali, 2017; Rahman *et al.*, 2017; Sheheli and Roy, 2014; Chowdhury and Rashed, 2015). Some of them are discussed below:

1.3.1 Cultivation and Production Advancement

Jute is the second most useful, consumable, and demanded vegetable fiber (Mia *et al.*, 2016). Sharna and Kamruzzaman (2020) stated that Bangladesh has a higher jute production area than China. Around 6% of Bangladesh's total land is under jute cultivation while it constitutes about 10% of the total agricultural area (Islam *et al.*, 2015). As a sensitive plant, Jute is susceptible to different conditions and cannot be cultivated on all the land. Some limited areas can be considered suitable for jute production. However, to meet the global demand, it is important to increase production, which can be done by extending their cultivable lands for jute. Rahman *et al.* (2017) mentioned that development in land extension or infrastructure establishment for irrigation can have a positive impact on increased jute production. Islam *et al.* (2018) stated the importance of charlands (Jamuna River, Sariakandi of Bogra, Shaghata and Fulchori of Gaibandha and Sorisabari) jute cultivation in Bangladesh as a great action to increase the production.

Furthermore, Hossain *et al.* (2020) recently discussed the Jute-based farming system (JBFS) developed by the Jute Farming Systems Division (JFSD) that includes jute with other farming components to make it sustainable farming and a preferable approach to farmers. In this way, jute can be cultivated in a way that is aligned with other demanded crops (within a specified cropping system). It can be used as a guideline to cultivate jute in a wide range of areas in Bangladesh. Many farmers in Bangladesh are reluctant to cultivate jute in their land and are more likely to alter jute cultivation with other valuable crops (rice, wheat, orchard, corn, maize). So, the JBFS can help the farmers cultivate their preferred crop along with jute to get the optimum economic benefit. On the other hand, Rahman *et al.* (2017) stated that the development of

cultivars that resist climatic challenges can be a great way to increase jute production by cultivating susceptible areas. Islam and Ali (2017) stated that the adoption of high-yield varieties can assist jute farmers in getting an increased harvest from reduced land cultivation. However, jute farmers asserted that they are having trouble getting quality seeds. They are often deprived of important market information like price, demand, and production (Islam, 2017). It is a great problem for them to lead the market accordingly. In addition, Akter, Sadekin and Islam (2020) mentioned that the storage problem of jute can lead to low-quality products. Most of the jute businessmen store processing jute in conventional storehouses, which can have an adverse impact on quality. Considering the facts, it is paramount for the industry to pay sincere attention to improving its field-related issues.

Jute processing is an important part of getting quality jute products that comes after harvesting the jute. Retting and striping are the core of jute processing and lead to the fiber extraction from jute sticks (Jahan, 2019). Conventionally the retting process in Bangladesh is performed with an immersing jute stick in running water (Islam, 2019) which has been found to have an adverse impact on the environment (Banik *et al.*, 2003). Such a conventional retting process requires extensive labor work. However, the alternative mechanical retting process named 'Ribbon retting' has been introduced globally as a sustainable and eco-friendly way with reduced cost and water waste (Banik *et al.*, 2003). Besides, it has improved fiber quality compared to conventional retting. So, this can be an important sector for Bangladesh's jute industry to get advanced with competitive techniques. The industry needs improved retting technology to produce high quality jute fiber within a short period of time and with low labour costs.

1.3.2 Jute industries and their processing strategy

The raw jute usually is processed in field then gets treated in the industrial setting to deliver commercial products. This is where it is converted into diverse products. Some major jute items that Bangladesh exports are raw jute, ropes, jute carpet and jute yarn. Jahan (2019) stated other traditional jute products made in Bangladesh named hessian cloth, canvas cloth, bags, serim cloth, tobacco sheet, decorative item and geo-textile. It has been mentioned that around 10% of total jute production is used in making DJP which is very low. Besides, most of the diversified jute producing industries or organizations are SME or small entrepreneur work. So, it can be assumed

that the level of DJP production in Bangladesh still needs improvement. Bangladesh has an institute for DJP named 'Jute Diversification Promotion Centre (JDPC)'. This is the institute with scientists and researchers to develop new DJPs and to help jute industries with financial and technical support (Islam and Ali, 2017). Different DJP lists can be found on their website (<http://www.jdpc.gov.bd/>). Considering the current global demand for DJP, the institute can come forward to implement the desired advancement in this sector to gain success in the global market. However, such products' worthiness and effective market value still need to be evaluated. Initiatives and achievements of this organization are also not yet at any level of satisfaction (Siddiqui, 2015). So, it can be said that the institute needs further advancement to meet the demand. Islam and Ali (2018) recommended modern machineries that can be adopted to get qualified jute products. For example, high output spreaders, new design high output Breaker and Finisher cards, high speed and high output drawing frames, ring twisters, shuttleless looms, precision winders, Ring spinning and automatic jute bag sewing units. Implementation of advanced machineries and technology will help the industry to prosper.

Bangladesh has around 219 jute mills that are divided into three organization (Bangladesh Jute spinners Association (BJSA), Bangladesh Jute Mills Association (BJMA), Bangladesh Jute Mills Corporation (BJMC)). Among these organizations, the production (422,000 MT) and export (3,42,195 MT yarns/twines) rate is higher for BJSA (Rahman and Khaled, 2011). According to Akter, Sadekin and Islam (2020) the jute mills under BJSA yearly use around 1.9 million bales of raw jute to produce about 0.29 million tonnes of jute yarn or twine of which they export 0.261 million tonnes in abroad. BJMC was directed by the Bangladesh government, and around 23 jute mills were running under this organization. Whereas BJMA is composed of privately running jute mills, and around 30 of these jute mills are currently involved in producing conventional jute products. Recent analysis indicates that the jute mills under the BJMC have ceased operations due to government intervention. The mills were shuttered primarily because of substantial bank debts, leading the government to privatize some facilities by offering them on lease (Paulsen, 2022). The mills were mostly dependent on government funds. Besides, lack of technology, skill power and the impact of corruption have been identified as barriers to the development of jute mills under BJMC. The mills were also struggling to carry out their labour cost and

machinery costs. In addition, their firm performance was also not desirable (Hossain, Nishu and Freelance Researcher, 2021). Considering the situation, the Bangladesh government has taken the decision to increase the local demand for jute products and transform the government-led jute mills into SMEs or privately owned industries to minimize the losses (Parvez, 2019). Nevertheless, Bangladesh's jute industry's recent massive industrial termination will adversely affect its reputation in the global market. It has become a great challenge for Bangladesh's jute industry to establish more industries that can increase their production. The government needs to support the expansion of the industry rather than wrapping it up.

1.3.3 Advancement in marketing policy

Islam and Ali (2017) mentioned some failures in marketing policies undertaken by the Bangladesh jute industry. The marketing strategy of the Bangladesh jute industry has been found to be lacking in both domestic and global markets. It has been identified that proper labelling of jute products is missing which is paramount to increase the sale. Akter (2015) discussed the problem of improper HS (harmonized system code) in Bangladesh's jute export system. It fails to classify the product as it is intended to. International business or transportation requires transparent information regarding the product that is being exported. Adequate production and processing details is required to be informed to get buyer acceptance. So, the industry can bring improvements in this sector to advance its competitive position.

The jute market is also restricted by different tariff management and market access barriers. While countries like the UK, Japan, and Australia have zero tariff facilities for jute products, Bangladesh has to pay a high tariff rate for Singapore, Vietnam, and Colombia (10%). Brazil applies an 8% tariff rate for Bangladesh raw jute (Rahman and Khaled, 2011). The tariffing cost varies from item to item. It is a major concern in improving global market access.

Rahman and Khaled (2011) stated strategies that can be useful to advance existing marketing policies of Bangladesh jute industry. For instance, improving product promotion, assisting SMEs, improving market for traditional jute product and works on trade barriers. Pricing is another important fact in marketing strategy. Considering the unsettled local jute market of Bangladesh, Akter, Sadekin and Islam (2020) suggested

that the government should develop local purchase centre where the farmers will have easy access and standard prices to sell their product.

1.4 RESEARCH PROBLEM, RATIONALE AND IMPLICATION OF CURRENT RESEARCH

It has already been mentioned that Bangladesh jute industry is about to experience a high demand in jute production to satisfy the global demand (Akter, Sadekin and Islam, 2020). Statistics show that the global market is trending toward environment-friendly products and jute has high demand for plastic bag substitutes (Boz, Korhonen and Koelsch Sand, 2020; Chowdhury and Rashed, 2015). Different DJPs are getting market attention all around the world. In this concern, Bangladesh, as one of the top jute-exporting countries, is anticipated to encounter this demand to produce more quality jute products.

Existing literatures has been identified to discuss different prospects of the Bangladesh jute industry in the global market and its opportunities. Studies have also discussed existing challenges and possible solutions for the industry. However, the current state of Bangladesh's jute industry with information regarding their implemented actions following global demand is overlooked in existing literature (Toky *et al.*, 2022). It was mentioned that an extensive assessment of the industrial advancement is required with updated data to guide future action plans (Akter, Sadekin and Islam, 2020; Islam and Ali, 2018; Sharna and Kamruzzaman, 2020). Advancement is a continuous process that needs regular monitoring to identify gaps and to work accordingly. Dziallas and Blind (2019), and Larsson (2017) stated that industrial improvement requires ongoing monitoring to evaluate their effectiveness and determine how actions will impact the desired outcome. It helps to identify any errors or shortcomings and to make changes accordingly. In this context, Hossain, Nishu and Freelance Researcher (2021) also stated that the actual scenario of the Bangladesh jute industry is required to be assessed to identify any missed opportunities or shortcomings to plan accordingly. So, current research seeks to contribute to this literature sector by identifying the present status of Bangladesh's jute industry in terms of its advancement and preparation to satisfy anticipated global demand. It will enrich the literature with updated information about actions that the industry has implemented and those that are still unnoticed. Based on the information, researchers can further

prioritize the needed actions. Policymakers and industrial professionals can also make appropriate decisions based on the research outcome to meet global demand.

1.5 RESEARCH AIM, OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1.5.1 Research aim

Based on the above-mentioned research problem, current research is aimed at investigating the overall advancement of the Bangladesh jute industry. To provide a comprehensive picture of the industry, it is important to start from its field to the export sector. It will give a broad understanding of the system. The research will assess any progress (agricultural production (raw jute), industrial processing and marketing) that Bangladesh's jute industry is undertaking to meet global demand. It will guide us to the information 'how much improvement is in the process and how far it will need to go to satisfy global competitive demand'. An action model will also be developed considering the outcome or obtained information from current research to recommend improved activities for the industry.

1.5.2 Research Objectives

To obtain the mentioned research aim, the following objectives were developed accordingly.

- To establish a conceptual framework by critically assessing existing literatures underpinning advancement in different industrial domain (production, processing and marketing), Bangladesh jute industry and its associated advancement to meet global demand.
- To assess agricultural strategies undertaken by Bangladesh jute industry to meet market demand.
- To examine advancement in industrial processing of jute products by Bangladesh jute industry.
- To investigate marketing strategies that they are implementing in current competitive market.
- To develop an action model after analysing existing literatures and current research outcome to propose recommended actions for Bangladesh jute industry to improve their current state.

1.5.3 Research questions

Furthermore, one main research question was developed to answer the above research objectives. The main research question is,

“How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards its advancement (agricultural production, industrial processing and marketing) to meet global demand?”

The main research question was then divided into sub-research questions to set the focus separately per the research objectives.

The sub-research questions are:

- How is Bangladesh jute industry working to increase their jute production (yield)?
- How is Bangladesh jute industry processing their product to satisfy global demand?
- What competitive marketing strategies are they adopting?
- What governmental assistance are they receiving in their advancement?

1.6 CHAPTER ARRANGEMENTS

This chapter (chapter 1) provides an overview of the research background. Based on this background, specific research questions and objectives have been developed to guide the research toward achieving its outcome. As we move forward, the next step is to assess existing literature to identify related research gaps.

Chapter 2 will review relevant literature and highlight the identified research gaps that the current study aims to address.

In Chapter 3, we will discuss the overall research methodology. This chapter will outline each step taken in the current research, from beginning to completion, and will explain the research strategies, techniques, and data analysis tools that will be utilized.

Chapter 4 will deliver a clear and organized overview of the current research data, accompanied by a thorough description to enhance understanding. On the other hand, chapter 5 will engage in a critical analysis of this data, articulating the research

outcomes and demonstrating how they effectively meet the existing research objectives.

Chapter 6 will provide a summary of the research. The chapter will highlight research outcomes along with their contribution, implications, limitations, and future recommendations.

Finally, chapter 7 will include the references, and chapter 8 will serve as the appendix. This structure organizes the entire research writing systematically and presents it in a standard academic format.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter is constructed to critically discuss available literatures and underpinning theories that are related to the field of current research. Current research aimed at investigating recent advancements in Bangladesh's jute industry, from the field to the export in correspondence to meet global demand. It was identified from existing literatures that the increasing trend in global jute demand will significantly impact the prosperity of Bangladesh jute industry. It was also suggested that the industry may benefit from a few advancements in the system to compete with other jute-exporting countries. However, adequate information regarding the industry's current movement towards such advancement is missing in existing literatures. This hinders policymakers and researchers from deciding on future action without knowing their current state. Hence, the industry currently needs proper direction for the advancement to achieve its target. Considering the facts, current research set its objectives on assessing advancement in all the domains of Bangladesh's jute industry that is involved in its raw material production, industrial product processing and product distribution in global market. This will help to get a broad view of the performance of Bangladesh jute industry to decide future actions in meeting global demand.

With such a research aim, it is apparent that the research contains few important elements to understand before going for analysing them. Including industrial advancement and different domains of an industry that undergoes the advancement. Assessing these elements in the context of existing literature and relating them with the Bangladesh jute industry will help the researcher to demonstrate the research gap and purpose of the current research. Hence, this chapter is structured to discuss related literatures and theories underpinning identified elements from the research aim.

The chapter starts with explaining industrial advancement and its importance in global market. The section further discusses occurrence of industrial advancement around the world and significance of advancements for Bangladesh jute industry. This will lead the reader to understand basis of current research.

In the next step, the chapter confers selected theories that supports aim and objectives of current research. Further, the chapter discusses different industrial realm (production, processing, marketing) that contributes to overall industrial advancement. This section critically highlights the importance of each industrial domain and their operational activities for advancement. Following the discussion, the chapter will develop a conceptual framework that links the concept of discussed facts with current research objectives. Finally, the chapter will conclude with identified research gap from extensive literature discussion.

2.1 INDUSTRIAL ADVANCEMENT AND UNDERPINNING CONCEPTS

Industrial advancement is an ongoing process of improving industrial systems to meet their target (Chen, Qi and Tan, 2022). To understand the basis of current research, it is essential to become acquainted with the term 'industrial advancement'. Since it is the main focus of current research to investigate. Several related terms came up in the search of existing literature while looking for industrial advancement. For instance, 'Industrial innovation', 'Industrial transformation' and 'industrial upgrading'. (Azadegan and Wagner, 2011; Chen, Qi and Tan, 2022; Esmaeilian, Behdad and Wang, 2016; Li and Li, 2017; Mamasioulas, Mourtzis and Chryssolouris, 2020). The terms are closely related to each other and indicate the same concept of industrial advancement in different ways.

Industrial innovation has been stated as a process of implementing new ideas, processes, strategies, or actions aimed at improving performance and satisfying customer demands (Mamasioulas, Mourtzis and Chryssolouris, 2020). Romero *et al.* (2017) mentioned industrial innovation as adopting advanced technology, next-generation production processes, strategies, and sustainable approaches to attain competitive advantage and meet customer needs. However, industrial innovation can be ahead of competitive advantage to prioritise the direction of customer requirements. It is not only focused on attaining competitive advancement but also on implementing required development in the system to satisfy customer needs. Gunday *et al.* (2011) mentioned that industrial innovation is not limited to the innovation in production and processing approach. It is an innovative process for the whole industrial system. Innovation can happen to industrial production, processes, marketing, and

organizational systems. According to Manual (2005) innovation guideline, these are the main industrial sectors where innovation activities occur.

On the other hand, industrial transformation and upgrading are associated with technological development and economic growth (Luken and Castellanos-Silveria, 2011; Zou, 2024). Luken and Castellanos-Silveria (2011) stated industrial transformation similar to technological transformation (ITT). It is the transformation of structural orientation from a simple one to an advanced technical one.

Industrial upgrade is another similar term to industrial advancement. It represents the process of improving an industrial system to pursue a competitive market position. It aims to move the system from a regular one to a complex and profitable one (Azadegan and Wagner, 2011). The advancement can be in the form of knowledge, skill, technology, and added value to the product, which will direct them toward the betterment of the global value chain (GVC) (Pietrobelli and Rabellotti, 2006; Tian, Dietzenbacher and Jong-A-Pin, 2019). Considering such upgrades occurring in industrial sectors, Humphrey and Schmitz (2002) categorized them into four types-product upgrade, process upgrade, functional upgrade, and inter-sectoral upgrade. Process upgrade indicates any advancement in the production processing that will improve production efficiency. On the other hand, production upgrade represents the improvement in products compared to its competitive one. Functional upgrading is aimed at implementing any skill improvement activities. Finally, the intersectoral upgrading is about to move into a new production mix with some added value to the existing value chain (Tian, Dietzenbacher and Jong-A-Pin, 2019).

Moreover, having a broad understanding of different terms related to industrial advancement, it can be acknowledged that advancement is any improvement in the industrial system to satisfy the need. It can be described as a step towards meeting global demand, securing a competitive position in the global market, and advancing performance while complying with global industrial policies. It is a comprehensive term that signifies advancement in all facets of industrial operations.

2.1.1 Importance of industrial advancement and its assessment

Industrial advancement in all forms of its related terminology (industrial innovation, industrial transformation, industrial upgrading) has been found to represent a continuous improvement in the industrial system. It is the changes in a system that

occur with changes in surroundings, either naturally or in demand. However, such changes in any form eventually bring prosperity to the industry. Prosper can come in different ways, improving competitive position and market share, adding value to the value chain and entering new markets, raising job opportunities, increasing the gross income of people within the country, and assuring social and environmental sustainability (Gunday *et al.*, 2011; Rocha, 2018; Szutowski, 2017). Industries worldwide are advancing their operation system, infrastructure, processing strategies, and management styles to obtain such prosperity. For instance, various industries are implementing automated quality control, AI-powered inspection, IoT Sensor energy consumption measurement, digital training of the workforce, real-time monitoring, and product feedback (Siddique, 2023). Arcidiacono *et al.* (2023) linked this transition of Smart manufacturing (SM) with competitive priorities. It was identified that SM with additional infrastructure development, will speed up advancement in a competitive market. Besides, industrial advancement in the form of technological upgrades is one of the rising trends that assist in improving overall industrial performance as well as keeping the industry step ahead in a competitive position. For example, digital technology as a means of industrial innovation is crucial to the global value chain's (GVC) robustness (Dilyard, Zhao and You, 2021). Particularly with the COVID-19 crisis and associated catastrophes, digitalization is an important factor in assuring the resilience of GVC in the future. Moreover, industrial advancement not only represents improvement within the industry itself but also has profound significance on the surroundings and economic growth (Ndou, Madonsela and Twala, 2020; UNIDO, 2020) of the associated country (Opoku and Yan, 2019; Yong, 2021).

Vitezic and Vitezic (2015) stated that the first step in implementing industrial innovation is to analyse the industry's current situation to plan ahead. Deciding on the development action is ineffective without knowing the existing practice. Once the current scenario is well understood, it is time to generate ideas accordingly to improve performance. Monitoring performance is the crucial stage of any innovation process.

Bogner *et al.* (2016) studied the implementation level of digital transformation in manufacturing industries to assess unexploited potential in meeting the 4th industrial revolution. The research aimed at comprehending the current state of digital transformation and strategizing subsequent steps. However, the research limited its exploration to digital automation, while the fourth industrial revolution requires a

massive transformation in the different industrial domains. Similar research on advancement assessment has also been conducted by Haut *et al.* (2018). However, the research was also limited to assessing the advancement only in the industry's environmental awareness rather than identifying improvements in other industrial domains. Industrial advancement can occur in single or multiple sectors of the system. It can happen in production, process, marketing, skill development, quality management, human resources, and in different dimensions within the organizational system. Therefore, it is preferable to assess overall progress in the industry from an integrated perspective rather than a limited one. A recent study was found to follow this concept. Stawiarska *et al.* (2021) assessed the maturity level of industrial technology advancement across different functional areas. The research provided a strong example of using maturity assessment tools to monitor progress in advancement. However, such research on overall industrial advancement assessment is absent in Bangladesh's jute industry. The existing literature lacks in providing evidence of the present state of advancement in Bangladesh's jute industry following the rising global demand, which can be useful to monitor its implementation success and propose further priority areas for improvements.

2.1.2 Industrial advancement in response to global demand

Global demand has been mentioned as one of the factors that trigger industrial advancement (Hosono, 2022). It compels industries to enhance their systems to meet the increasing demand effectively. Additionally, various researchers have identified other stimulators of industrial development, including globalization, economic growth, mounting pressure from global competitiveness, and shifts in systemic paradigms (Cefis *et al.*, 2023; Deif, 2011; Ikumapayi *et al.*, 2020). These factors are intricately linked; for instance, globalization stimulates economic growth and significantly influences global competitiveness. Hatzichronoglou (1996) supports this notion by asserting that globalization acts as a driving force behind global competition, fostering rivalry among countries, regions, and firms. Furthermore, Zhang (2010) affirmed the robust relationship between globalization and industrial competitiveness, utilizing foreign direct investment (FDI) as a measure of globalization's impact.

Industrial paradigm shifting is another major trigger for the initiation of industrial advancement. With each industrial revolution, a new and advanced operational system gets implemented in the process, which acquires higher demand in the market.

Industries must adapt or perform accordingly to follow the paradigm (Ciccarelli, Papetti and Germani, 2023). Diverging from demand-oriented industrial shifting, Boon and Edler (2018) demonstrated that the shifting could also be challenge-oriented. It is stated that demand is the combination of human needs and wants (Camilleri and Camilleri, 2018), while the challenge is the outlined competitive situation to satisfy those demands. UNIDO (2023) referred to industrial advancement as the best solution for addressing such challenges.

2.1.2.1 Assessing the demand prior to deciding on advancement

As can be seen from the above discussion, demand has a great influence on advancement decisions. Researchers prioritized assessing the demand or customer preference before any transformation implemented within the industrial system (Lin, Tan and Geng, 2013). It is stated that such a decision without considering the demand will not significantly impact the desired outcome. Lin, Tan and Geng (2013) demonstrated the importance of analyzing market demand before implementing green product innovation. It has been stated that demand assessment can positively impact innovation and overall firm performance. Additionally, a comprehensive understanding of demand equips policymakers with the insights to make informed decisions regarding innovation strategies. Factors influencing demand, such as consumers' financial capabilities, the availability of substitutes, and supply dynamics, also merit careful consideration during the demand assessment process (Fornell, Rust and Dekimpe, 2010; Rousu, Beach and Corrigan, 2008).

Barbosa, Christo and Costa (2015) applied demand forecasting methodologies in the food industry, demonstrating that such approaches facilitate effective production planning. Their findings suggest that aligning production with forecasted demand not only enhances operational efficiency but also strengthens competitive positioning within the market. Similarly, Pourafshary *et al.* (2009) explored the necessity of demand assessment when investing in nanotechnology within the petroleum industry. Their research underscores the importance of conducting thorough demand evaluations to mitigate the risks associated with unwarranted developments and to enable informed decision-making that aligns with industry needs.

Pal and Chakraborti (2011) analyzed the global demand for jute products amidst the dynamics of globalization. Their research indicates a resurgence of the global jute market, forecasting a promising trajectory for its future. Through the application of

Normalized Revealed Comparative (NRCA) indices, the study assessed the market competitiveness of Indian jute products. It was noted that while demand for newer jute products remains robust, the competitiveness of traditional jute products is waning, presenting both challenges and opportunities for stakeholders in the sector. Therefore, it can be seen that assessing demand can be a guide in making effective decisions for advancement.

2.1.3 Demand and advancement assessment in Bangladesh jute industry

Existing literature contains ample research conducted to acknowledge the global demand for jute and the prospects of Bangladesh's jute industry in the global market. As discussed earlier, this literature can be used as the basis of the current research aim, enabling a clear identification of gaps in the existing studies pertaining to industrial development.

Jute has a long-standing history in the global market, navigating various fluctuations throughout its trajectory. Despite its enduring presence, jute faced significant challenges, particularly due to competition from synthetic alternatives like polyethylene. Research indicates that the environmental costs associated with these synthetic substitutes have increasingly outweighed their market advantages (Boyce, 1995). Given these circumstances, jute and other eco-friendly products are beginning to reclaim their market share. Scholars worldwide have made substantial contributions to forecasting the jute market (Karmaker, Halder and Sarker, 2017; Chowdhury and Rashed, 2015) and have developed various models to enhance market conditions (Rifath, 2018).

Karmaker, Halder and Sarker (2017) conducted a case study on predicting jute yarn demand to assist manufacturers and jute industries in Bangladesh to pre-plan their production. The analysis was performed based on different time series forecasting techniques (holt's method, trend analysis, simple moving average and winters method), and data were obtained from different Bangladesh jute industries. The research gave a comparative view of different forecasting tools that the Bangladesh jute industry can use. Winters additive model was one of the tools recommended by the research. Jute manufacturers can use this technique to determine upcoming market conditions beforehand. However, the research was mostly focused on presenting different forecasting models rather than identifying the jute demand and

suggesting required advancements. Similarly, the work of Bhuiyan and Hasnat (2018) employs the Simple Exponential Smoothing model for jute demand assessment. The research succeeded in identifying prospective demand for the Bangladesh jute industry while failing to provide actionable recommendations mentioning how the jute mills can respond effectively to the forecasted bale requirements. The absence of a strategic framework for inventory management, production adjustments, and supply chain logistics limits the practical utility of their findings. Other studies were also identified in existing literature that discussed the prospective demand for Bangladesh jute products (Ammayappan *et al.*, 2013; Ray and Ghosh, 2018). Asrafuzzaman and Islam (2021) discussed the demand for jute and different determinants of Bangladeshi jute exports in the UK, Australia, the USA, Belgium, and Germany. In parallel, Peu (2019) highlighted the prospective demand for Bangladeshi diversified jute products (DJPs) and suggested various strategies for achieving success in this sector. Acknowledging the potential of Bangladesh's jute industry in the global market, the study recommended future research to conduct on proper marketing strategy in meeting the prospective demand.

From the above discussion, it is evident that existing literature worked on identifying prospective demand for Bangladesh jute products in the global market. However, it is imperative to consider assessing not only the demand but also the associated advancements that have been made in the industry responding to that demand which is overlooked in existing literatures.

Existing studies discussed different facts related to the jute in Bangladesh and its opportunity. The analysis conducted by Sharna and Kamruzzaman (2020) offers important insights into the comparative advantage of the jute industry in Bangladesh, particularly in relation to India and China. By employing Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) techniques, the study highlights significant shortcomings in Bangladesh's position within the global jute market, particularly regarding product quality. Identifying quality concerns as a primary issue may provide a focal point for further research and industry action. However, it is critical to note that the analysis is somewhat limited in scope, as it primarily discusses product quality without addressing the broader systemic challenges that is being faced by the industry. The research recommended that an extensive assessment of the industry is required to establish an effective plan for enhanced productivity. Islam and Alauddin (2012) also conducted a

comparative analysis of Bangladesh jute industry with other competitive countries, proposing that the industry has a huge opportunity in future to explore. Wiersema and Beck (2017) recommended that the Bangladesh jute industry needs to pay attention to product diversification to facilitate DJP to meet current market demands. Siddiqui (2015) stated that the diversified product can increase market value ten times compared to the old traditional value. Vries (2007) also presented a similar notion that market turnover and profit margin with DJP will be higher than traditional jute products. They used SWOT and PESTLE analysis to identify challenges (inadequate market/export knowledge, lack of policies, research, development, and lack of skilled workers) and opportunities for the industry.

Moreover, a substantial body of literature on the Bangladesh jute industry addresses the opportunities and demand for the sector. Based on these issues, they have also suggested various industry-wide improvement initiatives. However, existing literature lacks updated empirical data regarding the actions being undertaken by the industry to advance its position in the global market. This gap signifies a crucial oversight, as both researchers and policymakers are left without concrete progress metrics to inform their decisions. Thus, the current research aims to bridge this gap by scrutinizing the advancements in the Bangladeshi jute industry as well as its responsiveness to global demand. Further discussion on advancement assessment in different industry domains will be discussed later in the chapter.

2.2 RELATED THEORIES

This section will discuss selected theories underpinning the current research context and directing the research towards its aim. A theory can be defined as a set of thoughts or perspectives about any phenomenon (Collins and Stockton, 2018). It provides a broad and critical understanding of the facts. It guides the way of assessment and provides boundaries for target issues. So, a theoretical framework is paramount in any research. With the theoretical framework in place, researchers can grasp the underpinnings of their study and steer the results toward meaningful contributions (Ngulube, Mathipa and Gumbo, 2015).

2.2.1 Value chain theory

The concept of 'value chain' was first introduced by Porter (1985). It was represented as a wholesome picture of any product or service from its production to end use. The term 'value chain' represents activities adding value to the product to improve its competitive market advantage (Simatupang, Piboonrungraj and Williams, 2017). Hawkes and Ruel (2012) also stated that the value chain is a composition of two concepts- adding features to existing products and chains representing associates involved in this process.

However, the value chain concept has been modulated over time and with associated changes in the surrounding system. McPhee and Wheeler (2006) demonstrated the use of an added value chain- an extended form of the traditional linear value chain concept. With the changes in industrial phenomena, they presented the significance of the expanded value creation model. It was recommended that using an added value chain will reduce the risk of losing any opportunities by implementing additional strategic activities. Furthermore, the initial concept of the value chain for the single firms has been moved to the complex perception of the value chain as the firms started to collaborate in improving their performance (Zamora, 2016). It can be stated as the shift in value chain perception from linear to complex and multi-layer perspective (Alves *et al.*, 2022). The remarkable evolution of linear value chain theory can be observed in global value chain theory. Gary Gereffi introduced the concept of a global value chain during the mid-1990s. With the increasing offshore business trend, it was found that the simple value chain is evolving towards a global value chain. Ricciotti (2020) mentioned some of the facts behind this evolution. It was identified that globalization, sustainability, collaboration, agility, flexibility, and intangible assets are the modulators to move the value chain concept into the value network concept. However, Allee (2000) stated that changes in customer behaviour are one of the important factors for value chain evolution. Today's industries are expanding their activities and collaborating with other industries worldwide to improve functionality and performance. The industrial competition has also become global (Anderson, 2000). So, the boundary of value chain perception is desired to be extended to set the global vision. This paradigm shifting also known as moving from value chain to value network (Ricciotti, 2020).

With such changes in the initial perception of the value chain, the importance of these strategic tools is becoming more acknowledged in the current world of industrial evolution. Michal Porter stated the importance of the value chain for competitive advantage- in terms of cost advantage or differentiation. Porter (2001) mentions that analyzing the value chain is the appropriate way of assessing industrial competitive advantage rather than only assessing individual added value to the product or service. Gereffi and Fernandez-Stark (2011) validated this notion by mentioning that value chains offer collaboration among their links that are aimed at improving their market position or competitive advantage. Business units involved in the value chain are collaborated with each other following effective marketing manners so that changes in one unit will improve market values in other units. It is an important step towards competitive advantage to measure operational efficiency and improve accordingly in designated sector of processing. Value chain analysis assists in understanding the interaction between different players of this chain. It combines internal and external data of an industry to provide decisions about its competitive position and resources (Ricciotti, 2020). With such assessment it is then possible to identify desirable changes in the system. Value chain analysis offers a competitive assessment of the whole chain rather than focusing on a single industry. It has also been mentioned as important in assessing upgrades in the chain (Kaplinsky, Morris and Readman, 2002).

Upgrading is a fundamental phase in market competitiveness. So, assessing upgrades within the value chain facilitates understanding the challenges (Gehl Sampath and Vallejo, 2018). Kaplinsky and Morris, (2000) stated four categories of upgrading in value chain- process, product, functional and chain upgrading. They have also provided various indicators to assess upgrading in the value chain. Such indicators are helpful to analyse implementation and performance of upgrading in the industry. For example, process upgrading practices are mostly conducted to improve the process system that will provide quality products with lower production costs. Analyzing the value chain for such upgrading will help to understand the current status of actions that have been undertaken to fulfill the challenges and to plan accordingly (Kaplinsky, Morris and Readman, 2002). Pipkin and Fuentes (2017) conducted a similar study to assess upgrading in the global value chain of agricultural and light manufacturing industries. Different triggers and consequences were identified for such upgrading, which were then used to recommend future improvements in the industrial

upgrade. Angelis-Dimakis, Alexandratou and Balzarini (2016) conducted a value chain upgrading assessment to evaluate the eco-efficiency of the Italian textile industry. The assessment identified several issues at different stages of the value chain, which need to be addressed to improve the industry's overall performance. Additionally, the research by Kenta (2007) serves as another example of a value chain assessment aimed at industrial upgrades. It was demonstrated that industrial upgrading relies on the position of its actors within the value chain. It depends on the activities regarding supply, production, processing, and distribution networks. Considering such studies, value chain analysis can be identified as a crucial tool for industrial upgrade assessment.

2.2.1.1 Current research and value chain theory

With the discussed perception of value chain theory and its application in existing research, it can be said that it is instrumental in analyzing and enhancing industrial systems. It provides a comprehensive framework that spans from raw material acquisition to the final stages of marketing and consumption. This theoretical framework is particularly beneficial for evaluating industrial competitiveness and identifying areas for improvement.

In the context of the present study, which focuses on the overall advancement of the Bangladesh jute industry from cultivation through to the export sector, the value chain theory serves as a fitting foundation. By employing this theory, the research can clearly define its scope and parameters, ensuring a focused discussion that is easily comprehensible. This clarity will allow the researcher to pinpoint relevant key terms and locate necessary information efficiently, thereby facilitating a thorough investigation into the jute industry's dynamics and performance.

2.2.2 Strategic management theory

Strategic management refers to the strategic way of managing industrial function, initiatives and resources following industrial objectives. It is the strategic way of planning, implementing and monitoring actions to make appropriate organizational decision (Haberberg and Rieple, 2008). Omalaja and Eruola (2011) defined strategic management as the course of action that combines strategic planning, its application and post action evaluation. It is the management system of any corporate strategy that starts with making choice of implementation. The overall aim of strategic management is to reconstruct industrial system (working system and people) to obtain desired

performance (production). Organization requires clear strategy to achieve target goals. It needs the strategic decision that satisfy questions like competitive advantage, cost advantage, value creation and sustainability (Rosenberg Hansen and Ferlie, 2016). David, David and David (2020) stated that such strategic decision requires to consider organizational resources, associates, competitors and both internal and external facts to make plan accordingly. It helps to identify weakness and strength of the organization to guide the development. Based on the identified facts, the organization can then set their long-term strategic planning. It can also be stated as comprehensive planning for any organizational improvement (Alharbi, 2024). Comprehensive analysis of organizational situation and to make management planning according to for improvement. Usually, such decisions of action are undertaken by managerial authority of an organization (Wheelen & Hunger, 2008). It can be a collective decision by all managers to set better planning for organizational performance. Hence, strategic management can be marked as significant step towards better organizational performance and competitive advantage (Alkhodary, 2023). By implementing improved management planning, the organization is more likely to achieve a competitive edge in the global market.

Even though it was long time ago (1950-1960) that the concept of strategic management got attention in practice and research, several changes and revolution have subsequently occurred. Particularly the perception of strategic management by Michale Porter in 1985 was the most significant one (Griffin, 2021). It prioritised the focus of strategic management planning in improving competitive position. Porter developed different models and frameworks to identify place that needed improvement and to formulate strategies accordingly as per the competitive requirement. Any organization or industry aiming at developing their business in the global competitive environment can consider porter's five forces model to predict the situation and to develop their strategies accordingly. This framework enables strategy makers to closely examine the dynamics of market competition and implement informed strategies based on their findings (Baburaj and Narayanan, 2016). For instance, Göral (2021) utilized the Five Forces model to evaluate the competitiveness of the Kenyan hotel industry. By constructing questionnaires that focused on various competitive forces, the research aimed to gauge the competitive landscape effectively. The findings highlighted the "Threat of Substitutes" as the most significant force influencing

competition, while the "Bargaining Power of Suppliers" was deemed the least impactful in this context. Similarly, Kabeyi (2018) integrated Porter's model with other analytical frameworks to dissect the competitive dynamics within the global smartphone market. This study reaffirmed the model's effectiveness in analyzing competitive scenarios and providing actionable recommendations for future enhancements in strategy. These examples illustrate the relevance and adaptability of Porter's Five Forces model across different industries, underscoring its utility in strategic decision-making processes.

Recent changes in strategic management approach have been noticed with the shifting toward globalization paradigm (Smith, 2020). Globalization has moved all attention towards international perspective. Industries around the world are working globally in association with each other. It is more about adopting strategies to survive this paradigm and to compete globally.

2.2.2.1 Competitive strategy theory

Porter (1985) mentioned that competition-based strategy is the core of industrial success and excellent performance. It prioritizes competitive advantage in the strategic system. The theory mainly focuses on establishing system that will allow the industry to compete with other industries and to achieve their target position (Omalaja and Eruola, 2011). It is stated by Michael Porter, the founder of strategic management, that competitive advantage is the continuing work of competitive strategic management (Stonehouse and Snowdon, 2007). Both discuss the set of work associated with improving industrial competitive position. Porter (1985) presented generic competitive strategy in this regard that an organization or industry can follow to become competitive with its rival industry. It includes three choices for any organization- differentiation, cost leadership, and focus (Tanwar, 2013).

Here, cost leadership theory focuses on reducing production costs to offer low-priced products to the customer. The quality of product needs to be improved while minimizing its production cost. It will help the industry to become competitive in the market. On the other hand, differentiation is the competitive strategy to produce unique products for which the industry can get competitive prices and position in the market. It can be through developing unique features like product design, brand and service. Finally, with focus competitive strategy, industry can narrow down its target audience or market. In this strategy, industry concentrates on concise segment of market. It has

been mentioned that such strategy is suitable for small industry or firm to narrow down their target (Tanwar, 2013).

2.2.2.2 Marketing mix

Several theories and frameworks have been developed by researchers to assess the marketing strength of organizations and to develop corresponding marketing strategies (Gronroos, 1994; Kartawinata and Wardhana, 2013). The marketing mix is a significant paradigm in marketing management, serving as a valuable assessment tool that aids in strategic planning. Gronroos (1994) describes the marketing mix as a foundational and universal approach to marketing. Furthermore, it is characterized as a potent tool for enhancing the competitive position of any industry (Londhe, 2014). Support for this notion is provided by Khorsheed *et al.* (2020), who affirm the positive effect of the marketing mix on competitive advantage, emphasizing that the elements of the marketing mix function optimally when they operate in concert. This integrated approach assists marketers in making informed decisions concerning product marketing activities, trading, and interactions with both traders and customers (Morgan *et al.*, 2019). Ultimately, these factors contribute significantly to the overall outcomes within an industry (Išoraitė, 2009). Moreover, Slater, Hult and Olson (2010) stated that creative marketing and effective implementation profoundly impact overall firm performance. Therefore, to maintain high performance standards within any industry, it is essential to focus on the effectiveness of marketing strategy and the implementation of the marketing mix.

Marketing is a multifaceted discipline that encompasses various core elements essential for evaluating the effectiveness of any marketing strategy. Historically, the marketing mix has evolved from the foundational 4Ps—product, price, place, and promotion—to more comprehensive frameworks, eventually expanding to 6Ps and currently to 7Ps (Khan, 2014), which include personnel, process, and physical evidence. These components serve as a critical foundation for crafting robust marketing strategies, thus enabling marketing professionals to make informed decisions tailored to their specific industries. Recent studies illustrate the application of these frameworks in diverse sectors. For instance, Tsai, Tang and Chen (2022) employed the 5Ps framework to discern successful marketing strategies, demonstrating its versatility in different contexts. Similarly, Raji (2019) utilized the 5P's

model to develop a healthcare marketing plan aimed at minimizing waste and variation in service delivery. Furthermore, research by Ardianwiliandri, Lukodono and Efranto (2021) highlighted the impact of the 7Ps on enhancing customer satisfaction, indicating that certain elements of the expanded marketing mix are particularly effective in formulating strategies that resonate with consumers. These developments underscore the importance of the marketing mix as a dynamic tool for both strategizing and executing marketing initiatives that ultimately improve customer experience and satisfaction.

2.2.2.3 Current research and rationale for selected strategic theory

As it has been discussed already that strategic management is the process on assessing, planning and implementing appropriate management actions following the requirement. Different theories in strategic management will help to understand the strategic way of any organization that they follow to conduct management planning. It also helps the policy maker to identify appropriate strategic way that an organization is needed based on its present situation.

Current research is aimed at understanding ongoing advancement of Bangladesh Jute industry with as key objective is to comprehend strategies that Bangladesh Jute industry is adopting or planning to adopt in acquiring competitive advancement. Here, strategic management theory (generic competitive strategy) will lead the researcher to understand strategic planning of Bangladesh jute industry. Researchers with knowledge of generic competitive strategy can build up the boundary for strategy assessment. With different examples of scenario in mind, it will be easy for the researcher to understand specific strategic way that Bangladesh jute industry is following. It will also assist researcher in proposing appropriate strategic planning for the industry considering its current scenario.

Along with strategic management theory, marketing strategy is also important to understand strategic decisions of any industry. Marketing mix, as one of the widely used marketing assessment tools, will help the researcher to understand current marketing scenario of Bangladesh jute industry and to plan accordingly. The marketing mix has proven effective in enhancing competitive advantage (Darmawan and Grenier, 2021). Thus, it can be a valuable tool for advancing the competitive position of the Bangladesh jute industry.

2.3 INDUSTRIAL DOMAIN TO EXPERIENCE THE ADVANCEMENT

As noted earlier, current research involves several key terms that are essential for understanding the topic at hand. These terms include industrial advancement and the various sectors of an industry that experience such advancements. The previous section of this chapter has already explored the concept of advancement and its connection to current research. It was identified from the discussion that advancement is any form of innovation or upgrading with new ideas, technologies, and improved strategies to attain a competitive advantage in the market (Romero *et al.* 2017). However, this section of the chapter will pivot towards an examination of specific industrial sectors that undergo these advancements, elucidating the interconnectedness between industrial advancement and the relevant domains. Furthermore, this discussion will highlight their significance in the current research landscape, ultimately aiding in the identification of existing research gaps that need to be focused on current research.

The Manual (2005) provides an innovation guideline that categorizes industrial activities into four key sectors: production, processing, organizational management, and marketing. Each of these sectors plays a critical role in enhancing overall performance and has been identified as a focal point for industrial innovation. Supporting this perspective, Humphrey and Schmitz (2002) emphasize that industrial enhancements can manifest across various dimensions, including production, product processing, functional management, and inter-sectoral collaborations. Thus, essential domains of manufacturing operations can be delineated as production, product processing, operational management, and marketing. In light of these frameworks, the present research endeavors to evaluate each of these domains within Bangladesh's jute industry. The objective is to gain insights into their collective impact on the industry's advancement, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of the pathways for innovation and improvement in this vital sector. This assessment will highlight the current state of the jute industry's operations and identify potential areas for strategic enhancement.

2.3.1 Production domain of the manufacturing industry

The concept of the 'production domain' plays a pivotal role in the broader value chain framework, particularly as it relates to inbound logistics. This domain is integral to industrial operations, encompassing the various activities and management practices that govern inventory control. Inventory, in this context, refers to any asset or component utilized within an industry to facilitate efficient operational processes (Panigrahi *et al.*, 2021; Sharma and Arya, 2016). In the manufacturing sector, raw materials constitute a critical segment of inventory and significantly influence the quality of the finished product (Ali *et al.*, 2011). Variations in the quality of raw materials can directly impact the standards of the final outputs. Thus, it is imperative to ensure that raw materials meet established quality benchmarks prior to the initiation of production processes (Panigrahi *et al.*, 2015; Panigrahi *et al.*, 2022). Ensuring high-quality raw materials, along with their timely availability, fosters a competitive edge within the marketplace. Furthermore, the consistent evaluation of inventory management and raw material quality is essential in tracking organizational progress and identifying potential challenges. By implementing regular assessments, firms can enhance their operational strategies, ultimately yielding a positive correlation with overall performance.

In the jute industry, raw jute is paramount to its successful operation. It is the raw material for the industry, which comes from the agricultural field. Different agricultural resources have also been marked from existing literature that are being used as raw materials in other manufacturing industries. For example, wax, resins, fiber, oil, starch, sugar, wood, pigment agents, food products and energy products (fuel). (Beckman, Borchers and Jones, 2013; Trostle and Seeley, 2013; Sen and Reddy 2011). Therefore, advancement in this sector of raw material production is crucial for any manufacturing industry to secure a competitive position in the global market.

A brief discussion on advancements in various agricultural strategies are presented below to outline its connection to current research.

2.3.1.1 Advancement in increasing agricultural production

Existing literature has recommended different production strategies and approaches to increase yield. For instance, agricultural expansion, intensification (Pywell *et al.*, 2015), vertical farming (Benke and Tomkins, 2017), improved variety use, and other

land management techniques (soil, water, nutrient, and other resource management) (Sainju, Whitehead and Singh, 2003; Fan *et al.*, 2012).

Agricultural land expansion has long been practiced as an approach to increasing crop yields. It indicates the process of undertaking lands that are not being cultivated. These are either in conditions unsuitable for crop cultivation (waterlogged, improper drainage system, drought condition and salinity) or under urban civilization or as forests. Haq, Ghosal and Ghosh (2004) demonstrated that using waterlogged lands in Bangladesh can increase the yield of different crops. The system was named soil-less farming (hydroponics), where the waterlogged lands can be tuned into suitable cultivated situations to grow high-yielding crops. In this system, floating beds are prepared with organic materials (water hyacinth, aquatic weed), and crops are grown over it. Such an approach was beneficial for maintaining biodiversity and conserving nutrients in water. Bassu *et al.* (2009) also demonstrated alternative waterlogging strategies in extending production. The research suggested that early sowing of wheat (early cultivars) is suitable for the Mediterranean environment to get effective yield and to avoid any loss due to the waterlogged condition afterward. However, both studies mostly focused on emphasizing the effectiveness of wetland cultivation as an alternative to increasing production. They do not present data on implemented land expansion practices that can be considered to decide on future improvements. In contrast, Kaur *et al.* (2020) bring to light the critical challenges associated with waterlogged cultivation and emphasize the need for a robust assessment toolkit. While their reliance on existing literature provides a solid foundation, it also points to a significant gap in original research that evaluates the effectiveness of current management practices. This indicates a need for empirical studies that not only document the challenges but also contribute to actionable strategies for enhancing agricultural productivity in problematic landscapes.

Other research can be found in the available literature that proposes improved techniques and their possibilities in extensive cultivation. Saleem *et al.* (2020) proposed effective agricultural techniques for future jute farmers in China, cultivating jute in mining areas. Mining areas are generally unsuitable for crop cultivation due to the toxic nature of the environment. Both the soil and environment around a mining area are toxic due to the presence of heavy metals. Saleem *et al.* (2020) indicated that the additional application of phosphorus (P) can influence phytoremediation activities

in the mentioned jute varieties (HongTieGuXuan and GuBaChangJia) to eliminate the toxic effect of Copper (Cu) present in the site. However, the extent of their effectiveness in real-world applications remains to be validated. Further discussion in farmer level or with the researcher may reveal the success of implementing the proposed practice. Intercropping is another cultivation strategy that can increase production with the required changes in the pattern. Researchers have proposed different non-cultivable lands (coastal lands, hilly lands, char lands) in Bangladesh that can be used with improved intercropping patterns to get higher yields (Akter *et al.*, 2010; Kadir *et al.*, 2021; Karim, Higuchi and Nawata, 2018). Bybee-Finley and Ryan (2018) also presented examples of successful intercropping systems being adopted commercially. However, their reliance on existing literature that does not thoroughly capture the complexities of real-world agricultural production. While the examples of successfully implemented intercropping systems are promising, they underscore the necessity for empirical assessments to better understand the practicality of these methods to implement in diverse agricultural contexts.

In addition to horizontal expansion, vertical expansion is another strategy identified by the research to increase crop yield along with the growing demand (Beacham, Vickers and Monaghan, 2019; Benke and Tomkins, 2017). It is also known as urban agriculture, where people can grow their desired crop nearby within the urban building to satisfy their food demand (Chatterjee, Debnath and Pal, 2020). Some of the existing practices of commercial vertical farming around the world are Sky Greens (Singapore), Mirai Company (Japan) and Valcent Company (North America). (Benke and Tomkins, 2017). The setting of vertical farming varies based on its different factors including crop varieties, plant growth media, growth surface, stacking storeyed, lightening system, air conditioning, environmental controlling system, nutrient management and system management protocol (Beacham, Vickers and Monaghan, 2019; Benke and Tomkins, 2017; Van Gerrewey, Boon and Geelen, 2022). Researchers are evaluating the effectiveness of this system in increasing production (Banerjee and Adenaeuer, 2014; Karemangingo *et al.*, 2019; Shubha *et al.*, 2019; YESİL and TATAR, 2020). Toulaitos, Dodd and McAinsh (2016) demonstrated that vertical farming can be conducted to get an increased yield of lettuce. Similar results were found for barley fodder using vertical farming as a controlled cultivation approach (YESİL and TATAR,

2020). However, the advancement in vertical farming is still under process and needs further research for effective implementation.

Improved variety development represents a significant stage of innovation in recent agricultural advancements. Plant breeding technology enables researchers to create desired crop varieties resistant to harsh environmental conditions and produce high-quality yields (Qaim, 2020). Researchers worldwide are assessing the progress of such innovations. For instance, Idrissi *et al.* (2019) examined the breeding progress of enhanced lentil varieties cultivated in the field. Their study evaluated the adaptability and stability of these varieties to recommend effective cultivation strategies. The findings provide valuable insights into the lentil varieties used in agriculture, which is crucial for understanding the implementation level of developed varieties. However, a notable trend in crop variety improvement research is the predominant focus on laboratory evaluations of quality traits, often in isolation from field conditions. While such laboratory-centric approaches can significantly enhance specific quality attributes, they may fall short in delivering a holistic perspective on the actual progress and adaptation of the advancements within the agricultural landscape. This gap underscores the necessity of bridging laboratory findings with real-world performance and acceptance to foster a more comprehensive understanding of crop variety advancement.

2.3.1.1.1 Production advancement of raw jute in Bangladesh

From the perspective of advancement in Bangladesh jute production, existing literature highlights different land expansions and intensification advancements. For example, the recommendations put forth by Rahman *et al.* (2015) regarding the integration of jute into the cropping pattern of the Tangail region underscore a significant shift from traditional agricultural practices. Their proposal to adopt a mustard-boro-jute-T. Aman rotation instead of the conventional mustard-boro-T. Aman is a strategic move aimed at optimizing land use and improving agricultural productivity. This innovative approach leverages the cultivation of improved rice varieties, which creates an optimal window for jute planting, potentially enhancing both economic returns for farmers and agricultural sustainability in the medium-high land systems. Hossain *et al.* (2020) further contribute to this discourse by exploring alternative cropping patterns that include jute in conjunction with winter vegetable crops. By positioning jute cultivation as a seed crop within this system, they emphasize

the dual benefits of maximizing land utility while ensuring seed availability, an essential resource for farmers. However, while these studies present compelling arguments and potential pathways for jute cultivation, they remain primarily within the realm of field trials and exploratory research. The critical aspect of translating these proposals into tangible outcomes lies in the implementation within actual farming contexts. Understanding the integration of these cropping patterns will be vital for assessing their practical viability and understanding the dynamics of farmer adoption. Aiming at this, current research will emphasize to understand current practices that is being adopted by the jute industry following the advancement.

On the other hand, research on jute-related land expansion was also found to focus on char lands of Bangladesh. Bangladesh is a country with around 0.83 million hectares of char land. A huge portion of this char lands (.52-.79) million hectares are suitable for agricultural cultivation (Mahmud *et al.*, 2020). Jute researchers in Bangladesh explained that the transformation of this char lands into an extended jute cultivation area can be a great step towards improving yield as well as the financial situation of the villagers (Chanda *et al.*, 2018; Mahmud *et al.*, 2020; Sarker, Monira and Uddin, 2020; Sarker *et al.*, 2022). It has been mentioned that jute can be a great combination to include in the existing cropping pattern in char lands (Mahmud *et al.*, 2020; Sarker *et al.*, 2022). Incorporating jute in the improved cropping pattern can allow jute farmers to utilize this spare land effectively to get additional jute yield. For example, Millet (BARI Kaon-2)-Jute (O-9897)-T. Aman (Gainja) was recommended instead of the existing Millet (Local)-Fallow-T. Aman (Gainja) (Mahmud *et al.*, 2020). However, the studies also recommended future research to assess the use of these strategies in commercial practice.

In addition to the char lands, Bangladesh has a huge portion of coastal and hilly areas that remain uncultivable or limited cultivable due to its environmental and hydrological conditions. Only a limited variety of crops adapted to such an environment can be grown here. The researcher has proposed agroforestry as the most sustainable and efficient agricultural practice to perform in these hilly areas (Hanif *et al.*, 2018; Nath *et al.*, 2016). Farmers can cultivate crops alongside the trees/timbers in agroforestry. It allows them to perform combined cultivation. Therefore, such an area can be turned into a great opportunity for agricultural expansion with the application of appropriate techniques and in a sustainable way. Piya *et al.* (2019) conducted a study in

Potuakhali, indicating that effective potassium fertilizer contributes positively to jute productivity in coastal regions. It was identified that with effective fertilizer and treatment, jute production could be increased in such coastal regions of Bangladesh. While their findings underscore the potential for increased yield through scientific fertilization techniques, the research is largely constrained by repeating established field trial methodologies. Similarly, Al-Mamun *et al.* (2017) focused on the motivational factors for jute cultivation in hilly and coastal areas. Their emphasis on developing advanced strategies for quality seed production to address the seed shortages in the country is commendable. However, it raises questions about the scalability of these strategies and their actual effectiveness in real-world scenarios. Hossain *et al.* (2020) explored alternative approaches by integrating jute cultivation as an intercrop in agroforestry systems, specifically in young litchi and mango orchards. This proposition points towards a more sustainable agricultural practice, yet it lacks empirical evidence on its practical use in farming contexts. Overall, while the literature presents promising theories and methodologies for enhancing jute production, it conspicuously lacks comprehensive studies that bridge the gap between theoretical strategies and their practical adaptation at the commercial level.

In terms of variety improvements in jute, existing literature has provided information regarding different improved jute varieties that have been developed so far to obtain increased yield in adverse conditions (Khatun *et al.*, 2009; Akter *et al.*, 2009; Mukul *et al.*, 2021; Miah *et al.*, 2020). The studies mainly demonstrated the performance level of these varieties in the different trial stages, which again requires understanding their actual implementation and acceptance in commercial use. As noted by Lenaerts, Collard and Demont (2019), it is essential to develop these varieties not only in a laboratory setting but also to ensure they are readily accessible in the market. This accessibility is crucial for their proper distribution to farmers.

Moreover, several developmental initiatives are being undertaken in Bangladesh to improve its jute production. However, most of these actions remain at the laboratory level or are in the field-testing stage, with limited implementation at the commercial level. Hereby, the present research aims to understand the current state of the advancements in field application by discussing it with the expertise to propose future action plan.

2.3.2 Industrial processing domain

Industrial processing is another essential primary activity in the value chain after the inbound logistics. It is represented by the category named 'operations' in the value chain (Dubey *et al.*, 2020). All kind of activities related to transforming the raw material or input into the desired output is associated with this operational service. Esmailian, Behdad and Wang (2016) also mentioned that industrial processing is not only about product processing but also indicates different operational or management activities associated with the processing. So, in other words, the industrial processing sector can be linked with the operational management domain that controls activities and operations for desired output (Khanna, 2015). It is a huge domain of any industry that governs a range of strategic actions for the industry, including planning, product processing, HR management, technological improvement, and standardizing the overall production system (Khanna, 2015). It creates value from the raw material and helps to increase industrial production (Porter, 2001). This combined sector has a profound impact on the overall industrial performance. Hence, it is an important industry domain to advance the overall system. Given this context, current research aimed to assess this sector of Bangladesh's jute industry to identify potential advancement in response to global jute demand. However, current research has focused solely on evaluating the product processing aspect of this domain, which includes the strategic processing methods, the technologies and machinery used, the processes that add value to the product, and the competitive advantages of both the product and its processing methods. Various challenges have been identified in the existing literature relating to these facts that were recommended for significant improvements. Considering this, some activities involved in product processing and their advancements are discussed below to identify research gaps within this area.

2.3.2.1 Improvements in processing strategy

A standard processing system is the prior requirement of getting the demanded quality and quantity of product. This can be achieved by setting up effective action strategies. Gemser and Leenders (2001) demonstrated the importance of strategic design in product development to attain competitive advancement. The research indicated that it is paramount to plan for industrial processing design if the industry is looking forward to improving its competitive position. Lasalewo *et al.* (2016) defined such strategic

action as competitive strategy. This can be the actions involved in advancing a product's features, production, processing, and delivery. ElMaraghy *et al.* (2013) mentioned product variety management (value creation, product combination selection, standard product structure) as another form of processing advancement to satisfy the competitive market.

Industries are more focused these days on advancing their processing capabilities for diverse product demands. The customer's choice for the product is changing every day. Hence, the industrial processing paradigm faces a challenging phase in adopting a sustainable and profitable processing strategy (ElMaraghy *et al.*, 2012). It has been observed that industrial personnel construct such strategic planning based on existing circumstances and necessities (Walker, 2013). It follows the situation demand and makes a competitive strategy accordingly. In this matter, Randeree and Youha (2009) prioritized the importance of a performance management system to decide effective strategic actions. Critical evaluation of overall performance can be an outstanding way to make effective strategic decisions. Leong *et al.* (2020) have demonstrated the use of different performance indicators to identify optimized processing strategies. It can help to identify flexible and effective strategies to bring improvement in product quality. After analysing the performance indicators, industries are implementing different strategies that will improve their processing. Sim *et al.* (2022) evaluated the implementation of Lean Six Sigma (LSS) practices as an advanced strategy for improving product quality. In the medical device manufacturing industry in Malaysia, this strategy was found to have a positive impact on quality performance. This serves as an example of the research focused on assessing advancements in processing strategies.

Existing literature on the Bangladesh jute industry has mentioned the processing of jute fibres that are being followed or recommended for the industry to improve product quality and variety. Shahinur *et al.* (2022) examined various processing strategies for the production of jute-based bio-composites. There is a growing global demand for environmentally friendly composites, and jute, being an eco-friendly crop, is increasingly sought after for its potential to produce high-quality bio-composites. Shahinur *et al.* (2022) mainly identify several challenges, including issues related to processing technology, the implementation of appropriate strategies, and the lack of a cost-effective approach to achieving high-quality production. It is important to note

that this research does not evaluate the existing advancements in processing techniques that are being followed by the industry. In terms of implementing operational practices within the industry, Haider and Rafiquzzaman (2023) discussed the importance of implementing Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) practices in the Bangladesh jute industry to enhance overall performance. Various TPM practices, namely Kobetsu Kaizen, 5S, Planned Maintenance, Autonomous Maintenance, and Education and Training, have been observed to effectively reduce industrial losses, including equipment failure and manufacturing defects. However, the study primarily focused on assessing the efficiency of the framework and recommending effective strategies, while it did not address the current practices within the industry. This oversight results in a lack of updated information regarding advanced practices in the processing domain to meet global demand.

2.3.2.2 Advancement in technological use

In order to get processing advancement, technological advancement is paramount. This plays a crucial role in the evolutionary development of the industrial sector (Dosi and Nelson, 2010), particularly through the integration of smart technology across all components of the processing system. It involves digitalizing the entire manufacturing ecosystem to ensure competitiveness on a global scale. Rosnah *et al.* (2003) demonstrated in their research that the level of technological advancement serves as a key indicator for assessing the global competitiveness of an industry. It has also been mentioned that the combination of advanced technology and processing strategy has a significant impact on overall performance (Garrido-Vega, Jimenez and Morita, 2015). Effective management of this combination can lead to achieving a competitive position in the market. Supporting this idea, Rothaermel (2008) emphasized the significance of continuous technological innovation as essential for maintaining a sustained competitive advantage. Consistent innovation is crucial for long-term success. Recent research by Al Mubarak and Hamdan (2023) also explored the impact of technological advancements on firm performance and sustainable competitive advantage. It has been found that advancements in technology positively correlate with enhanced firm performance and quality production. Technological upgrades can help lower production costs, reduce production time, ensure high-quality output, and deliver the desired quantity of products on time (Kasongo, Sithole and Buchana, 2023). By implementing advanced technology, industries position

themselves ahead in the competitive market. Supporting this notion, research conducted by Fu (2022) on industrial advancement and digitalization of the Chinese manufacturing industry demonstrated that upgrades in the manufacturing industry have a positive relation with technology incorporation. Application of different technological upgrade including artificial intelligent (AI), automated technology and Internet of thing (IoT) are getting high demand in global market in recent era as form of technological innovation. For instance, Yam *et al.* (2003) discussed the technological transformation of Hong Kong manufacturing industries into an i-supply chain system to march towards an i-competitive model. It has been recommended that with the implementation of suggested internet-based technology, the industry will obtain improved operation system. Chakraborty and Biswas (2020) have provided a broad picture of 3D printing demand in the textile and fashion industry. With the recent advancement in technology, 3D printing is getting huge demand over conventional manufacturing. Researchers around the world are evaluating the implementation of advanced technology and its validity in industrial outcomes to assess how performance can be improved with the elimination of any drawbacks. For instance, Huang, Talla Chicoma and Huang (2019) conducted interviews and surveys to assess factors that were hindering the effective implementation of advanced technology in micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Peru. This provided the industry with notable recommendations to improve their system in updating technology. Manglani, Hodge, and Oxenham (2019) also conducted research to identify the usefulness of IoT applications in the spinning industry. It was aimed at understanding any challenges in the progress of implementing IoT technology. Such research assesses the progress of integrating updated technology into processing systems and identifies the challenges associated with it.

However, similar research to evaluate or assess technological upgrades in Bangladesh's jute industry is absent. Existing literature on the jute industry primarily discusses various challenges and suggests a few upgrades that could lead to prosperity (Alimuzzaman *et al.*, 2024; Hossain, Nishu and Freelance Researcher 2021). For example, Alimuzzaman *et al.* (2024) highlighted the benefits of using updated machinery, specifically the mechanical left-handed dobby loom with a cutting arrangement, compared to traditional production methods. This modern technology is suggested as a profitable and sustainable option for the jute industry in Bangladesh,

particularly in the context of its competitive global market. However, the advancement of any industry relies on the practical implementation of upgraded technology. Therefore, it is required to be assured that the machineries are being used in the commercial stage to get the desired outcome.

Hossain, Nishu and Freelance Researcher (2021) noted that Bangladesh's jute industry primarily relies on outdated machinery and needs technological improvements to enhance both production and quality. However, their research lacks detailed information about the current machinery and technologies in use within the industry. This gap makes it difficult to evaluate the technological advancements that the industry is experiencing. So, it can be observed that more information is needed about the current status of the Bangladesh jute industry and its technological upgrade to plan for further implementation. No update about current technological practice can be found in existing literature, as can be found in the early years by Kibria and Tisdell (1983). The research pictured technological advancement in the weaving sector of the Bangladesh jute industry. Therefore, similar research or assessing the industry for its technological position is vital to make further recommendations.

2.3.2.3 Advancement in sustainable processing practice

In addition to implementing different processing strategies and technological upgrades, assuring sustainable production is another vital concern in the advancement of the processing domain in any industry. Compared to traditional manufacturing strategy, present manufacturers are more willing to turn towards sustainable manufacturing to deal with limited natural resources and growing customer demand (Madu, 2022). Such a strategy is also assumed to offer positive firm performance and competitive advantage in the current global market. Pande and Adil (2023) analysed competitive values for sustainable manufacturing framework. It was identified that pollution control as a sustainable approach could assist the industry with competitive advantages like cost-benefit and resource conservation. Rusinko (2007) validated the assumption that sustainable manufacturing practices lead to competitive outcomes through research on green manufacturing strategies. This study demonstrated that adopting a green manufacturing strategy can add competitive value by reducing manufacturing costs and improving product quality. Additionally, Hermundsdottir and Aspelund (2022) highlighted the positive impact of sustainable manufacturing strategies on overall firm performance. Their research showed that

implementing environmental innovations leads to better firm performance compared to a social sustainability approach.

Many industries around the world are undergoing various structural and strategic changes to comply with sustainable production regulations. For example, the Indonesian tannery industry has adopted green technology to reduce waste (Ramdhani *et al.*, 2017). The implementation of such green technology can provide benefits from environmental, financial, and social perspectives. However, this research focuses solely on a single sustainable practice within the tannery industry, neglecting to highlight other sustainable actions that are also being implemented. Evaluating industrial progress involves recognizing all the practices currently being implemented.

Cai *et al.* (2019) detailed the use of energy-saving and emission reduction (ESER) strategy as shifting towards green production. Besides explaining the implementation of ESER at the industrial level, the research demonstrated the current use and benefits of this strategy at Zcrubber Group Co. Ltd. It was identified that ESER could be considered an effective, sustainable strategy in reducing emissions, energy consumption, and environmental pollution. The research neglects to address other sustainable practices considered for industrial advancement, primarily focusing on a single sustainable practice to demonstrate its effectiveness and practical implementation.

Talapatra and Gaine (2019) implemented Lean Six Sigma (LSS) and environmental framework in the Bangladesh jute industry to observe the impact of undertaken activities on reducing negative environmental impact. They experienced difficulties in implementing the actions, including continuous resource management monitoring. It was also identified that the jute industries in Bangladesh are unaware of the LSS model and reluctant to implement such strategies for environmental safety. The research does not aim to evaluate industrial advancements in sustainable practices. Instead, it seeks to demonstrate the effectiveness of existing sustainable practices using specific assessment tools. Further investigation is needed to assess the progress of these practices.

Similar to advancements in processing and technology, existing literature has been deficient in explaining the current state of sustainable practices adopted by

Bangladesh's jute industry to meet global demand. Therefore, to assess progress in this sector, it is crucial to identify current practices and to plan for further competitive advancements.

2.3.3 Industrial marketing domain

Marketing is a crucial component of any industry that interacts with customers. In the value chain model, it is identified as part of outbound logistics and marketing sales (Dubey *et al.*, 2020). Outbound logistics primarily focus on activities related to product delivery and distribution, serving as a bridge between the product and the customer and helping to balance this relationship (Vitezic and Vitezic, 2015). This sector is dedicated to promoting products or services through various activities like advertising and communicating the product's value to encourage customer purchases and generate market demand. It plays a vital role in overall industrial performance by being the final point in the distribution process, ultimately determining whether a product reaches the customer or not (Slater, Hult and Olson, 2010). Additionally, the outbound logistics or marketing department significantly impacts competitive advantage by managing the global supply chain network. They implement multi-channel strategies to balance supply and production while addressing challenges related to transportation, inventory management, and identifying suitable customers and markets (Bhatnagar and Teo, 2009).

Moreover, the success and growth of any industry are closely linked to advancements in its marketing approach. These advancements facilitate continuous improvements in quality production and new product development (Veryzer, 2005). Therefore, to maintain high-performance standards in any industry, it is essential to monitor activities associated with the marketing domain (Feng, Morgan and Rego, 2015).

Several theories and frameworks have been developed through research to assess an organization's marketing capabilities and to formulate an appropriate marketing strategy (Gronroos, 1994; Kartawinata and Wardhana, 2013). These tools help identify the current position of the firm's marketing strategy and recognize any advancements occurring within the industry.

2.3.3.1 Advancement in the marketing strategy

With the advancement of the global market, industries are facing challenges in improving their marketing approaches (Skare and Soriano, 2021). Sudirjo (2023)

proposed various marketing tactics that can assist future marketing managers in responding to demand. For example, these tactics include identifying the target customer group for a specific product, conducting proper market segmentation, effectively utilizing advanced technology, optimizing packaging and distribution, setting competitive pricing, and implementing strategies to manage brand reputation. Golob and Podnar (2007) analyzed comparative marketing strategies of around 18 European Union firms to understand their relationship with a competitive advantage. Many firms were found to practice more distribution and quality marketing strategies, whereas others were using price and quality product strategies. However, the research indicated that distribution and quality management mix strategies are more durable compared to pricing and quality mix strategies. Nahar *et al.* (2021) also conducted similar aimed research to analyze marketing strategies adopted by Banking industries in Bangladesh to achieve a competitive advantage. The research prioritized brand value and customer satisfaction-related marketing strategies for competitive advantage. Moreover, the studies discussed different marketing strategies that the industries are adopting in response to their competitive advancement. Industries that possess a strong understanding of their market position and have well-planned strategies are more likely to succeed in meeting consumer demand (Aldaihani *et al.*, 2023). However, existing literature notably lacks similar research on analyzing the advancement in marketing strategies adopted by the Bangladesh jute industry.

For instance, Akter, Sadekin and Islam (2020) conducted research on the potential of the jute market in Australia. Their study primarily focused on assessing the demand for Bangladeshi jute in the Australian market and proposing various market solutions, including product design, distribution, promotion, and pricing, to enhance current export conditions. However, the research did not examine the current marketing practices that the Bangladeshi jute industry is using to identify any gap in the competitive advancement. Peu (2019) also conducted research on the market potentiality of Bangladesh DJPs. The research emphasised future research to work on identifying competitive marketing strategies for the industry. Similar statement has also come from Akter (2015) prioritizing the assessment of marketing challenges and competitive strategy for Bangladesh jute industry. In this context, Islam (2017) studied the raw jute marketing channel of Bangladesh jute industry and identified different

challenges that the industry is experiencing. However, updated research with validated data is required to decide competitive marketing strategy for the industry.

In terms of discussing advancement in industrial marketing, packaging and labelling of product comes with a great importance. Marketing is the industrial domain to represent product to its consumer. Proper presentation of the product with appropriate information is paramount. Nancarrow, Tiu Wright and Brace (1998) stated that proper labelling and packaging with attractive information about product can be a great tool to acquire competitive advantages over other substitutes. Labelling on a package of product can be very useful in catching customer attention and to inform them about competitive attributes of the product. Rundh (2013) also indicated the importance of packaging in marketing in terms of communication. However, the research mentioned that innovative idea needs to be generate in packaging to reduce manufacturing cost and negative impact on environment. The case study was conducted to identify different challenges that effective packaging has and to suggest solution for new packaging idea. Despite of packaging and labelling being such an important part of marketing, no research evidence is present in existing literature regarding Bangladesh jute market. Some research discussed different challenges regarding proper labelling, export barrier and packaging of jute product from Bangladesh (Moniruzzaman *et al.*, 2024). However, no primary evidence is there to understand practicing actions that Bangladesh jute industry is following to meet the challenge and to satisfy global marketing demand.

Product pricing is another important consideration in marketing decision to achieve competitive advancement. Different industry applies different strategies in their product pricing to get the competitive position in market. So, advancement in pricing strategies can also bring prosper to the firm performance. Azad and Shankar Singh (2019) demonstrated positive correlation between pricing strategy and customer retention. It has been indicated that price is one of the important factors considered by customer in selecting product. Therefore, keeping price within customer's preference allow the company or industry to become their favourite. Here, Azad and Shankar Singh (2019) recommended penetration pricing strategy to retain customer. Customer observed in this study was found to have preference on product price over the quality. Another pricing strategy named 'Innovation in pricing' has been found be new in the market to achieve competitive advantage (Hinterhuber and Liozu, 2014; Hinterhuber

and Liozu, 2017). It is the pricing strategy to maintain both organizational profit and customer satisfaction. Hinterhuber and Liozu (2014) developed a roadmap to guide implementation of innovation in pricing strategy. The roadmap indicated several steps that can be adopted to follow the pricing strategy. The steps are need-based market segmentation, pay-for-performance, goo-better-best market segmentation and zero as special price. The study provided a full guidance for industrial personnel who want to improve their pricing strategy and follow innovative approach. Zhang *et al.* (2023) also suggested some advanced pricing strategies for innovative product in market. It was stated that pricing for any innovative product should not be something that the consumer regret afterwards. It will drop customer's interest towards the product. So, policy makers should set pricing for innovative product in a way to avoid any selling risk and to improve product demand. Indounas (2015) demonstrated the impact of implementing strategic pricing on firm performance. Adoption of advanced strategic pricing was found to have positive impact on industrial performance measures namely profitability, brand awareness, customer satisfaction, total revenue, corporate reputation and cost effectiveness. Moreover, pricing is one of the strategic sectors in marketing that has a great interconnection with industrial advancement. Changes in industrial's competitive situation also alter its optimal pricing choice (Pettersen, 2016). So, analysing pricing strategy of any industry can picture any advancement in in overall industrial system. As discussed above, several research are being conducted on evaluating pricing strategies of industries around the world to identify effective one. For instance, Yan (2008) conducted research on identifying optimum pricing strategy for retailing industry that will offer maximum profit outcome. Ambachew (2012) also conducted similar research on assessing pricing strategy on audio CD music industry. The research additionally identified different determinants and factor associated with pricing decision. The revealed relationship between pricing and determinants was recommended to take measures for future pricing decision making. However, existing literature lacks such research to analyse pricing strategy in Bangladesh jute industry. No research work has been conducted in Bangladesh jute industry to discuss their existing pricing strategy and to assess any advancement in this sector to meet global competitive position. Considering the gap, current research will focus on studying the marketing strategies that Bangladesh jute industry is practicing currently to meet global demand including packaging, labelling and pricing strategy, and to propose plan for future improvements.

2.3.3.2 Advancement in marketing technology

Implementation of standard technology in marketing and sales approaches can speed up the process and obtain more customers. Digital marketing is one of the effective tools to reach desired customers within a short period. Compared to traditional marketing, digital or online marketing covers a huge audience and even targets audiences from around the world (Krizanova *et al.*, 2019). Advanced marketing is more of e-marketing and provides strong communication opportunities with consumers. With the use of e-commerce and the availability of different social commerce platforms, it has been easier to understand the customers and to design the products accordingly (Tajvidi, Wang and Hajli, 2018). Advanced technology in marketing data analysis has brought great prospects to understand customer's preferences and to act consequently in improving product quality. Kumar and Pansari (2016) emphasized that firm performance improves with higher consumer engagement. The more consumers are involved in product design and express their preferences, the better the product quality becomes. Technological advancements also create opportunities to influence consumer behaviour in a positive way. Furthermore, effective marketing provides customers with easy access to product information before making a purchase. Producers and traders can easily gather feedback from customers and make updates accordingly (Corniani, 2006).

Recently, in the period of the pandemic (COVID-19), it was observed that digital marketing introduced a new turn in market communication (Alshaketheep *et al.*, 2020; Meshko and Savinova, 2020). Consumers preferred digital marketing over conventional marketing while they were bound to stay home. Online marketing brought them easy access to the products they required. Digital marketing capabilities (DMCs) emerged from digital marketing has been found to have higher profitable outcomes compared to that of classical marketing capabilities (CMCs). DMCs offer firms with higher revenues, cost performance, imperfect imitability, rarity and potentiality. Nwankpa and Roumani (2016) stated that digital marketing offers a firm a competitive position in innovation and firm performance. Firms applying digital marketing in their system can develop new ideas and innovations to attract more customers that consequently bring progress in overall performance. Cvitanović, (2018) acknowledged that digital marketing or multi-channel marketing has great positive impact on

customer satisfaction and competitive advantage. With implementation of such technology-based marketing, any firm can achieve real-time customer interaction, unique customer experience and higher customer brand recognition.

However, marketers around the world are experiencing different challenges with the adaptation of advanced marketing approaches (Verma, Rathee and Malik, 2023). Existing research can be observed in analysing the implementation of digital marketing or advanced technological tools in the industrial marketing sector. For instance, Eze *et al.* (2019) discussed the implementation of mobile marketing in SME to assess associated factors and challenges. Researchers identified different mediator and future improvements in mobile marketing implementation as they analysed the existing practice from people's perception regarding mobile marketing adoption. However, no research has been found in existing literatures that has discussed or analysed advanced marketing technology use in Bangladesh jute industry., So, this area of current practice is also unknown in Bangladesh's jute industry perspective that needs to be revealed to plan for future improvement.

Moreover, existing literature on the marketing advancement of Bangladesh's jute industry was only found to explore the market potentiality of the industry rather than identifying the marketing strategies that the industry is adopting to meet global demand (Akter, 2015; Peu, 2019; Islam, 2017; Sharna and Kamruzzaman, 2020). To make future decisions, the industry needs updated information regarding their current practice and opportunities to make competitive plan accordingly. So, current research is aimed to bridge the gap by assessing existing practices that are being conducted by the industry in practical situations to understand their level of industrial advancement and to assist the industry in making informative action plan.

2.4 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The recent discourse surrounding industrial advancement has culminated in the establishment of a conceptual framework aimed at steering current research to meet its specific objectives. This framework emphasizes a focused exploration of three pivotal domains within the jute industry: production, processing, and marketing. By concentrating on these domains, the study aspires to foster a comprehensive understanding of the industry's adaptation to the ever-evolving global demand.

Insights gleaned from the works of Humphrey and Schmitz (2002) and Manual (2005) underscore the critical nature of these domains in facilitating progress across various industrial landscapes.

Figure 5: Conceptual framework

Furthermore, current research will delve into the core components of each domain, focusing on various critical aspects like field strategies, the implementation of field technologies, innovations in industrial processing, advancements in industrial technology, sustainable processing practices, marketing strategies, pricing dynamics, export barriers, distribution methodologies, and promotional tactics. As noted by Romero *et al.* (2017) industrial innovation relies on these actions—advanced technology, next-generation production processes, strategies, and sustainable approaches—to achieve a competitive edge and effectively meet customer demands. Additionally, Kaplinsky and Morris (2000) highlighted process, product, functional, and chain upgrading as essential elements in fostering advancement. Moreover, the thorough analysis of each domain, approached individually, permits the investigation of a spectrum of advancements that are paramount for the jute industry's overall success.

2.5 SUMMARY OF THE CHAPTER AND RESEARCH GAP

This chapter presents a critical review of the literature pertinent to the outlined research objectives. The central focus is on evaluating the current developments within Bangladesh's jute industry, with an emphasis on aligning it with anticipated global demand. To facilitate a thorough evaluation, the analysis is organized into three key domains: production, processing, and marketing—each of which plays a vital role in fostering industrial growth and innovation. Existing studies underscore the significance of these three areas for advancement in the jute sector (Humphrey and Schmitz, 2002; Manual, 2005). For any industry—including jute—that aspires to improve its operational effectiveness, it is imperative to undertake strategic actions within these domains. This chapter elaborates on the existing body of literature regarding advancements and prospective developments in the mentioned industrial departments while simultaneously identifying the research gaps the study aims to address for Bangladesh's jute industry (table 2). Based on the existing literatures about Bangladesh jute industry, a literature table has also been developed to identify the gap and research demand in the industry that will guide the objectives of the current research (table 1).

Table 1: Literature table

Author	Research purpose	Findings	Limitations/ Gaps	Comments/Recommendation for future research
Sharna and Kamruzzaman (2020)	Assessing comparative advantage of Bangladesh jute industry	Demonstrated comparative scenario of Bangladesh jute sector	The paper was based on secondary data	Extensive assessment of the industry is required to establish an effective plan for enhanced productivity
Niloy (2021)	To identify possible diversification of jute and opportunities of Bangladesh jute industry	Identified different diversification opportunities of jute that can be possible by Bangladesh jute industry	The paper was based on secondary data	The research stated that advancement in Bangladesh jute diversification is important to meet global demand that need to be assessed further
Akter, Sadekin, and Islam (2020)	Identifying policies to eradicate challenges that Bangladesh jute industry is experiencing	Recommended several policies based on existing problems of Bangladesh jute industry	The research was based on secondary data	Future research is required to understand the scenario based on extensive primary data

Hossain, Nishu and Freelance Researcher (2021)	To determine the reasons behind the failure of state-owned jute mills	Identified the reasons for closing jute mills and stated feasible solutions	The research was limited to only state-owned jute mills in Bangladesh	The research indicated that the real scenario of Bangladesh jute industry is required to be assessed to identify missed opportunities and problems in rethinking future decision
Amin and Sarker (2023)	Understanding the current state of challenges and opportunities of Bangladesh jute products	Assessed the demand of jute product both locally and internationally, to identifying their challenges and opportunity	Only focused on export-related challenges and opportunities, mostly focused on the demand of jute rather than identifying challenges and	Need to assess the scenario of other domains of the industry

			recommending future actions	
Toky <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Assessing current state of Bangladesh jute industry and its demand	The research discussed the current yield of Bangladesh jute industry, associated challenges and solution	The research was based on secondary data, reviewing existing literature	It was mentioned in the research that details about current state of Bangladesh jute industry is missing in existing literature, which need to be assessed to decide for future action in meeting global demand
Islam and Ali (2018)	To conduct a review of Bangladesh jute processing	Reviewed different jute processing development and their properties as biodegradable fibre	Limited to secondary data analysis	The research emphasised future research on the development of each stage of jute manufacturing in Bangladesh
Mukul <i>et al.</i> (2021)	To assess the comparative potentiality of BJRI Tossa Pat 7	The variety was found to have high fibre quality and yield compared to other varieties	Efficiency and adoption in commercial use has not been discussed	Future research needs to study the extent of commercial use of the improved varieties to decide further action

Haider and Rafiquzzaman (2023)	To implement TPM in improving industrial performance	Assessed different TPM practices, and recommended the effective practice in enhancing industrial performance	Overlooked the discussion on actual strategic practices that is being conducted by the industry	Study absents regarding the processing strategy implemented by Bangladesh jute industry to enhance performance
Alimuzzaman <i>et al.</i> (2024)	To introduce a novel approach of manufacturing sustainable seamless jute bags	highlighted the benefits of using updated machinery compared to traditional production methods	Have not discussed the practical use of updated machineries in industrial level	Research needs to identify the current practice of Bangladesh jute industry regarding advanced technology in processing domain
Peu (2019)	Identifying export market potentiality of Bangladesh JDP	Promising market potentiality of Bangladesh JDP	The research only focused on DJP sector of the industry	Future research is required on identifying competitive marketing strategy
Akter (2015)	Assessing the market potentiality of Bangladesh jute in Australia	Bangladesh jute was found to have great potential in Australian market with	Limited to only assessing Australian market for Bangladesh jute	The research stated that existing literature is lack of sufficient academic research on marketing challenges

		some recommended advancement in place		
Islam (2017)	Identifying raw jute marketing channels in Bangladesh	Identified different challenges associated with Bangladesh raw jute marketing channel	Limited to secondary data and was conducted long ago (2012)	Research needed to be undertaken with update recent data

It was identified from the above discussion that most of the advanced actions in jute production are still in the trial phase rather than being implemented in commercial practice (Hossain *et al.*, 2020; Mukul *et al.*, 2021; Rahman *et al.*, 2015). Different agricultural production enhancement actions have been recommended by existing literature that are assumed to have great prosperity in increasing yield and quality production (Mahmud *et al.*, 2020; Sarker *et al.*, 2022). Existing research primarily emphasizes the challenges and opportunities faced by the Bangladesh jute industry in the global market (Al-Mamun *et al.*, 2017). However, it often overlooks the significant progress and advancements in these activities being made at a commercial level. By neglecting to discuss these developments, crucial insights to pinpoint valuable areas for future enhancement and innovation are also being missed. Therefore, it is essential that we broaden our knowledge in these aspects to understand how far the development has been reached to plan further.

Additionally, inadequate information about industrial processing advancement was observed in the existing literature. Existing literatures only discussed the importance of different strategic practices to improve overall performance (Haider and Rafiquzzaman, 2023; Shahinur *et al.*, 2022). Some studies identified suitable processing strategies to enhance quality products. However, these are not something that the industry is practising in its daily processes. The industry needs to implement these strategies in practical practice to achieve the target goal. Besides, an in-depth understanding of current technological and sustainable practices in Bangladesh's jute industry is also unknown from existing literature. Finally, barely any research has been conducted on the Bangladesh jute industry to discuss its marketing strategies. Existing literature presented different marketing challenges that Bangladesh's jute industry is experiencing in meeting global demand, proposing some effective solutions (Akter, 2015; Asrafuzzaman and Islam, 2021; Peu, 2019; Sharna and Kamruzzaman, 2020). However, no research has been found to explain or assess existing marketing strategies adopted by the Bangladesh jute industry in practical situations following the recommendation.

Moreover, considering the overall situation of the industry, Islam and Ali (2018) recommended that each stage of jute manufacturing needs to be assessed to identify its progress. Existing research worked on identifying associated challenges and opportunities for the industry. However, a considerable amount of the research was

found to be limited on using secondary data rather than conducting validated research on the industry (Akter, Sadekin and Islam, 2020; Islam, 2017; Islam and Ali, 2018; Niloy, 2021; Toky et al., 2022). Therefore, it was proposed by the research that the current state of Bangladesh jute industry needs to be evaluated in identifying missed opportunities and problems to make plan for future actions (Hossain, Nishu and Freelance Researcher, 2021).

Based on the overall discussion on existing literature, identified research gap has been proposed here in table 2 linking them with current research objectives.

Table 2: Research gaps align with research objectives

Research objective	Research gap
To assess agricultural strategies undertaken by Bangladesh jute industry to meet market demand.	Existing literature mostly presented different field trials, pilot assessments and opportunities for improved agricultural strategies. Future research is required to assess the use of these strategies on a commercial basis, to develop enhanced production plan
To examine advancement in industrial processing of jute products by Bangladesh jute industry.	Inadequate information about processing strategies undertaken by the Bangladesh jute industry. Only a few research were found to discuss the importance of different strategies. Requires further assessment of the advancement in processing strategy to make future plan
To investigate marketing strategies that they are implementing in current competitive market.	Research with only different marketing challenges and recommended actions rather than indicating current practices that are being adopted by the industry

Hereby, current research will examine the present situation of Bangladesh jute industry in terms of their activities from field to export (agricultural jute production and yield associated actions, industrial processing and marketing) to unravel the

knowledge of current advancement that the industry is experiencing aimed at meeting global jute demand. Based on the research aim, it can be acknowledged that current research will follow the in-depth study method that will expose as much information as possible to comprehend the whole scenario. This will contribute to the literature with detailed, validated information about Bangladesh's jute industry to represent how far they are in establishing themselves in the global market. In addition to these theoretical implications, current research will propose a model with future action recommendations to assist industrial professionals in making required strategic decisions.

Details about the research approach and methodology are discussed in the following chapter along with its research philosophy.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

This chapter highlights the research methodology used in current research to obtain desired results. Research methodology is an important part of any research and is shaped by the research questions. Research questions and aims usually guide the researcher in constructing an appropriate research methodology. Current research aims to conduct a thorough assessment of the Bangladesh Jute industry. Based on this aim and the chosen research philosophy, qualitative research with semi-structured interviews has been selected as the approach for current research.

Research philosophy is the perception of the researcher about their surroundings. It is the way they think about reality or any phenomenon. The selection of research methodology is highly modulated by research philosophy. Based on the perception that a researcher carries, they decide strategy or methodology to conduct the research. In this chapter, a comprehensive overview of the research philosophy and justification for selecting the current research philosophy is discussed. The section further elaborates on the foundation of the chosen research strategies, offering justifications for each choice. Moreover, it portrays the reason and justification for selecting interviews as the current research approach compared to other qualitative approaches. Different facts related to questionnaire development, sampling, interviewing, data collection, data validity, and ethical consideration are also discussed in this chapter. Finally, the section discusses steps that have been carried out to present data for final analysis. Herein, main purpose of this chapter is to state and justify the choice of each stage of research methodology that has been adopted in the current research.

3.1 CONCEPT OF RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology can be defined as a set of activities or processes that seek to provide a scientific answer to the specified research question (Dźwigoł and Dźwigoł-Barosz, 2018). It can also be defined as the philosophy and framework that underpins the entire research work (Opoku, Ahmed and Akotia, 2016). Research methodology

is the design or architecture that guides the researcher in solving any research problem (Jamshed, 2014).

It is developed from the research paradigm supported by a theoretical perspective. Usually, research methodology includes some specific sections namely philosophical assumption, research approach, method, research strategy, research design, ethical consideration, limitations, data collection, and analysis. It has a crucial role in any research by ensuring that every step of the research structure is chosen consistently and has an interconnection between them. In this area, it is obvious to appreciate the contribution of Saunders Lewis and Thornhill (2016) to provide researchers with a very important theoretical base of research, 'Research Onion.' It is the framework representing every stage that needs to be considered in preparing an effective research methodology (Melnikovas, 2018). The consistency and coherence between each stage of this research framework are the key regulators to obtain constructive research outcomes. Figure 6 illustrates the methodological steps of current research following Saunder's research onion to provide a brief idea of how current research approaches were developed. Further elaboration of each step will be given below in the current section.

Figure 6: Research Onion of current study (adopted from Saunders Lewis and Thornhill, 2016)

3.2 UNDERSTANDING CURRENT RESEARCH AIM

Selecting an appropriate research method, is the foremost step to understanding the current research scenario and its aim. Jute, as one of the sustainable and environment-friendly fiber crops, is getting attention in the global market to replace polythene or to use it as a substitute for polythene. Besides, there are several diversified products of jute that can be brought into the market to intensify its use and to satisfy the demand. In terms of jute production, Bangladesh is well known in the global market *along* with other jute importing countries. Researchers stated that Bangladesh could have a great prospect in the current global jute market with its ability to supply demanded raw and processed jute products. The government of Bangladesh itself, with the alliance of several private organizations, is taking essential steps to improve the jute market of Bangladesh. However, the progress needs to be monitored to understand the current scenario of the industry and to understand their strategies in getting along with the competitive global jute market. Assessing the activities of the Bangladesh Jute industry will allow future researchers and policymakers to decide how best to modify the system going forward. Current research also aimed at presenting an action model that can be considered in the future as a sustainable and effective one to continue the success of Bangladesh's jute industry in the world market. It will help the industry to get the right direction for improvement by identifying positions where advancement is lacking and needs the most attention in the future.

The main research question of the current study is- “How is Bangladesh's jute industry working towards its advancement (e.g., agricultural production, industrial processing, and marketing) to meet global demand?”. Based on the developed research question, an appropriate research methodology has been selected. In this section, the selection of research methodology, its basis, and philosophy will be discussed. Here a schematic presentation of steps followed in current research is given to have a brief understanding of the research methodology (figure 7)

Figure 7: Schematic illustration of research steps

3.3 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

Research philosophy is an important part of any research that helps in the selection of an appropriate research approach. With proper knowledge and understanding of research philosophy, a researcher can step forward towards undertaking an effective research approach. Gliner, Morgan and Leech (2016) said that it is research philosophy that assists the researchers in identifying the required research methodology for the intended study. The paradigm (epistemology, ontology, and methodology) of any research depends on the accurate establishment of research philosophy (Žukauskas, Vveinhardt and Andriukaitienė, 2018). It provides the direction for research performance.

Research philosophy encompasses a researcher’s understanding of reality, beliefs, and knowledge. It articulates the researcher’s cognitive framework and awareness regarding their investigative work. This philosophy serves as the foundational step in the research onion model, providing the overarching context from which research assumptions are formulated (Abutabenjeh and Jaradat, 2018). It reflects the researcher’s perception of the world’s reality, the existence of the subject matter, the

body of knowledge, and the surrounding context. Research constitutes a means of acquiring information that enhances our understanding and assumptions about our beliefs concerning our environment or a particular research domain. The research philosophy influences how the researcher engages with knowledge, assumptions, and beliefs (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). Furthermore, it directs the formulation of research questions, the structuring of the research methodology, and the interpretation of results. Research philosophy is fundamentally categorized into three primary bases: epistemology (the study of knowledge), ontology (the study of existence and reality), and axiology (the study of values and beliefs). These categories provide the framework within which researchers make methodological choices.

3.3.1 Justification for selecting current research philosophy

Ontology is the part of research philosophy that represents how the researcher thinks of the research area and its reality (Ahmed, 2008). Levers (2013) mentioned that relativist ontologists believe that human experience can describe the reality of any plot. If anyone wants to understand the reality, it can be comprehensible through people's experience. People who are associated with practical situations. However, the experience is different for each person. So, the perception of reality also varies from person to person. Relativist ontology prioritise observation to assess the reality. However, realism ontology is the philosophy where reasoning is more prioritized (Proctor, 1998). In realism ontology, the reality is certain, not biased. It believes in reality as independent of human thought. It can only be acquired through sincere observation and measurement, avoiding any bias in the assessment.

The current research was aimed at assessing the present condition of the Bangladesh jute market. It is a huge industrial sector that involves a vast number of human resources and encounters daily changes within the industry. This human resource serves as a source of information, with experience from both past and present contexts of the industry. So, they serve as an accessible, time-efficient, and reliable source of information for assessing industrial phenomena. It indicates that the reality of the target industry can be well comprehended from the perception of associated professionals. They are a crucial part of the industry. Hereby, relativism ontology was identified as the best-suited ontological philosophy considering the current research aim and objectives. This prioritizes the perception of humans to elucidate any situation. It is the same reason that current research did not follow realism philosophy. Since it

was believed by the researcher that the reality of the target scenario is not independent of the associated people's perception (Holden and Lynch, 2004). People's perceptions and thoughts have significant importance while assessing the target situation.

Ontological view significantly controls making epistemological choices (Kant, 2014). Ontology expresses how a researcher thinks of a research situation (is it measurable or observable), and based on that thinking, they decide how they can obtain knowledge from the situation (with reasoning or perspective) (Ahmed, 2008). Epistemology explains the way through which a researcher wants to acquire knowledge and decide who will be the source of information (person or object). For instance, if the research situation is measurable, then it can be reasoning (objectivism), while on the other hand, the observable situation needs to be understood through perception (subjectivism). Subjectivist epistemology is the philosophy where reality is demonstrated through people's perception or observation (Moon and Blackman, 2017). As current research follows a relativist philosophy in constructing knowledge, it can be said that the research follows subjectivist epistemology. Subjectivism, as the epistemological view of current research, indicates that the research is more about prioritizing people's perceptions. It acknowledges reality as not something universal or unaltered. In this type of research philosophy, it is believed that knowledge can be influenced and interpreted by the reflection of the observer (Levers, 2013). Any situation can be pictured with the perception of the associated individual. Current research does not consider objectivism as its epistemological view. Objectivism relies on believing that reality is certain and independent of people's perceptions.

However, after obtaining research data, it is important to process them to get the desired result. Here, axiology is the philosophy that determines how the researcher is going to prioritize values. As can be seen, the current research philosophy is more toward subjectivist epistemology (value bound). It gives importance to one's perception and acknowledges that factors can affect values. Social life can only be interpreted through analysing the values of people living in it. Everyone's perspective is important, even if they are far different from each other (Aliyu *et al.*, 2015). So, during planning methodology for current research, axiology suggests taking ethical and bias-related facts into consideration. It will help the researcher to interpret the exact situation impartially (Chilisa and Kawulich, 2012).

3.3.2 Selection of research paradigm and justification

A research paradigm can be developed based on these philosophical views of the researcher (ontology, epistemology, and axiology). Research paradigm has been stated as the set of beliefs about reality or existence that a researcher contains before conducting any research (Aliyu *et al.*, 2015). This is the basis of research that represents the researcher's values and perceptions. Based on this, the research structure is formed. The paradigms of any research are positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism. Here, positivism represents the belief in subjective knowledge, whereas interpretivism is the knowledge based on objective observation (Alharahsheh and Pius, 2020). Positivist research considers any research component as a physical object and thus believes that it is measurable. On the other hand, interpretive research data varies based on surrounding factors and individual context, value, and perception. Considering the relativist subjectivism philosophy of current research, it can be said that the research will follow an interpretivist paradigm (Levers, 2013) where the target phenomenon will be well understood with the evaluation of associated individual experience. It is about understanding an individual's experience and perception and interpreting it accordingly.

3.4 RESEARCH APPROACH

The researcher's philosophical view then directs them towards choosing an appropriate research approach. This is where the researcher can decide on further research steps (Teherani *et al.*, 2015). Two forms of research approach can be derived from Saunders' Research Onion: inductive and deductive research approaches.

3.4.1 Rationale for selecting current research approach

The interpretive paradigm of the current research indicates a reliance on an inductive research approach (Al-Ababneh, 2020). Inductive research begins with observation, identifying patterns among the gathered data, generalizing these patterns, and ultimately suggesting theoretical frameworks. Soiferman (2010) stated that inductive research as an approach of research to work from bottom to top, systematically developing new theories (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). It is the approach to present observation in a generalized abstract, emphasizing its utility in exploratory contexts that seek a deeper understanding of a particular phenomenon.

The basis of current research does not endorse the use of a deductive research approach, which typically commences with a hypothesis or pre-established theory to inform data analysis (Soiferman, 2010). In contrast, this research aims to examine the overall landscape of the jute industry, making an exploratory analysis more appropriate. This methodology grants the researcher the flexibility to engage in comprehensive observations, generating novel insights regarding the industry's dynamics, rather than confining the study within a hypothesis-driven framework. Therefore, the inductive research approach has been selected to guide the development of the research methodology for this investigation.

3.5 SELECTION AND JUSTIFICATION FOR CURRENT RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research approaches are commonly divided into two main paradigms: qualitative and quantitative research (Al-Ababneh, 2020). The quantitative paradigm focuses on the statistical analysis of numerical data, whereas qualitative research addresses non-numerical data. According to Khaldi (2017), qualitative research is integral in uncovering social science facts. The data derived from qualitative research is referred to as qualitative data, which encompasses non-numerical information gathered through the perceptions and observations of individuals (Soiferman, 2010). This type of research is conducted in natural settings where researcher controls the data collection process. Gelo, Braakmann and Benetka (2008) further characterize qualitative research as employing a naturalist experimental design, in contrast to quantitative research, which measures variables within manipulated environments. In recent years, a new research paradigm has emerged that integrates both qualitative and quantitative methodologies, termed mixed methods research. Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004) describe mixed methods as a complementary approach that combines the strengths of traditional qualitative and quantitative research. This hybrid approach has gained popularity for its ability to harness the advantages of both methods while mitigating their respective weaknesses, allowing researchers to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomena under study.

The current research aims to delve into people's perceptions, employing an inductive research approach to achieve a thorough understanding of the target situation. This research adheres to a qualitative paradigm, focusing specifically on non-numerical data. By exploring practices in natural settings, the research intends to shed light on

the current state of the industry. Consequently, quantitative or mixed methods are not suitable for this investigation. The research does not seek to test hypotheses or conduct statistical analyses, reinforcing the choice to forego quantitative methods. According to McCusker and Gunaydin (2015), numerical analysis often overlooks the human perspective and behavior as significant factors influencing data variation, which contradicts the research philosophy adopted here. In contrast, qualitative research approaches offer a pathway for conducting an in-depth assessment of phenomena, where human perspectives play a critical role in shaping data. Moreover, the objectives of this research reflect a commitment to exploring a broad inquiry field flexibly, which is a hallmark of the qualitative research approach. This aligns with findings from Agyekum *et al.* (2019), who underscored the effectiveness of qualitative methods in uncovering deeper insights into people's perceptions. This research aims to contribute to the understanding of the subject matter by embracing the nuances of human experience and perspectives.

The researcher in the current study has consciously opted against utilizing a mixed methods approach. This decision stems from the alignment of the research philosophy with the interpretivist paradigm, which emphasizes understanding the subjective meanings and experiences of individuals. By avoiding a mixed methods framework, the researcher aims to circumvent potential paradigm conflicts, which have been noted in existing literature (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The integration of qualitative and quantitative research methodologies has been criticized for creating confusion in data collection processes, ultimately resulting in questions regarding the validity of the findings (Adu *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, combining both systems may lead to inaccuracies in data collection from pre-selected sources. Such challenges necessitate meticulous planning and a careful selection of an appropriate research philosophy. Consequently, the current research deliberately chose to eliminate any uncertainties related to mixed methods, focusing instead on a single, cohesive research approach.

3.6 RESEARCH STRATEGY

A research strategy is a plan that outlines how data will be collected from sources to address a specific research question. Research philosophy, research approach, and research paradigm are crucial in selecting an appropriate research strategy. Khaldi (2017) classified the qualitative research paradigm into three main categories of

research strategies: interactive, non-interactive, and mixed strategies. As the names suggest, these categories reflect the nature of interaction between the researcher and participants. Additionally, the depth and validity of the information gathered can vary depending on the type of interaction employed (Östlund *et al.*, 2011). For instance, interactive research allows broad interaction between the researcher and participants, where the researcher directly or indirectly interacts with the participant to get desired information. It will help to interact closely with participants to gain an in-depth understanding of the target situation (Ohlsson and Johansson (2010).

Different interactive qualitative research strategies are popular and widely used by researchers. For example, the case study is one of the most extensively used qualitative research methods. It provides researchers with descriptive, explanatory, and exploratory data collection approaches to gain an in-depth understanding of phenomena (Priya, 2021). According to Yin (2009), a case study encompasses a set of research designs rather than just a data collection process. It involves continuous monitoring to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the target phenomena. However, the effectiveness of a case study is limited by various external factors present in the natural setting where it is conducted (Priya, 2021)

Focus group research is another qualitative data collection approach. It entails collecting the perceptions of a group of people or participants on a specific topic, and they tend to discuss that topic (Onwuegbuzie *et al.*, 2009). It prioritizes opinions coming from the participants in that group discussion. It is a data collection method where a researcher can have direct face-to-face interaction with participants in the group and get first-hand information from them.

Researchers also found individual in-depth interviews as a promising qualitative data collection tool compared to focus groups. Both approaches collect information from participants. However, it was identified that participants felt the individual in-depth interviews comparatively a secure way to express their opinions (Kruger *et al.*, 2019). The individual interview offers participants the space to openly discuss their concerns in a broad context rather than being limited to group discussion (Milena, Dainora and Alin, 2008). Jamshed (2014) also supported in-depth interviews as the most used qualitative research strategy in qualitative research. So, current research chooses interviews as its research strategy to obtain desired data.

3.6.1 Rationale for interview as selected research strategy

The selection of a research methodology is primarily determined by the nature of the research problem (Noor, 2008). Ebneyamini and Sadeghi Moghadam (2018) identified three crucial factors that significantly influence the choice of research methodology: the formulation of research questions, the extent of behavioral events that the researcher is willing to explore, and the degree of focus that the researcher intends to apply to the study. The way in which research questions are articulated can guide the selection of the appropriate methodology for the investigation. For instance, numerous researchers (Ibrahim, 2008) have indicated that research questions framed in terms of how and why often lead to methodologies like experimental research and case studies. Conversely, research questions that focus on quantifiable aspects—how many, how much, where, and what—tend to favor methodologies like surveys and interviews. Nonetheless, this framework does not universally apply in all cases. A researcher's choice of research method is frequently influenced by their philosophical stance regarding their context and the research phenomena under examination.

The present research employed interviews as a methodological approach to gain a nuanced understanding of the jute industry in Bangladesh. The research questions were formulated using 'how' and 'what,' indicating the researcher's intent to delve into the complexities of the Bangladesh jute sector (Ibrahim, 2008). This formulation guided the investigation toward conducting interviews with specialized personnel who possess significant expertise and knowledge in this domain. Milena, Dainora, and Alin (2008) advocated for the use of individual interviews over focus group discussions, highlighting that individual interviews facilitate the collection of insights directly from subject matter experts. This approach acknowledges that these experts possess the most substantial knowledge regarding their field, thus making them ideal subjects for obtaining in-depth information. Furthermore, interviews serve as a qualitative research method that enhances our understanding of various phenomena. This approach is particularly effective in capturing the perceptions of individuals who are relevant to or directly engaged in specific situations through direct dialogue. By utilizing this method, researchers are able to uncover numerous facets of the situation based on an individual's unique perspective and experiences, which may remain obscured to others.

Interviews are predominantly conducted through face-to-face meetings with respondents, which is often regarded as the most effective approach for fostering close interaction with participants. However, advancements in technology have led to the increased popularity of alternative interview methods, including phone, email, and online platforms namely Zoom and Skype (Gray *et al.*, 2020; Saarijärvi and Bratt, 2021). The current research adopted an online video interview methodology (utilizing Zoom and Skype) due to its time and cost-effectiveness. According to Saarijärvi and Bratt (2021), online video interviews are not significantly inferior to traditional face-to-face interviews, as they facilitate visual interaction between the interviewer and participant.

The primary aim of the current research is to examine the dynamics of the Bangladesh jute industry, necessitating data collection from individuals actively engaged in the sector. In this context, the online interview approach was identified as the most appropriate method for engaging with geographically dispersed participants (Deakin and Wakefield, 2014). This technological advancement enables researchers to reduce travel expenses and offers greater flexibility in scheduling interviews at mutually convenient times. Consequently, some interviews were conducted after office hours to accommodate the availability of participants. Nevertheless, online interviews come with certain limitations, as highlighted by Deakin and Wakefield (2014). These limitations include potential distractions, network connectivity issues, variances in sound and video quality, and the possibility of participant absent-mindedness. Despite these challenges, the researcher opted for in-depth online interviews as the data collection approach for the current study, carefully considering the advantages of this method in relation to its drawbacks. This approach not only provides the researcher with the necessary flexibility to elicit comprehensive information but also allows for extended engagement with participants to achieve the desired insights.

Considering all the positive aspects and prospects of the interviews in collecting exclusive information, the current research decided to proceed with online interviews as its data collection method. Compared to other qualitative data collection approaches, individual interviews afford participants the opportunity to convey their thoughts and feelings in a confidential setting, rather than within a group context. Furthermore, this method enables the researcher to achieve the research objectives through remote data collection, eliminating the necessity for travel to the physical

research site. Following the selection of the research method, the subsequent step involved the collection of data from the target participants, which will be addressed in the ensuing discussion.

3.7 DATA COLLECTION

Several types of interviews can be observed in existing literatures. For example, unstructured and semi-structured interviews (Brinkmann, 2014; Chauhan, 2022; Fylan, 2005). The unstructured interview is more independent, where participants can express their feelings or perceptions with no boundaries. In this kind of interview, the sequence of questions can follow the lead of the participants as they prefer the facts to discuss. There is no pre-determined set of questions to follow in the interview process (Showkat and Parveen, 2017). With such a type of interview, it is more likely to extract huge amounts of information from the participants. Participants are open to discussing facts within the selected topic. So, they can express as much information as they want. On the other hand, in-depth interviews can also be conducted with a semi-structured questionnaire format. It is the most commonly used method in interviews. (Kallio *et al.*, 2016). It is usually performed with open-ended questions where the interviewer keeps the questions within the desired topic of research. In this type of research, the participant still has the freedom to express their perception while remaining within a boundary. This kind of data collection tool helps the researcher to keep conversation with participants within the research interest. Since they have a set of questions for certain research areas that the participants need to discuss (Blandford, 2013).

3.7.1 Justification for selected data collection tool

Considering features and facts about the mentioned interview questionnaire types, current research chooses semi-structured interviews as its research method. It was assumed that this would be a more flexible method to use, keeping aligned with current research objectives. As discussed, a Semi-structured interview offers proper utilization of time as a researcher can keep the conversation with participants within the pre-determined topic. Besides, there is a great chance to explore the research topic as the researcher is not bound to strictly follow the research questions. They can go with the information flow led by interviewees within the research topic (Kelly, Bourgeault, and Dingwall, 2010). For instance, if the participant is giving information about some

exciting facts within the research topic, then researcher can form immediate questions accordingly to lead the way further and to get more details (Kallio *et al.*, 2016). They do not have to follow any strict question series with semi-structured questionnaires, unlike the structured questionnaire system. Besides, with the semi-structured interviews, the participant can openly express their opinion. Whereas structured questionnaires place strict boundaries beyond which the discussion cannot go. The researcher also avoided the unstructured questionnaire forms as they can cause a waste of time in discussing off-topic subjects. To gather plenty of information in a limited time period, semi-structured interviews were found to be the best tool. However, a semi-structured interview requires the researcher to have previous knowledge of the research area to prepare a set of questionnaires (Wengraf, 2001). With some prior knowledge, they can predict the responses from participants and can form the questions accordingly.

3.7.2 Selection of participants and questionnaire development

To collect information from participants, a semi-structured questionnaire was prepared (Appendix I). Before preparing the questionnaire, decisions about participants were made. The research targeted individuals who are related to the Bangladesh jute industry and are experts in their field. Conducting in-depth interviews with these experts is the best way to gather information relevant to the research. Current research aimed to contact professionals from four different sectors related to the jute industry. They are agricultural expertise, industrial processing personnel, jute marketing personnel, and jute researchers. As discussed in the previous chapter, this research will concentrate on three key areas of the jute industry: production, processing, and marketing. The focus will be on gathering information from professionals in these sectors to gain insights into advancements in the industry. For instance, agricultural expertise from different jute related organizations can provide valuable information about the production advancement that is occurring in the industry. On the other hand, processing expertise and marketing personnel are for the information about the other two remaining domains. However, one extra sector of professionals (jute researchers) has been selected to get information from. They were the jute-related researchers from different research institutes and Universities. Researcher- as and experts in their field, stay well-informed about recent developments and concerns. They can be considered as one of the validated and trustworthy sources of information. Hereby, these are the

four main groups that were considered to have broad knowledge about advancement in the jute industry.

As the selected participant groups were from different professional backgrounds, the questionnaire was also made separately for each of the groups, considering their specialized knowledge. The questionnaire started with an overview of the interview process how the interview process will be, how long it will take, what they can expect to be asked about, and data confidentiality (Appendix I). Then it was some demographic questions (Part A) (age, gender, institution, profession, year of experience and responsibilities.) that was given in the questionnaire to obtain general information about the participants. These were the same for all participants in every group.

Variation in questions mainly occurred in part B of the questionnaire, which was topic-specific inquiries from the experts. For example, participants who specialized in the agricultural field were mainly asked about crop science-related questions but not marketing-related questions. Participants in industrial processing experts were asked questions on the processing strategies of jute. The overall questions in part B were divided into nine sections (current advancement, production strategy, DJP, technology, pricing, marketing strategy, trading barrier, governmental involvement, and sustainability) that were developed by keeping current research questions in mind. Each of the sections has an interconnection with the advancement of the industrial systems, as it has been discussed in the literature review chapter. They are linked to the concern about performance in the main domain of industry. Some of the questions in this section were developed from existing literatures (Caiado *et al.*, 2019; De Toni *et al.*, 2017; Ferdous and Ikeda, 2018; Onyango, 2021; Swazan and Das, 2022; Tomasin *et al.*, 2013; Van Der Walt, 2020; Winter and Lasch, 2016). They used questions with similar concerns to conduct their research. A total of 34 questions were created for Part B of the questionnaire, intended for all professionals involved. However, during the individual interviews, each professional was asked between 16 to 22 questions. As previously mentioned, the questions posed were specifically related to each professional's area of expertise. Besides, with the nature of a semi-structured questionnaire, it is not always a strictly fixed number of questions that the interviewer asks the interviewee. The pattern and number of questions can vary based

on the flow of conversation between interviewer and interviewee. It depends on how and what the interviewee wants to discuss about the topic.

3.7.3 Reliability and validity of the questionnaire

While developing the questions, some techniques were also adopted to make them effective in getting the desired information. The questionnaire used two kinds of questions (main theme and follow-up question). Some follow-up questions were asked to the participants to cross-check answers to the main theme questions. It is more like asking similar questions in different ways to assess whether the answer is the same or not. Kallio *et al.* (2016) indicated that such an approach improves the effectiveness of the questionnaire. More in-depth information can be obtained by applying such a technique. The ordering of the questions was repeatedly checked to avoid the presence of any misleading questions. Precautions were taken to avoid any kind of questions that attack participants personally. They were given full freedom to avoid any question they wished or to terminate the interview anytime they wanted. In addition to developing a questionnaire, some additional file was also prepared for participants. They are consent forms and participant information sheets (Appendix I). It was aimed that consent from the participants is collected before conducting the interview, and with a pre-sent participant information sheet, they can have some idea about current research before making the decision.

It is important to note that current research lacks pilot tests of the questionnaires. Existing literature highlights the significant role of pilot testing in enhancing the effectiveness of questionnaires to collect the desired data (Malmqvist *et al.*, 2019). It is the test to understand the level of feasibility, validity, and flexibility of any questionnaire that includes pilot testing or pre-testing of questionnaires, which significantly enhances the likelihood of achieving high-quality outcomes compared to studies that forgo these crucial steps. However, some researchers have proposed alternative approaches. Aung, Razak, and Nazry (2021), who suggest that a deep understanding of the research field and participants' backgrounds can replace the need for pilot testing. With such knowledge, it is possible to develop feasible question sets that require no prior test. It can provide considerable quality and quantity of information to satisfy the research demand. On the other hand, the selection of semi-structured interviews offers flexibility in questioning and hence allows the researcher to navigate the conversation based on the participants' responses. Unlike rigid

interview formats, in this method, the interviewer can ask questions as required in the interviewing situation to gather desired information. Recognizing this benefit, the researcher decided to move forward with the interviews directly rather than allocating time for pilot testing.

3.7.4 Sampling and justification for selected sampling strategy

After developing the questionnaire, the next pivotal step is selecting participants and arranging an interview schedule. Sampling participants is an important part of the research methodology, which highly influences data quality. It is the process of selecting representatives from the population (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Obtaining data from a whole population is not always possible, especially with a large population. Therefore, an appropriate sampling method should be followed to get the required participants. The selection of relevant participants for the research will facilitate obtaining proper information (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

In research, two main sampling methods are typically utilized: probability sampling and non-probability sampling (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). Probability sampling offers an unbiased and easy sampling approach where all the participants have an equal chance of selection (Malhotra, 2020). This method often employs simple random selection, allowing researchers to choose individuals from the population randomly. However, random selection can be challenging, especially with large populations (Collis & Hussey, 2014). To address this, a researcher needs to plan carefully and thoroughly understand their population before selecting samples. As an alternative, researchers can use non-probability sampling methods. In this approach, the researcher characterizes the population and can follow various non-probability sampling processes to obtain representative samples. For instance, in purposive sampling, researchers select individuals based on specific research objectives or instincts to gather the desired information from participants (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Researchers may also choose participants based on their availability and accessibility, which is referred to as quota sampling or convenience sampling. Additionally, some non-probability sampling methods involve selecting participants based on referrals from other participants, known as snowball sampling.

Considering the purpose of all different sampling techniques, the purposive sampling technique was used in the current research. Since current research aims to obtain in-

depth information from field experts, the purposive sampling technique will allow the researcher to select participants with this specific target. It will assist in selecting participants with intensive knowledge in the field and can offer high-quality information. For example, the researcher selected general managers from the industrial processing sector, marketing managers from the jute marketing sector, research fellows on jute research, and senior scientific officers specializing in agricultural expertise. These professionals represent the leading voices in their fields, equipped to provide critical insights and factual data. Thus, selecting participants was carried out with precision and a clear objective, ensuring the research is grounded in expert knowledge. Palinkas *et al.* (2015) also validated that research with information-rich intention is usually conducted by purposive sampling. Agyekum *et al.* (2019) also demonstrated the use of purposive sampling while targeting information-rich participants.

Current research also employed convenience sampling along with purposive sampling strategies. The justification for using convenience sampling in this research is discussed below.

3.7.5 Conducting the interview

Individuals within the group of participants (as mentioned above) were carefully selected from online sources including industrial blue books and reputable online directories. Subsequently, they were contacted via email and phone to ask for their interest and to schedule interview meetings. Initially nine respondents were interviewed as they started to show interest in the interview. However, the response rate was slower than anticipated. Since the participants were from the highest positions in their profession, it was challenging to get their availability. It was taking an extended time than expected. Acknowledging this challenge, the researcher decided to follow the concept of convenience sampling by moving forward with the available participants, ensuring that the research meets the given timeline effectively (Golzar, Noor and Tajik, 2022).

So, the interview process commenced with available participants from the selected group, but the focus on achieving data saturation was paramount (Guest, Bunce and Johnson, 2006). Data saturation refers to the point at which no new insights or information emerge from the participants (Fusch and Ness, 2015), confirming that the information gathered is adequate (Naeem *et al.*, 2024). After evaluating the data from

nine participants, the researcher decided to interview seven additional participants to ensure high-quality data and achieve saturation. It was identified that participants were providing repeated information that was already assessed. Hereby, the researcher decided to conclude the interview and proceed with the data analysis.

In the interview process, the participants were informed in advance about the aim and purpose of the current research. A consent form was also emailed to them before the interviews to obtain their approval. With their consent, the interviews were conducted online at the scheduled times using either Zoom or Skype as the interview platform. The interviews were recorded to assist with transcript preparation and analysis.

3.7.6 Justification for the sample size

A total of 16 participants were interviewed in the whole process. The decision to work with a small sample size of 16 participants can be well-supported by Malterud, Siersma and Guassora (2016), who emphasized that the appropriate sample size for an interview depends on its information power. It is stated by Malterud, Siersma and Guassora (2016) that the sample size does not need to be large but specified to have enough quality information for the research purpose. Participants selected in the current research are from the specified group with enriched information. Given this fact, it can be said that current research emphasizes the information power theory when selecting participants for the interview (Malterud, Siersma and Guassora, 2016). This approach prioritized the power of quality data over the number of participants. Additionally, Agyekum *et al.* (2019) corroborated this viewpoint, suggesting that a sample of two to ten information-rich participants is adequate for gathering quality data. In a nutshell, it can be said that current research mainly focuses on the depth of information rather than increasing the number of participants.

3.7.7 Validity and reliability of data

Qualitative research is more likely to explore the reality of the situation while having the limitation of reliability and validity (Queirós, Faria and Almeida, 2017). Thus, it is important to consider some steps in making the research data valid and reliable. The validity and reliability of qualitative research depend on the research design. Golafshani (2003) suggested that qualitative research's reliability, dependability, validity, and trustworthiness can be maintained if the research remains truthful, reduces biases in the research, and follows a triangulation system. Current research follows the triangulation theory to ensure the validity of collected data. Triangulation is

the process of validating data from different points. Current research uses a data triangulation system among several types of triangulations (data, theory, method, and investigator triangulation) (Carter, 1969). Here, data was collected from different sources or groups of individuals to cross-check its validity (Flick, 2004; Morse, 2015). Besides, some measurements were taken during the interview to ensure reliability and validity, as mentioned by Alshenqeeti (2014). Interviewees were asked to summarise the conversation at the end and connect the summary with the discussion in the topic question. On the other hand, data accuracy depends on sample size. However, the meaning of sample size here is represented by its number and the quality of information that the participant or sample can provide about the target situation or fact. Hennink and Kaiser (2021) stated that it is very important to have the justification for sample size in qualitative research, which is already provided above, so the reviewer can understand how the decision for sample size was made and why. Furthermore, to validate the depth of data collection, it is important to discuss the facts with the interviewee for as long as possible to gather more information (Minhat, 2015). Current research interviewed each participant for around an hour and a half, discussing the semi-structured questionnaire. Researcher decided to keep the interview length optimum, discussing the facts as guided by the questionnaire rather than extending the interview time where the participant may be distracted from the actual topic. Since participants in the current research were highly experienced personnel from their related work field, they were able to provide informative conversation even within the short period of the interview time.

3.8 DATA PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS

Qualitative research generates diverse data as each participant perceives the specified phenomenon differently (Golafshani, 2003). So, arranging the data for analysis as soon as it is collected is important. It is the most important part of the research, leading to effective conclusions and insights about the research area. By effectively arranging and analyzing the data, researchers can delve deeper into the information gathered and uncover more precise knowledge (Gibson and O'Connor, 2003).

The existing literature has used several approaches for qualitative data analysis, including content analysis, grounded theory, narrative analysis, and thematic analysis. Among these approaches, thematic analysis is a widely used method. Nowell *et al.*

(2017) stated that it is an effective approach to analyzing data from a wide range of epistemology research. Thematic analysis allows for a descriptive presentation of the research context, whereas content analysis primarily focuses on identifying themes or patterns in the information. It offers a more in-depth understanding of the themes or facts within the data (Graue, 2015; Vaismoradi, Turunen, and Bondas, 2013). Additionally, while thematic analysis emphasizes the actions and meanings derived from the data, the narrative approach seeks specific moments or stories present within the data (McAllum *et al.*, 2019). Javadi and Zarea, (2016) stated thematic analysis as an effective qualitative data analysis process to act on reality. Thematic analysis offers significant advantages when working with extensive data sets and varied participant groups. Its credibility is well established in the literature, where numerous researchers have effectively utilized this method. For example, Jones *et al.* (2023) employed thematic analysis to understand industrial professionals' perceptions of implementing specific policies. Similarly, Agyekum *et al.* (2019) used semi-structured interviews coupled with thematic analysis to extract insights from professionals in relevant fields. Given these compelling examples and the proven effectiveness of thematic analysis for in-depth qualitative assessments, the researcher has decided to conduct this approach in the current study.

3.8.1 Thematic data analysis

Many researchers have demonstrated the systematic guidelines for conducting a thematic analysis (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017; Naeem *et al.*, 2023). The analysis started with getting familiar with the data (transcript preparation) and then generating initial codes. In the next step, themes were identified from the coding to review them further and interpret the results. The steps of data processing with thematic analysis are discussed in detail below.

3.8.1.1 preparing transcript of data

Castleberry and Nolen (2018) suggested that the first step after obtaining interview data for data analysis is to organize the data by transcribing it. It is the step toward transforming audio data into written form (Bailey, 2008; Sutton and Austin, 2015). As stated by many researchers, transcribing interview data is very time-consuming and hard work. Numerous software or online tools can simplify transcription tasks for research. However, the current research transcription was conducted manually by the researcher. It is suggested by many researchers that self-transcribing is much more

viable and effective compared to using software (Castleberry and Nolen, 2018; Sutton and Austin, 2015). Self-transcribing allows researchers to engage more deeply with the data. As they transcribe, researchers can develop a broader understanding of the content by hearing and writing it repeatedly. Careful attention during transcription ensures that no information is overlooked. Sutton and Austin (2015) also emphasize the importance of verbatim transcription, as it helps maintain the validity of the research and captures all the information provided by the interviewee.

It is important to note that interviews in the current research were conducted in the Bengali language. Participants were asked about their language preference and most of them preferred to provide their information in Bengali language. Therefore, it was required to convert the language from Bengali to English while writing the transcript. Many language-converting tools are available online. However, none of them were found convenient to convert voice from Bengali to English. So, the transcription was done by the researcher himself to convert information into the English language in a convenient manner. It was kind of transforming field text into research text, as mentioned by Halai (2007). It is a very hard job where it is important to have sincere concentration to keep the information intact while the language is being converted from one to another. The interview audio recording was listened to multiple times to ensure an accurate transcription. To validate the translation and transcript, a third party with the same language background reviewed the materials to confirm that the information remained intact after translation.

3.8.1.2 Coding

After transcribing interview data, it was a huge number of pages with enormous information provided by participants. According to Naeem *et al.* (2023), it is important to identify keywords in the transcript before moving forward to code the data. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) also demonstrated the steps of open, axial, and selective coding in effectively processing qualitative data. Coding is an important part of thematic analysis that helps to get something logical and meaningful from that huge bundle of conversation. It is about finding and summarizing points to ease understanding of participants' perceptions of that specified fact (Rivas, 2012). In a nutshell, coding transforms raw data into something valuable and usable. The steps of coding followed in the current research are discussed below.

3.8.1.2.1 Open coding

While performing the coding, researcher needs to be very attentive in finding out similarities and differences in the data. The first step of coding is identifying patterns or repeated facts in the data (Naeem *et al.*, 2023). It is called open coding where the interview transcript is marked for similar information or phases (Mohajan and Mohajan, 2022). Open coding of current research was conducted manually with printed interview transcripts. It can be said to 'hand on a hard copy of the transcript' as stated by Sutton and Austin (2015). The transcripts were reviewed multiple times to correlate overall interview data with the study questions and to identify recurring information within the data. The prioritized information was subsequently regarded as code for further analysis. The Researcher reviewed the coding repeatedly to avoid biases or missing coding (Vollstedt and Rezat, 2019). However, identifying repeated and important facts in the data was comparatively easy for the researcher as the researcher manually transcribed and translated the interview data. The researcher used colored pens to mark the code in a printed copy. Information with different concerns was marked with different colors. This was the act of sorting data for code. Current research follows inductive coding, which represents using words or phrases directly from the data set rather than making them up from a pre-conceived hypothesis (Thomas, 2006).

Coding in the current research was also conducted by following the intra-coding suggestion by Castleberry and Nolen (2018). The intra-coding steps were performed to increase the reliability of the code. According to the intra-code guidelines, the coding was reviewed and recorded at intervals of a few days to check its consistency. Some new code was identified following these steps, while a few codes were also removed.

3.8.1.2.2 Axial coding to identify themes

Sorting data into codes was a supportive act toward the next step (axial coding) to categorize them into groups. Existing variables from the literature concerning industrial advancement, as well as the objectives of the current research, were considered here in making the themes. For example, similar information representing advancement in the industry has been categorized under the group name strategic advancement. Since observing industrial advancement is the main objective of current research. It will bring all related information together in one place to access later for analysis. On the other hand, 'advancement in diversified jute product' was named for another theme where information related to DJP development was discussed. Existing literature

identified DJPs as a promising issue in global jute demand. So, the researcher decided to bring discussion in this fact in the interview questionnaire. It resulted in obtaining valuable information about DJP to code and select this variable as one of the themes. Similarly, Governmental assistance in advancement and Future recommendations were also considered as themes in current research linked with research objectives.

The theme reflects the overall perspective of the data set developed from the related codes (Castleberry and Nolen, 2018). This research was conducted with careful consideration to avoid any repetition of themes and to categorize the codes as effectively as possible. Frequent checks of the codes were performed during the theme development process. Following the guidance of Castleberry and Nolen (2018), several key questions were addressed before finalizing the theme. These questions included whether it is a theme or still code, the quality of the theme, the boundaries of the theme, whether it is meaningful, whether it supports the code within it, and whether it is too diverse. These questions were instrumental in validating the theme developed in this research.

3.8.1.2.3 Selective coding

After grouping and selecting themes for the data set, it is time to connect the themes or find a relation among them. It is the way of presenting and interpreting data in an orderly manner. It is known as selective coding. Selective coding is the step where the researcher gets the chance to interpret and form a meaningful representation of the whole data while forming a core theme (Mohajan and Mohajan, 2022; Vollstedt and Rezat, 2019). Several research has suggested that in thematic analysis, developing a thematic map is an important section to represent the relation among the themes (Castleberry and Nolen, 2018). A thematic map is developed in the current research (Figure 8 in Chapter 4), analysing the themes repeatedly to interpret relationships among them and to link them with the current research aim.

According to Naeem *et al.* (2023), the last step of coding is to interpret data while validating them by discussing in the reference with existing literature. Current research provided a critical interpretation of data in chapter 5 along with an action model as mentioned in the research objectives.

3.9 MANAGING BIASES IN PROCESSING DATA

In qualitative research, it is a concern that researchers may prioritise their own preferences while dealing with data (Smith and Noble, 2014). Therefore, issues like subjectivity in processing data needed to be addressed. In the current research, different approaches were adopted to avoid biases and to ensure objectivity. The researcher had previous experience working in the textile industry. The experience was used to understand the position of the target participants and their level of knowledge in the research field. It was also helpful to guide the researcher in finding the appropriate contact address of the prospective interviewees. Transparency in participant selection was maintained in the research by providing the process details to represent that the research avoided any bias issue with participant recruitment. Participants from diverse fields (agriculture, industry, research, and marketing) were contacted using their available contact information from online sources. Besides, participants who responded to the email were only directed to the next step of attending the interview.

Furthermore, the current researcher used a second reviewer in preparing transcript to avoid associated bias. The transcript prepared by the researcher was rechecked with another reviewer from same language background to ensure that information from participants remained intact. The coding of the dataset was also reviewed by the research supervisor to avoid any personal bias in the data processing. Existing literature has validated this approach as external checking to increase the credibility of data (Nowell *et al.*, 2017). The researcher also followed intra-coding strategy to minimise bias issues (Castleberry and Nolen, 2018). The coding was performed at a time interval to assess its consistency. With the performance of intra-coding, a few new codes came up while some of them were eliminated.

3.10 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Ethical considerations represent a fundamental aspect of professional research (Hasan *et al.*, 2021). They serve as essential guidelines for conducting research in a manner that minimizes harm and prevents complications for individuals involved. The primary objective of ethical considerations is to uphold the rights, values, principles, dignity, and morality of all participants in the research process. Consequently,

researchers must adhere to ethical guidelines from the inception of their projects through to their completion.

At every phase of research—including topic selection, methodology, analysis of results, discussion, citation, and publication—it is critical to maintain a heightened awareness of the associated ethical issues (Hasan *et al.*, 2021). Qualitative research, which entails an in-depth exploration of human perception, is particularly susceptible to various ethical concerns (Arifin, 2018; Ngozwana, 2018). Such concerns encompass confidentiality, informed consent, anonymity, and data protection.

Specific measures were adopted to ensure anonymity and safeguard the complete confidentiality of the data set (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). For example, during the presentation of the research findings, participants were assigned identification codes. Industrial processing experts were designated as "IP," while participants within industrial processing were labeled as IP1, IP2, IP3, and IP4.

Data protection and privacy were prioritized by restricting data access solely to the researcher. It was ensured that the data collected from participants, including their interview recordings, would not be retained for an extended period. All data will be deleted as soon as the research is completed (Lin, 2009). To address issues of truthfulness and bias, the researcher presented the data exactly as it was obtained. The researcher was particularly careful in processing the data to prevent any alterations. Proper citation and referencing were maintained throughout the research to uphold its authenticity and to acknowledge the sources of related information. These practices contribute to the originality of the work. Therefore, it is evident that standard ethical measures were implemented at every stage of the current research to ensure quality and enhance its acceptability to others.

Furthermore, the research methodology was carefully designed to ensure the confidentiality, privacy, and accuracy of the data collected. Prior to the interviews, consent was obtained from each participant (Kaiser, 2009). Participants were informed about the purpose and procedures of the research in advance to avoid any ethical issues. The questionnaire was designed to avoid personal attacks or discussions of sensitive issues (Heale and Twycross, 2015). Participants were interviewed with caution to prevent any misleading or offensive questions. Implementing these ethical considerations is beneficial for fostering participants' confidence and trust in the

researcher. To adhere to the appropriate ethical standards, the researcher followed the university's ethical guidelines meticulously. Ethical clearance was also obtained from the university authority to comply with regulations (Appendix II).

3.11 SUMMARY OF THE CHAPTER

In this chapter, the researcher outlines the methodology and its foundation for current research. Current research is aimed at analysing the advancement of the Bangladesh jute industry in the global jute market. The objectives of the research were to investigate strategies, improvement, and developmental actions conducted by the Bangladesh jute industry to meet global demand. In this chapter, the whole set of procedures to follow such objectives and to obtain relevant data from target individuals were discussed.

Based on the aim of the current research, the researcher decided to follow a qualitative research approach in this research. The research was aimed at performing an in-depth assessment of target phenomena. So, the qualitative research approach was selected to perform an explorative investigation compared to that of the quantitative approach. Among different qualitative research strategies, a semi-structured interview was considered suitable for current research. The most favourable criterion of semi-structured interviews for current research was to offer the participants the freedom to express their opinions. The interview was identified as the approach to have direct interaction with participants where a researcher can lead the direction of conversation on the target topic. The chapter also provided details of the steps that the research followed for questionnaire development, sampling, interviewing, and data processing. An in-depth discussion was provided regarding the researcher's actions to ensure data validity and ethical considerations. Additionally, this chapter included an extensive discussion on the selected data processing approach—thematic analysis.

CHAPTER 4

FINDINGS

This section is structured to present findings from current research. The research findings will be presented using tables and graphs, followed by further discussion. This chapter is of paramount significance in any research, as it encapsulates the essence of the analysis. It will address the research questions based on the acquired results. Therefore, it is imperative to plan for the section to clearly and logically present the findings. As discussed earlier, current research conducted qualitative research analysis with interviews as the research approach. The research is aimed at identifying current advancements in Bangladesh's jute industry. It was decided for the research to obtain data from professionals related to the Bangladesh jute industry to follow an information-rich data process. Information obtained from participants was then analyzed using thematic analysis and presented here in this section to interpret the obtained data.

4.1 DEMOGRAPHIC PRESENTATION OF PARTICIPANT

Demographics (age, gender, sex, ethnicity, employment responsibilities, education, job status and level of experience) represent important characteristics of participants to develop a broad understanding of them (Ray and Fellow, 2020). Such data present details about participants that need to be understood before interpreting their perceptions. It helps to understand the participant's level of knowledge regarding the target research topic (Connelly, 2013). It can also help to differentiate current research from existing research based on the participant's background (Hammer, 2011). Furthermore, future researchers can unlock valuable insights through the demographic information provided, enhancing their secondary data analysis.

After gathering and processing information from participants, the first step was to organize their demographic data in a comparable and easy-to-interpret format. Table 2 represents the demographic data of participants from current research.

Table 2: Demographic presentation of participants

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Age group</i>	<i>Job position</i>	<i>Year of experience</i>	<i>Gender</i>
Industrial processing personnel (1)	Above 50	General manager	≥20	Male
Industrial processing personnel (2)	Above 50	General manager	≥20	Male
Industrial processing personnel (3)	Above 50	General manager	≥20	Male
Industrial processing personnel (4)	Above 45	Senior manager	≥20	Male
Jute researcher (1)	Above 50	Research Fellow	10-20	Male
Jute researcher (2)	40-50	Senior Scientific officer	≥10	Female
Jute researcher (3)	40-50	Professor	≥20	Male
Jute researcher (4)	40	Assistant Professor	≥10	Male
Agricultural expertise (1)	35-40	Senior- scientific officer	≥10	Male
Agricultural expertise (2)	35-40	Senior scientific officer	10-15	Male
Agricultural expertise (3)	45	Senior scientific officer	10-15	Male
Agricultural expertise (4)	35-40	Scientific officer	≤10	Female
Marketing expertise (1)	40-50	Marketing manager	10-20	Male
Marketing expertise (2)	35-40	Marketing manager	10-20	Male
Marketing expertise (3)	40-45	Senior Marketing manager	25	Male
Marketing expertise (4)	40-45	Marketing manager	15	Male

4.1.1 Participants age

The table 2 shows that all current research participants were aged 35-50, with four of them aged above 50. Since current research was aimed at obtaining information from field experts, their age can be linked to their age. In Bangladesh, it takes many years for professionals to reach top positions that enrich their experience in that specific field. Therefore, based on the age range of the participants in this research, we can conclude that they all possess significant experience in their fields.

4.1.2 Job position of participants

Current research mostly targeted individuals with higher job positions to ensure the collection of in-depth knowledge in the field. It can be noticed that at the industrial level, most of them were from the managerial level, and other participants were also from the senior scientific officer's level. This represents their depth of knowledge in the specified field.

4.1.3 Participant's year of experience

The level of participant's experience can be acknowledged from the number of years that they are involved in that specified job field. Current research participants can be seen to have experience from 10 to more than 20 years in the specified field. This long period of their career enabled them to develop in-depth knowledge of the subject matter and to experience different scenarios based on which they can suggest future improvement. The experience level can also be linked with their age and work position. It can be seen that participants from industrial professionals in current research have ≥ 20 years of experience, are above 50 years old, and possess general manager positions in their field. The senior scientific officers can also be seen as having ≥ 10 years of experience and around 40 years of age. In contrast, the scientific officer has less than 10 years of experience.

4.1.4 Participant's Institute

To align with ethical regulations, participants were kept anonymous. Revealing the institutional details of participants will make them traceable. Besides, participants preferred to keep the industrial details anonymous. So, the researcher decided to maintain the confidentiality of participant's personal details.

4.1.5 Gender of participants

Most of the participants were male. As for demographic data, 14 out of 16 participants were male, and only two were female. Although this differentiation does not significantly impact the data, it can be valuable information to record if needed in future analysis.

4.2 PARTICIPANT'S RESPONSE FROM INTERVIEW

The research sought to gather information through a semi-structured interview, resulting in extensive discussions on each issue. The researcher followed the interviewees' lead to gather additional pertinent information on the topic. In total, the research questionnaire had 34 questions, which were divided into different topics according to the professional background of participants. To facilitate a clearer understanding of the responses gathered, the findings from each question have been summarized and presented in Table 3. This table serves as a concise overview of the discussions, encapsulating the key findings of the research, which will be further analyzed in this chapter.

Table 3: Data summary obtained from the interview

QUESTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE	SUMMARY STATEMENTS FROM ALL PARTICIPANTS
Current progression	
<p>1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and the current position of Bangladesh's jute industry?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In terms of quality, production and export, Bangladesh is in the top position • Bangladesh is 2nd in jute production and 1st in jute export. Bangladesh's jute growing progress is better than other countries • Bangladesh's position is better than Pakistan and Sri Lanka, but not better than China and India. Bangladesh does not have much product development work, software development, research work. There is some work going on research and development, product diversification, but still can't compare them with India and China
<p>2. What do you think about the current progression/development of the Bangladesh jute industry compared to the past?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The overall progress is not as we expected. However, better now than past • In the past, it was golden for the jute industry in Bangladesh. However, this position has decreased. There are very few developments is being occurred in this sector, not enough • The jute market is not stable in the last 10 years. especially in the yarn market (major market) (carpet). However, packaging market is in good condition (hessian (small market) and sacking (huge)). Jute demand is only increasing in terms of packaging. Quality of jute product deteriorated but production increased. Quality deteriorated due to lack of rainwater and in lack of retting.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • volume of exporting is increasing. • the yield/ production has not increased that much, nearly same. However, the cultivable land is being decreased. Intensity of production per land is increasing • Maximum govt. jute mills have been closed. Now private mills are active. Bangladesh jute sector is progressing after private sector involved into this
Strategic improvement	
<p>3. What strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute sector is adopting to increase their production (both field strategy to produce raw jute and industrial strategy to process) and meet global jute demand?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trying to minimize the costing so that we can produce more in the same cost and export • Most of the government jute mill has been closed these days because of their loss year after year. In this crisis time of Bangladesh Jute industry, some private sector or owner has come forward to involve in this business • We are trying to supply our own seed and use our own to have better use and quality • We developed some new machinery (retting) to reduce labour cost and to get quality fiber
<p>4. What do you think about the Bangladesh jute industry in the global jute market with such strategies in the next 10 years? (any recommendations)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By increasing use of jute product and reducing production cost Bangladesh can do far better in global jute market. we can attract more buyer. Using more jute product will increase the demand in global market

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The private sector of Bangladesh jute industry is contributing huge to increase the production and to hold the position of Bangladesh jute industry in global market • With producing own seed, we can fulfil our seed demand and increase production • If Bangladesh Jute Corporation can develop the stress tolerant variety (biotic and abiotic) we can get 1.5-time higher jute production in 10 years. With the development of short duration variety, we can use the existing available land and get more yield • We need to provide subsidies to the farmer so that they can produce more
<p>5. What are the steps being taken by jute cultivators to produce more jute against climatic barriers? (Improve seed/ genetically modified cultivars/ cultivation strategy and so on.)?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We are trying to do some mutation, salinity tolerant and drought tolerant variety of tossa jute. Still in laboratory and field trial process • Farmers are using short duration and high yield variety
<p>6. How jute cultivation in Bangladesh is planning to increase with extending cultivation area?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The World Bank is going to take a project where they will research how jute cultivation can be extended in a climatic variety of areas. However, the extension is still in planning stage • If we can increase the market price and ensure the suitable environment for jute cultivation, then we can extend area for jute

<p>7. What is your thinking about hydroponic and vertical farming in terms of jute cultivation to increase the production?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We have already tried hydroponic farming on jute but not succeeded and also this is a costly system. We may get some yield from hydroponic or vertical farming (vertical farming with genetically modified jute crop that will have low height but quality fiber) with further research and initiatives. but not may fulfil our target production. • still in research level
<p>Diversified jute product</p>	
<p>8. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with DJP? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their production/sale of DJP?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bangladesh not only exporting raw jute but also exporting DJP like yarn to Iran, Netherland, Australia and so many countries. Different Govt and private organizations are taking action towards improving DJP. Private sector has done lots of work in this sector, but govt. has not a visible contribution • improving but not rapidly. its slow improvement • Current position of Bangladesh with DJP is not that good comparing to other country • We don't have proper infrastructure or management system that will initiate towards producing DJP. don't have proper research centre or facilities for DJP development. not proper new machineries

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • However, as a new idea and concept, Bangladesh is doing good. Many handicraft industries are growing based on this diversified product. The jute development board are arranging some fair to increase sale. • There is not so much improvement in jute diversification. Government's plan is good initiative, but implementation is slow and not sufficient because of lack of technology, skilled manpower and regular research. There is a jute diversification promotion centre established in 2002 and they are started their work already. This is a good progress actually. • India imports huge amount raw jute from Bangladesh and make diversified product, then export it to other countries. This is our big problem because India already controls the diversified global market. India also imposed anti-dumping legislation on only diverse jute product from Bangladesh, not on raw jute. Which also hampering our private sector which are making different diversified product
<p>9. What is your suggestion about DJPs that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We can only use jute in packaging and showpiece as a diversified product. Blending jute with other product (cotton) to make fabric is not a feasible idea. It will be expensive, and I don't think it will be accepted in Bangladesh market • We have to create the demand for jute and minimize the cost if we want to improve the sale. We need to offer attractive price to the buyer

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different small entrepreneurs are making DJPs, but it need to be more. We should not only focus on making one product (yarn) but diverse product • The challenges of jute diversification sector are lack of technology, proper infrastructure, skilled manpower and regular research • We need to lower the cost of jute product to compete with that substitute market • Government and other organization should pay attention towards improving technical and technological skill, skilled worker (training, knowledge) to produce diverse jute product • Entrepreneurs of the jute sector can take financial support from the bank. Government can provide some subsidiary to this sector • Government needs to come forward on this issue. They should focus on marketing globally. Government, Jute Industry, and Jute Development Board need to arrange some seminars to aware people about this DJP
Technological update	
<p>10.What upgraded processing techniques are Bangladesh jute industry following to increase quality production?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • most of the industrial personnel and even government is reluctant to upgrading the processing system and bring upgraded technology. It is I think lack of awareness • Recently we are importing machine from China and India. We do not have our own machine manufacture, even some industries are using that old machineries as before

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some of the mills are using new model machineries which are also using in China. This machine has increased the production and quality product. With the old machine knitting company produced 5-6 ton product but with new one we can now produce 8-9 ton product. We are now developing inverter machineries.
11. What is the technological situation/new technology being used in Bangladesh Jute industry marketing sector? How are they planning to improve?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attending different international trade fair to promote our product • Having adequate fund from government and increasing our skilled manpower
12. What is the technological improvement in jute cultivation and field processing?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • technological improvement is happening in Jute cultivation and field processing. We are collecting ribbon from raw jute by using technology. We are not depending only on pond for retting • we are developing and upgrading machineries to get better result. We have ribbon retting machine
13. What is your opinion about technologies that is being used in Bangladesh Jute industry? Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comparing to past, we are using upgraded machine. We are trying to develop our technical side, but China is using the best quality machineries • Our current world has gone so far with technology, but we are still far behind. I can see least amount investment in this sector and technologies are not like as our neighbour country. progress is not satisfied • Social media advertisement is new era of marketing comparing to past

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are lots of improvements happening in Jute sector comparing the past
14. How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Since it is the same technology, we all are using, we are not competing here with other exporting country
15. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute sector can adopt to improve their current position?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • public and private sector should come forward to make technological improvement in Bangladesh jute sector. They should make plan-policies and implement it • we need to encourage recent graduates to come and contribute their talent here in our jute industry. Need more skilled worker we need skilled manpower. We can open relatable courses in institute. We train people for the product diversification development and manufacturing program • we can have our own manufacturing industries that will provide us required machineries for the development of diverse jute product • I am not expert in machineries, but I think if we move towards automated machineries like the modern world, then we can save labour cost and time in jute processing. But obviously we need to assess if it is cost effective for us or not
16. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lack of manpower, skilled manpower • Finance I think the main challenge and also the co-ordination between different departments

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Govt. and private both sectors are not taking this issue seriously. There are many plans and policies but no implementation. Govt. and private both sectors are using and importing alternative product of jute from different countries because we do not have upgrade machineries or technology to make jute product. • we do not have the proper machineries and skilled man-power
<p>17.What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other research saying that jute sector will do lot of development in next 5 year. But with my experience I can say that it will not happen. Research may say that demand will increase but in practical I don't see it • If we can import machineries in lower price or make them by ourselves then we can reduce the production cost as well, which is very important currently in meeting global demand of jute product at lower price • I think if we can have enough financial backup, then we can move forward in exporting updated technologies and machineries • I think Jute production and jute field will increase in next 5 years by upgrading technology
<p>Pricing</p>	
<p>18.How you establish both internal (local) and external (export) pricing? What facts do you consider in establishing pricing?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When we are pricing for local market, we know that we will not get any subside from government so local price become high. But in export pricing we consider the subside matters and price become low

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government is not taking actions towards making the carrying container cheap or ease available. This has ultimate impact on the overall pricing. If we can carry or transport our product easily at lower price, then the overall product price will also become less • Pricing depends on variety of factors, production cost, profit, subsidies from government, market demand and so on.
19. What do you think of competitive pricing and how jute industries in Bangladesh are working in this?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In this period of pandemic and Ukraine war, we are trying to hold the buyer by lowering price
20. What is the pricing strategy to increase export profitability in jute sector?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We are trying to improve the product quality and lowering the price so we can increase the amount of sale
21. What is the local pricing strategy to keep market flow inside the country?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If we got any subsidy from government then we could keep the market flow inside the country • There are some industries who buy yarn from local market at lower price and sell different diverse product only in local market at high price. So, they meet their price demand. But it is not same for big industries who sell both locally and export outside
22. What is your suggestion about improvements in existing pricing strategy that will increase profit?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bangladesh export commission bureau can make arrangement and deal with other countries to sell our product in their country at standard price.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government is not taking actions towards making the carrying container cheap or ease available. If we can carry or transport our product easily at lower price then the overall product price will also become less.
Marketing strategy	
23. What marketing/sale strategies are currently implementing in Bangladesh jute industry to stand in competitive global market?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attending global fair, exhibition, inviting buyer to the industry to have a look in the production and increase their attraction towards product • Social media advertisement is being popular and effective
24. How you advertise or promote jute products to the buyer countries?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seminar, exhibition, fair, social media
25. What is your strategy towards attracting customer towards new DJP?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We invite buyer to visit our industry where we can demonstrate them the whole processing system and to get more attention from them
26. How do you think Bangladesh jute industry can improve their marketing system?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By collaborating with other departments • Recruiting skilled worker and professionals
Trading barriers	
27. What is your thought about different trading barriers that Bangladesh jute industry is experiencing?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are lots of trading barriers. Port problems, financial problems, coordination problems, and so on. Bangladesh is facing all the problems. We have barrier to export yarn, other jute product but no regulation on raw jute export. Negotiation with exporting countries is not good enough to sell our product there without any hassle and in good price. Need to remove these barriers from exporting yarn and DJP so we can export them easily

<p>28. How is Bangladesh jute industry tackling with such barriers?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private sectors are trying to solve the barriers. They are visiting other country, business fair and learning from them • recently the government has taken some steps to overcome the barriers. They have opened a new international port in Mongla to solve the port problem
<p>29. What policies Bangladesh jute industry applies when experiencing any logistic port problem?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In past it took almost one week to reach CTG port but now with the help of government we can reach CTG in short time. So I can say that we already overcome the logistic port problem
<p>Government involvement</p>	
<p>30. How Bangladesh Government helps with its rules and regulation to overcome logistic challenges experienced by Bangladesh jute industry?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Now every work is online based. So we face fewer problems than previous. That is only because of government help. But there is also a problem. We have only one international port. So sometimes here we face schedule problem. Government are already taking necessary steps to overcome it.
<p>31. Is there any other support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute industry? What are they?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Currently there is no support from government to improve current processing of jute in Bangladesh. It seems like government has no interest in the area, particularly in the development of DJP • Govt. are taking lot of steps to improve current position. They are making plan and policies to protect the jute sector but in reality, implementation is not happening • Govt. is very friendly about any project and research. They support to do the best. Govt. has positive attitude. We just need to do it properly. We

	<p>have around 280 diverse jute product that we are exporting worldwide. However, government is not doing this. It is being done by different small entrepreneur. They may have got some subsidies from government, but government can do more. Like arranging programs to train their skill. It will expand our opportunity</p>
<p>Sustainability</p>	
<p>32. How is Bangladesh jute industry working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We are using dust collector system to reduce dust that comes from jute processing. We have treatment plant for waste management • Bangladesh jute industry working in a sustainable manner. We don't use any chemical. That's why jute industry is not threaten to environment. • we are working by using biofriendly techniques to protect plant from pathogen, artificial retting to avoid hazard to aquatic eco-system etc.
<p>33. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • there are no govt policies or rules yet now to become sustainable. I think, Govt. have to make rules and regulation and to ensure that everyone is following it to become sustainable • Govt. has made lot of rules and policies but most of the factories are not maintaining it • yes, there are some rules and regulations. Government is making plans to make it more sustainable. However, the application of such rules is not satisfactory. Even, it is not present in all case. Most of the time, due to the

	<p>lack of proper implementation of policies, people are also reluctant in following them</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time to time government visit our factory and ensure the sustainability. They make lot of rules and regulation to keep it sustainable
<p>34. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many research and seminar should be held to aware people about DJP. Govt. and private sector have to come forward. Educational institute can increase interest of students to do research on this subject • Government should increase its subsidy and support DJP production. To improve performance in future we need effective manpower. More and more training and research need in this sector • focus on skilled manpower and upgrade technologies • research is needed to improve. Bangladesh government doing some work, providing fund but implementation of these courses is not so good. We need to monitor the whole system and improve it. • This country needs to make some policies and rules to improvement the present condition and ensure the implementation of it.

4.3 DATA FROM THEMATIC ANALYSIS

Information obtained from participants was then coded to narrow them down and to concise them in a manner that will answer the research questions (table 4). It will also help to gather similar statements that will validate the information while comparing it. Coding is the way to detangle qualitative data and extract desired information from it. After coding, similar information was grouped under

different themes. Some themes ended up with many codes that were further divided into sub-themes to get a clear understanding of the information. It helps to make it more rational and to keep related information together. As mentioned earlier, themes of current research were developed considering three facts. Firstly, themes were developed based on repeated information from interview questionnaires (Governmental assistance in advancement, future recommendation). Secondly, paying attention to the variables mentioned in existing literature regarding the advancement of Bangladesh's jute industry (advancement in diversified jute products). Thirdly, keeping research objectives in mind to set the boundary (strategic advancement). It helps to develop themes in a way that allows easy access to desired data in answering research questions. A tabular presentation codes for each theme is given below.

Table 4: Code, themes and sub-theme

Theme	Sub-theme	code
Strategic advancement	agricultural strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved variety use (AG1, AG2) • extending cultivable land (AG1, AG3, AG2) • Increased seed production (AG1, AG2 AG4) • Using optimised ribbon retting machine (AG2, AG1, AG3, AG4) • new cost-effective retting machineries (IP2, AG1, AG2, AG3, AG4) • artificial retting in limited scale (AG1, AG3, AG4) • Artificial retting as sustainable approach (AG1, AG4) • Using biopesticides as sustainable action (AG2, AG3) • hydroponic farming (AG1)
	Processing strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimizing production cost (IP1, IP2, JR1, IP4, M1) • Improved machineries compared to past (IP2, IP1, IP4, JR1, M1, AG4) • Lack of own machineries (IP1, IP2, IP4, M1, JR1, JR4, JR3) • No use of competitive technology and machineries (IP1, IP2, IP3, IP4, JR1, M1) • Private industries using modern technologies and machineries (IP3, IP2, IP4, JR4, JR3) • Introducing inverter-controlled machine (IP4, IP2) • following local and international law for sustainable production (IP4)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using dust collector system as sustainable approach (IP2, IP3) waste management (IP2, IP3, JR2)
	Marketing strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> conducting conference and seminars (IP1, M1, M3) jute fair and campaign locally and globally (IP2, M1, M3, M4) knowledge development program to educate farmer (M3, JR1, IP3, AG2, AG4) digital marketing (M3, M2, M4) Reduced price (IP1, IP2, M4, M1)
advancement in diversified jute product		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Comparable production of DJP (AG2, IP3, M1, JR1, IP4, IP1, M1) Actions by private and govt organization to improve diversified product (IP1, M4, IP4, IP2) Dying jute to make diversified products (IP2) jute sticks to make charcoal (IP2, JR1)
Governmental assistance in advancement	Policies/legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> policies and legislation (IP1, IP2, AG2, M1, JR1) regular audit to maintain sustainable performance (M1, IP4)
	Funding/financial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subsidy from government (IP2, AG1, AG2, M1, M4) support and involvement in improving technology or machineries (IP1, IP2, IP3, JR1) funding for standard level research (JR1, AG1, AG2)
	Other actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> logistic port issue (M1, M3, M1) Inter-government negotiation for trading barriers (M2, M1). actions towards transport (M1, M2, M3) Governmental support in research (IP1, T1, JR3) Governmental support in seed distribution (IP2, AG3, AG2, AG1)
Future recommendation	Diversified jute product	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> quantity and quality of DJP (IP1, JR1, JR4) technical and technological training (IP1, JR1, JR3, IP2, IP4) Support from both govt and private sector (IP2, AG1, JR1, JR3, JR4, IP4) trading cost (IP1, M1, IP4, M4) Seminar and conferences (IP1, AG3) proper infrastructure, management system and machineries (IP2, JR1, IP1, IP4)

	Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support from both govt and private sector (IP1, AG3, IP4, JR1, JR3) • upgrade machineries and technologies (IP2, JR1, M1, M3) • skilled manpower and professionals (IP1, IP2, IP3, JR1, JR2, AG2, AG4, M3, M2) • automate machineries (M2, IP2) • financial backup to advance technology (IP3, IP1, JR1, JR2, AG1)
	Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules and regulation in implementation (IP1, AG1, IP3, M4, T3) • Involvement of extension officer (AG1, AG2)
	Governmental action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • governmental involvement in reducing production and processing cost (IP1, JR1) • Governmental subsidy in local sale (IP2, AG1, M1, M4, JR3, JR4) • duty free export (M1, M3) • Financial assistance from government (JR1, M3, IP3, IP4, IP1, M2, JR4, AG2) • Setting accurate market price locally (AG1)
	strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementing plan and policies (IP1, AG1, M1, JR1) • quality product with reduced cost (IP2, JR1, M1) • utilize available cultivable land (AG1, AG3, AG4) • Producing own seed (AG1, AG4) • Implementing improved variety in field (AG1) • Vertical farming (AG1) • modern farming (weeding, harvesting-modern technology, retting-artificial retting) (AG1, AG4) • attract more buyer through seminar and meeting (M1, M4) • Removing trading barriers (anti-dumping barrier, port barrier) (M1, M3) • New market, extending sell in local market (M1, JR1)
	Research /education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing educational institute (IP1, JR1, M1, JR2, AG1) • improving research and collaboration (IP2, JR3, AG2, AG4, JR1) • funding from government in research (AG1, JR1, JR3, AG3) • more training for farmers and other jute workers (AG1, AG2, JR1)

N.B: IP-Industrial processing expert, M-marketing expert, AG-Agricultural expert, JR-Jute researcher

4.3.1 Strategic advancement

Assessing industrial advancement is the main target of current research. Any industrial advancement requires some strategic actions that will assist in improving their current performance. So, information from participants regarding the strategic actions is assembled under the theme 'strategic advancement' to extend the understanding accordingly. Earlier chapters have already highlighted the contribution of three domains (production, processing, and marketing) of any industry in advancement. Participants were also interviewed based on this professional categorization. Consequently, the theme here is sub-categorized following the mentioned professional backgrounds to better understand the information related to advancements in each domain.

4.3.1 Agricultural strategy

Agricultural strategy is the production strategy conducted at the field level to increase yield. It depends on the actions taken by associates like farmers and agriculture officers (professionals), who work in the field production. Farmers are the main characters whom we need to direct if we want to increase production. However, the involvement of agricultural officers is also important here who direct farmers in the right direction. In terms of the jute industry, participants with agricultural expertise were interviewed to understand current practices and advancements in raw jute production. Participants mentioned some advanced actions that are currently being implemented. Besides, they have also stated some planning that they are looking forward to and are under process.

It was mentioned by the participants that farmers exhibit reluctance towards jute farming due to the prolonged duration required for harvesting yields. Farmers cannot cultivate other commercial or food crops if they cultivate jute. It causes huge financial losses for them. Therefore, recently farmers are moving toward the jute varieties with what they can get yield comparatively earlier to grow another crop in the same field. They are aware of cultivating high-yield varieties compared to the low-yield varieties.

“Some type of jute needs 120 days’ time to harvest. But if it can be harvest within 100 days then farmer can cultivate another crop in the same season. But this being difficult with jute cultivation, farmers miss the season for other crops and are losing interest for jute.”

(Agricultural expert 1)

“There is a jute variety (GRO 52) comes from India that can give yield 20 days earlier. So, farmer is more interested to that variety.....”

(Agricultural expert 2)

Researchers and jute farmers in Bangladesh are considering expanding their cultivable land to increase jute production. They are showing an interest in developing and implementing stress-tolerant jute varieties to use the climate susceptible lands.

“Recently a variety has been founded (BJRI deshi pat 10) which can tolerate the salinity. It is in field application. Nevertheless, it is not being used that much still now as its just came in market very recently.”

(Agricultural expert 2)

The agricultural extension officers are helping farmers in different area of the country which is not suitable for jute cultivation, to introduce possible cultivation strategies that can be undertaken to produce jute. Farmers are really doing great, showing their interest. However, they need further motivation and if possible some financial assistance as well to start new cultivation strategy with associated risk.

(Agricultural expert 3)

However, the main issue hindering production advancement, as identified by the participants, was the inadequate supply of seeds to the farmers. Farmers are experiencing difficulties in getting cheap and desired amounts of seed from local providers. Hence, they need to collect seeds from illegal providers. Respondents emphasized that the Bangladesh jute industry is attentively working in this sector and planning to develop seed centres in the near future.

I think the seed distribution problem is another concern that the authorised people need to pay attention. Farmers are forced to buy expensive seeds which ultimately reduce their interest in jute farming. The easy availability of quality seed is very important, which is missing in our jute system

(Agricultural expert 4)

“We are trying to supply our own seed and use our own to have better use and quality.....we have the demand for Robi 1 variety seed. We applied for a government project for huge seed production, if it is granted then hopefully, we will be able to produce more seed and satisfy our farmer’s seed demand with the establishment of seed centre.

(Agricultural expert 2)

In terms of technological advancement in field production, Bangladesh industry is moving from conventional retting to advanced retting techniques. Retting is one of the main steps in processing fiber from jute sticks. Conventionally, it required a huge amount of water, and it was found to be hazardous to our environment. Farmers used to struggle with retting in water scarcity situations. It was also time-consuming and laborious work. This led the farmers to avoid jute cultivation.

However, agricultural officers or researchers have introduced some efficient and cost-effective retting processes. Farmers are now using this advanced retting method with improved machinery. Such a retting system allows farmers to process jute even if they have water scarcity. Nevertheless, there is also some problem with the existing retting system that the researchers are working on to propose a new, improved mechanism. Participants confirmed that farmers are using different cost-effective retting techniques and ribbon retting to reduce the quality damage of jute products. They are also focusing on using cost-effective retting techniques to optimize market price. The topic of artificial retting systems was brought up by one participant. However, it was noted that the application of artificial retting is limited to certain industrial levels.

In ribbon retting the jute stick get broken during retting processing and we used to get the jute fiber as output. But now we are activating new machinery that will break a bit of jute stick and we can get the fiber. So, we get fiber without breaking stick. We have also different retting techniques that is cost effective/ reduced cost so we can get preferred market price.

(Agricultural expert1)

Some industries are using different artificial retting techniques. However, it is in limited use since it needs special training and acceptance by the farmer to get it in field level.

(Agricultural expert 4)

Farmers are showing great acceptance towards cost-effective advanced retting techniques to get preferred market price. The agricultural extension officers conducting different program to introduce new retting techniques to farmer and they said that the acceptance rate is very good.

(Agricultural expert 3)

Participants were asked about the various sustainable strategies they are implementing to position themselves as sustainable jute producers in a global market. They shared that they are employing different practices that could be classified as sustainable, for instance, using bio-friendly pesticides and limiting the use of artificial retting. These efforts hold the potential to transform the jute industry. However, they expressed that they do not receive sufficient recognition as sustainable producers, and many farmers lack adequate education on sustainable production practices. This knowledge gap hinders their progress toward sustainable practices.

In present we are focusing on bio pesticides. We are trying to use environmentally friendly ways to treat jute. We are going for a sustainable agriculture now which will not harm the environment. Govt. are taking various steps to reach this goal

(Agricultural expert 2)

We have some sustainable practice that can be considered like bio-pesticides and artificial retting. But I do not think that these practices get recognition when government is trading the product. Anyway, there is positive responses from farmer to follow such instruction. They need more training and facilities (financial) to conduct such practice in huge scale.

(Agricultural expert 3)

Current research also emphasised to identify any possibilities in hydroponic cultivation of jute. Hydroponic cultivation is the modern form of cultivation to optimise the use of land. It was mentioned by the participants that this is not a suitable alternative cultivation option for jute. They mentioned in details that the root structure of jute is not suitable for hydroponic cultivation. Some researchers have been conducted their experiments in this topic but unfortunately, they have negative results for this

alternative approach. Participants stated that jute as a long-term crop has less possibilities to grow in hydroponic media. Such approach is mostly for short-term and high consumable crops.

With hydroponic jute cultivation, I only was able to get seedlings of jute from seed. When they were growing more, they didn't survive. We do not need only seedling of jute; to get fiber, we need whole plant. So, in my opinion, hydroponic is not proper alternative growing system for jute to increase yield in land scarcity.

(Agricultural expert 1)

4.3.2 Processing strategy

In terms of advancements in industrial processing strategies, participants highlighted several key factors: minimizing production costs, implementing advanced technologies, and adopting sustainable practices. They noted that reducing production costs could help meet buyers' price expectations. To compete in the global jute market, the Bangladesh jute industry is currently focusing on offering lower prices for high-quality products. The industry is concentrating on strategies aimed at surviving in a highly competitive global environment and is not prioritizing profit at this time; instead, their main goal is to maintain their presence in the global market. Many jute industries in Bangladesh have shut down due to bankruptcy, hence the primary concern of industrial professionals is to keep their operations productive and to create new markets.

“Production and other costing are very high in jute sector. Bangladesh Govt. is trying to minimize the costing so that we can produce more in the same cost and export more. Because buyer from various sector always want to buy in minimum cost, if our production cost remains high, we lose buyer. So, with lowering the production cost we can also attract buyer with reduced price and more production.

(Industrial processing expert 1)

Covid and Ukraine war and now war in middle east are affecting our jute market badly. Many of our jute industries are also shutted down because of their bankruptcy.

With all of this situation, industries whatever is left are now mostly focusing on surviving. Right now, we are trying to survive. It's really critical time for this sector.

(Industrial processing expert 4)

Participants informed that they are using different modern technologies in jute processing comparing to past. The machineries assisted them to increase the production and improve their quality of the product comparing to the machineries that they used before. The jute industry primarily relies on machinery imported from other jute-processing countries. Participants noted this reliance as a significant drawback to progress, as there are no domestic industries to invent or manufacture these machines. Despite being one of the top-ranked jute-producing countries, Bangladesh still lacks sufficient advancements in modern technology within the jute industry, which hampers its ability to compete in the global market.

Old model was not as good in production. With the old machine knitting company produced 5–6-tons product but with new one we can now produce 8–9-tons product. Similar to as past we are bringing machineries from abroad, (China), we do not have our own machine.

(Industrial processing expert 2)

Recently we are importing machine from China and India but I don't think Bangladesh has any of its own effort to manufacture the technology or processing. They mostly follow and dependent on the machine imported from other country.....; we were supposed to take strong position in jute but we could not. Because we do not have sufficient machineries.

(Industrial processing expert 1)

Stating the implementation of new machineries, respondents noted that private industries are taking more initiative in implementing new technologies compared to government industries. These private companies are integrating modern technologies into their operations and are generally more trained and informed about technological upgrades. Consequently, the respondents emphasized the need for government involvement to improve this situation. Additionally, participants from the industrial processing sector noted the recent introduction of inverted control machinery in the jute industry.

It is also a matter of concern that the privet industries are showing more positive attitudes and initiatives towards upgrading their machineries and technology

comparing to government industries. The private industries are more competitive in attitude as they want to make a good position in global market.

(Industrial processing expert 4)

In addition to revealing above mentioned information regarding different processing practices adopted by the Bangladesh jute industry, the researcher also identified facts related to sustainable practices that the industry is implementing. Sustainability as one of the burning facts in global market, researcher was trying to focus such initiatives undertaken by Bangladesh jute industry in their processing of jute product. It was informed that Bangladesh jute industries follow different international laws related to sustainable production namely labour law, using ETP and child law. They also employ effective practices like waste treatment and dust collection, which are crucial for sustainability. However, it's important to recognize that the adoption of these practices is inconsistent across the nation. Many industries remain resistant to fully implementing ETP and child labour laws. Implementation of ETP requires technical expertise, and many industries are experiencing difficulties with operating ETP. Some of them do not run their ETPs to save power even though they have the settings for ETP. So, participants mentioned the lack of proper operating knowledge and awareness while coming to the sustainable practice. By addressing these gaps, we can ensure that all jute manufacturers uphold sustainable standards, benefiting both the environment and society as a whole.

We are already using different machineries that are sustainable in their action. We also have measurements in processing our dust and residues from jute processing that help us to hold the micro-particles and waste from mixing with the environment.

(Industrial processing expert 3)

We need to follow the local law as well as comply with international law. When I am saying international laws, I want to mention about labour law, and particularly child law. You know how some people in our country misuse children at work against the child law. Abandoned children are working different places which is against the child law. However, we as jute industry in Bangladesh, we are trying to comply with global labour law. We are trying to respect the law made for child labour.

(Industrial processing expert 4)

4.3.3 Marketing strategy

Assessing the marketing strategy of Bangladesh jute industry was chosen as one of the objectives of current research. It was identified as an important fact to assess overall advancement in the industry. Marketing experts from different jute industries in Bangladesh were interviewed to understand current scenario of their strategies that the industry is following to meet global demand. To evaluate their marketing strategy, researcher questioned them about different marketing aspects like marketing technology, trading strategies, pricing and trading barriers. Participant informed that they are adopting strategies to advertise their products in global market. They try to attend and arrange different seminars around the world to exhibit their product as well as to understand product requirements where they can work accordingly. buyer from different country feel interested to visit the industry and monitor before making any deal. This is a good opportunity for the seller to attract them while they visit industry by showing variety products they have and possible products that can be made if proper support is given. Besides, different jute product fairs also occur around the world time to times that is helpful to get new buyer and to improve networking.

Buyer from different country comes to visit and we also visit them. This is how we attract them by showing them our production are. While visiting here, they can have first-hand look in our product and can assess its quality before buying. On the other hand, when we visit them, we can also have an idea about their requirement and can show our products during our visit to them. So, this is how we communicate sometimes to improve interaction between us and to increase sale..... We have to attend different fair which are held in different country (china, Germany, dubai).

(Marketing expert 1)

Professionals in the jute industry are organizing various conferences and lectures across the country to raise awareness among local communities about jute as a sustainable alternative to plastic. By fostering local demand for jute products, the industry can expand its market. Additionally, increasing public awareness of the sustainability benefits of jute will generate greater interest in this sector and help the industry progress.

We also exhibit different poster to let people know about our industry and its production. Sometime, we go to rural area to educate people about the advantage of

jute product over another alternative biohazard products. We invite different industrial personnel to discuss our product development and to discuss future possibilities.

(Marketing expert 3)

Participants were asked about their pricing strategy as it is one of the important facts in competitive marketing of product. Participants were not keen to discuss in details about their pricing strategies. However, it was mentioned that they are trying to reduce the price of product to grab more customer. They are mostly focusing on surviving in this competitive world. It was stated by the participants that current the industry is not looking for high profit strategy rather than prioritising surviving techniques. Participants also discussed various improvements and challenges related to trading barriers. The trading-related barriers represent a significant topic in marketing strategies that must be considered for advancement. However, much of the information provided by the participants were centered on the role of government involvement. The topic was therefore addressed under the theme of "Governmental Assistance."

4.3.2 Advancement in diversified jute product

It was identified from existing literature that Bangladesh jute industry has an enormous opportunity in global market with some improvements in their diversified jute product. Considering this, researcher interviewed participants about current production state of their DJPs. Most of the participant agreed on the progression of DJP comparing to past, although it was also mentioned that the progression is not satisfactory or in desirable level. Participants also compared the current progression of DJP in Bangladesh with its competitor countries. They stated that Bangladesh is still falling behind compared to other countries in providing the market with high-quality DJPs.

Different Govt and private organizations are taking action towards improving diversified jute products. However, I think that compared to India, Bangladesh is lagging in diversified product production. Besides, their current action is also not in satisfactory level what is expected by the global market. We have some DJPs produced by our industry but still need further actions to get them into global market

(Industrial processing expert 1)

Current advancement of DJPs is mostly occurring in small scales. Different private companies are showing interest in DJPs. They are analysing current demand and working on different DJPs in a small scale to avoid any associated financial loss.

They are the small intrapreneurs and are taking steps towards advancing DJPs of Bangladesh. However, to optimize the financial loss, they are mostly starting this production and processing at small scale.

(Industrial processing expert 4)

The advancements in various industries are becoming increasingly apparent. Many are taking initiatives to enhance the aesthetics of their jute products and to innovate new jute items as per market demands. Some industries are also experimenting with dyeing or blending jute fabric to make their products more appealing to consumers. Researchers are also interested in this issue to identify effective dyeing techniques for the industry. Furthermore, Bangladesh jute industry recently started using jute sticks to make sustainable charcoal. As it has been recommended by different research studies, the industry has recently started to implement this idea into action.

Recently we are dyeing jute to make diverse product. Some industries are dyeing jute to beautify its product. They are trying to get the market with something different with jute. Some industry is also dyeing blended jute products to satisfy customer demand.

(Industrial processing expert 2)

Even though the progression is not much significant. I have heard that some of the industry is trying to use different part of jute plant to make diversified products. Such as recently I heard that they are using jute sticks to make sustainable charcoal. Jute as a sustainable raw material, researchers are now trying to innovate different product from it to propose its efficient use in industrial level.

(Jute researcher 3)

4.3.3 Governmental assistance in advancement

The government plays a crucial role in the development of any sector within a country. No industry can thrive without the involvement and support of the government. The

participation of the Bangladesh government in the advancement of the jute industry was evaluated from the perspective of various participants. Based on their knowledge and experiences, they shared how the government of Bangladesh is assisting them through policies, legislation, financial support, and other actions to enhance their current market conditions.

Bangladesh possesses several policies designed to promote jute products as viable alternatives to plastic. However, the primary issue lies in the lack of effective implementation. By properly enforcing these regulations, we could drive a significant shift towards jute products, benefiting both the environment and the economy. Unfortunately, as highlighted by participants, this potential is not being realized in Bangladesh, underscoring the urgent need for action to harness the power of jute for a sustainable future.

“Government is taking lot of steps to improve current position. They are making plan and policies to protect the jute sector but in reality, implementation is not happening.... India has policy to buy jute product from industries to increase market. But we do not have such policies here implemented from government to increase our production,”.

(Industrial processing expert 2)

To become sustainable, yes there are some rules and regulations. Government is making plans to make it more sustainable. However, the apply of such rules is not satisfactory. Even, it is not present in all case. Most of the time, due to the lack of proper implementation of policies, people are also reluctant in following them.

(Jute researcher 1)

Government is making some plan and policies. But there no implementation of these plans. Government already banned poly bag from the market and order to use jute bag but still this is not happening.

(Jute researcher 2)

According to reports, only two participants mentioned that regular audits are being conducted in certain industries to monitor the implementation and performance of sustainable actions. They indicated that the government and some third parties have

recently initiated this process to track performance and encourage sustainable practices across the country. Regular monitoring is a positive step towards motivating the implementation of desirable actions. Therefore, this can be seen as an advancement for the jute industry in Bangladesh.

Government, third party organization and Buyer representative visit and perform audit Time to time in our factories. Labour ministry also does audit to the factory otherwise will not be possible to run the factories

(Marketing expert 3)

Participants also discussed about different financial supports from the government. Both the participants from field and industrial production have stated that their government's subsidies are extremely meagre and unacceptable. It has been noted that government funding is insufficient for advancements in technology and research. This lack of adequate funding is causing progress in the sector to lag. Conversely, two participants stated that funding is contingent upon proposing effective project plans. The government has funding available but requires a solid action plan to provide it

Our price sometimes bit higher in local market than the export because order volume is smaller in local market and also we do not get any subsidies from government.

(Marketing expert 4)

Government is happy to give fund, but we need to make project plan. We need to make appropriate plan and then government will fund us. In my opinion, government has the willing to support but at least we as researcher also has the responsibilities to provide excellent project plant that will worth the funding to bring advancement in our system

(Agricultural expert 2)

The government's role in industrial growth goes beyond just regulations and financing; it also involves actions that promote smooth global trade of products. Participants have noted that while government efforts to enhance trade are effective in some areas, there is still room for improvement in others. For instance, participants applauded governmental action in extending international trading ports and improving port

transport facilities. However, the way of governmental negotiation with trading countries were criticized by the participants.

In past it took almost one week to reach CTG port but now with the help of government we can reach CTG in short time. So I can say that we already overcome the logistic port problem. Government look into this problem and solve it.

(Market expert 1)

It is governments duty to resolve such problem and make negotiation with trading countries where we can sale our product. However, our government has lacking in this sector. Negotiation with exporting countries is not good enough to sell our product there without any hassle and in good price.

(Marketing expert 2)

4.3.4 Future recommendation

During the interview, respondents mentioned different facts that needed to be considered in improving current jute market in Bangladesh. This information was grouped under the theme “Future recommendations”. Furthermore, the theme was divided into sub-themes for better understanding of the topics. This segment of the research is crucial for directing future researchers and advising essential measures for the industry. Respondents suggested different actions mentioning associated challenges that they are experiencing.

4.3.4.1 Diversified jute product

In terms of improving current status in DJP, participants have suggested several actions that can be adopted in future. The action can be increased quantity and quality of DJP, technical and technological skill, skilled worker, skilled worker, contribution from both government and private sector, lower the trading cost to compete, motivating people towards DJP, more research, seminar and conference about DJP. Although participants noted that some private and governmental organizations are stepping in to improve their DJPs, they suggested placing greater emphasis on the mentioned aspects. Advancement requires cooperation from both parties—the government and private organizations. It is challenging for one party to make progress while the other remains inactive.

To increase the diversity in jute product. Government and other organization should pay attention towards improving technical and technological skill, skilled worker (training, knowledge) to produce diverse jute product.....We need to lower the cost of jute product to compete with that substitute market

(Industrial processing 1)

Research and seminar should be held to aware people about DJP. Govt. and private sector have to come forward. Educational institute can increase interest of students to do research on this subject

(Agricultural expert 1)

It can be another way to attract customer by lowering our trading cost for JDP. I know this is bit difficult to get profit with lowering trading price. This can be one of the ways to get market for our product at initial level. Just to start the market and make people interested

(Marketing expert 4)

4.3.4.2 Technology

Some technological advancement has been noticed in Bangladesh jute industry as per the comments from participants. However, they have also mentioned that the industry is lack of skilled worker or professionals to work on updated machineries. They further suggested that the industry should motivate new graduates to join the sector. They can use their knowledge in expanding the industry. It has become very important to recruit educated and experienced professionals in the sector. Besides, it was also mentioned that it will be better if Bangladesh can have its own manufacturer to develop required machineries rather than importing them. It will also be cost effective for the industry if they can develop their own machineries. On the other hand, agricultural experts (participants) indicated the importance of modern farming technology (weeding, harvesting-modern technology, retting-artificial retting) that will reduce production cost and will consequently solve the market price issue.

Not only in industrial technology, we also need to advanced field technology (artificial retting and modern harvesting processing) to lower the overall cost and to attract more buyer.....I think professionals need some training and motivation to use new

technologies. It can also be done by recruiting technology experts in the industry who knows which one is best to use.

(Agricultural expert 1)

We need to ensure the financial support. Without adequate financial support, it is not possible to compete with developed countries. Many industries around here are interested in upgrading their technology but lack of fund from government. So, this is one of the important facts that is hindering advancement in technology upgrade.

(Industrial processing 4)

4.3.4.3 Sustainability

In the issue of being sustainability, participants mostly prioritised imposing rules and regulation and to have their implementation. Professionals can engage to elucidate the significance of sustainability to the farmer. They have mentioned the role of agricultural extension officers who have direct contact with farmers and are in a position to motivate farmers to follow sustainable practices in the field. Sustainability is an important feature of any product in global market to reach the top position. Government should give attention to this matter that will add value to the jute product exported from Bangladesh. It was informed by the participants that different conferences and seminars are being conducted around the country to aware industrial personnel about sustainable practices. However, implementation and practice of such action are not inconspicuous. Therefore, it is recommended that requisite measures be implemented to operationalize the actions.

Different conferences and seminar occurs occasionally to inform us about recent practices around the world and to aware us about sustainable production processes.....However, I do not think such action are being implemented. We are learning about the effects of different sustainable production processes, but not implementing them in real life. It requires training, skilled knowledge, and most importantly adequate budget to undertake the actions.

(Industrial processing expert 4)

Not all the industries are maintaining sustainable measurements. Since there is not strict regulation from the government. Hereby, everyone is trying to take the

advantage. They are saving money by not implementing a sustainable plan. They have it just in paper and pen, not in reality.

(Jute researcher 2)

4.3.4.4 Pricing

Setting proper prices is also important to hold the market and to compete with other substitute products. It was observed that Bangladesh jute industry mainly has difficulties in lowering local prices as they do not have any subsidies from government when selling products locally. If the industry wants to expand, it also needs to attract local markets to increase demand. Participants suggested that government should provide subsidies in this sector to help in lowering market price. They also suggested government to allow duty free export of jute product that will increase export globally. Export commission bureau can make arrangement and deal with other countries to sell jute product in their country at standard price.

Governmental subsidies for local sale is not in place which make us to increase local jute product price while we have good amount of subsidy from government in terms of export

(Marketing expert 2)

Export commission bureau can make arrangement and deal with other countries to sell our product in their country at standard price.

(Marketing expert 1)

4.3.4.5 Strategy

To improve existing strategy of jute market, participants suggested that industry should focus on lowering production cost and assure quality production while the agricultural researcher should supply farmer their own seed rather than importing from India. Besides, there is some trading barrier issues (anti-dumping barrier, port barrier) that need to be solved by government to ease the market exchange.

If we can import machineries in lower price or make them by ourselves then we can reduce the production cost as well, which is very important currently in meeting global demand of jute product at lower price. Importing machineries from other country is expensive and affect the overall market price of our product.

(Marketing expert 1)

we just need to make sure that we have enough seed for these varieties to provide farmer and we need to take them in field application.

(Agricultural expert 2)

4.3.4.6 Research and education

While recommending steps for industrial strategies and actions, participants also prioritised the impact of research and education in the advancement of Bangladesh jute industry. Participants mentioned that development of research institutes and encouraging collaborative research will help to improve the research quality. Besides, adequate funding is also needed to facilitate research continuation. In addition to the advancement in the research sector, participants also discussed the importance of educational and training programs for farmers.

Many research and seminar should be held to aware people about diversified jute product. Govt. and private sector has to come forward. Educational institute can increase interest of students to do research on this subject. In this way we can hold the first position of jute sector in the world.

(Industrial processing expert 1)

Bangladesh jute sector are not getting proper research work. Most of the talent students are not interested in this sector. If they can find interest in it we would get strong research work.

(Jute researcher 1)

4.4 THEMATIC MAP

Once the theme has been developed from the code, it is time to interpret the data. Establishing a thematic map is one of the first steps in interpreting data of thematic analysis (Castleberry and Nolen, 2018). It provides a visual representation of the themes in a larger context to represent the target research phenomenon. Thematic map demonstrates how the themes are related to each other, directing the research aim.

Figure 8: Thematic map (self-created by the researcher)

Figure 8 represents the thematic map of current research. It was observed that all the themes are related to each other. For example, it can be said that advancement in DJP take place while there is advancement in industrial strategy and support from the government. Besides, participants also discussed different future recommendations regarding the advancement of DJP. The themes were also categorised into different sub-themes for precise discussion. Moreover, information in all the themes was found to contribute to the advancement of the jute industry.

4.5 CHAPTER SUMMARY

This chapter summarised and presented data obtained from participants in the current research. The chapter began with a review of the participants' demographic

information. This helps to develop a broad understanding of participants backgrounds and their depth of subject-related knowledge. Subsequently, information obtained from participants on each question from the questionnaire was presented here in this section. This has assisted in providing a brief of data obtained from each question to facilitate theme analysis and coding. Since, semi-structured interviews allow the researcher to follow the interviewee's interest in conversation. The researcher eventually left with a mountain of data that needed to be well organized. Hereby it is important to concise the information based on research objectives. Furthermore, the chapter presented data from thematic analysis which includes codes, theme and sub-themes. A broad discussion on each theme has also been provided here to discuss the findings. The findings reveal that the jute industry in Bangladesh is on the path to transformation, embracing a range of advancements in field production, processing, technology, sustainability, and marketing to align with global demand. Farmers are adopting early-yield jute varieties and enhanced retting techniques, leading to remarkable improvements in output. In addition, several companies are investing in state-of-the-art machinery comparable to that of leading competitors, positioning themselves for success. The industry is also innovating by creating diverse products from various parts of the jute plant, showcasing its versatility. Furthermore, participants highlighted exciting new marketing strategies that have emerged, enhancing the industry's appeal. The government's active support is pivotal in driving these initiatives forward, ensuring a bright future for the jute sector in Bangladesh. Nevertheless, current findings have also directed different flaws that the industry has in its advancement and need further consideration. Finally, a thematic map was developed to demonstrate the relationship among the themes and to present how the themes were subjected to the research aim.

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION

Current research aims to assess the present state of advancement in Bangladesh's jute industry. Existing literature predicted that Bangladesh's jute industry will experience an increase in global jute demand, which requires some advancement in the industry to meet the demand. In addition, researchers identified that the Bangladesh jute industry has the potential to be in the global market with such an increase in jute demand as a sustainable alternative to plastic. The status of Bangladesh's jute industry in the global market with its renowned product is well established. However, the competition is growing due to the advent of other exporting countries. Considering this fact, Current research aims to evaluate the industry's overall advancement to understand how they are progressing to meet demand. Current research targeted different domains of the Bangladesh jute industry subjected to the advancement. Participants involved in the industry were interviewed to obtain desired information about the industry.

The foregoing chapter depicted results acquired from current research data. It discussed information obtained from participants on different facts related to the research questions. In total, 16 participants associated with the Bangladesh jute industry were interviewed to gather in-depth information about the industry. The data acknowledges that the industry has undergone some recent advancements that still have potential for further development. It has also been noticed that the industry has plans for its advancement, which they are looking forward to. However, some actions are needed to speed up and implement the plans.

No data holds significance unless it is interpreted and contextualized in relation to the research questions (Castleberry and Nolen, 2018). Regardless of whether the data is qualitative or quantitative, it must be analyzed through the lens of specific research objectives to yield meaningful insights. This chapter is organized to explicitly demonstrate how the research findings correspond with the research questions, facilitating a clearer comprehension of how the study has effectively addressed its objectives. The chapter will critically examine the findings while linking them to existing

literature, thereby enhancing the understanding of how this research contributes to the academic body of knowledge.

5.1 RESEARCH QUESTION 1: HOW IS BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY WORKING TO INCREASE THEIR JUTE PRODUCTION (YIELD)?

The significance of agriculture in driving industrial advancement is well-established in current research. Improving raw production is essential for enhancing the quality of industrial products. Recent findings have highlighted the adoption of innovative field strategies within the Bangladesh jute industry. Participants in the study focused on four crucial aspects for agricultural improvement: variety enhancements, expansion of production, advancements in retting methods, and the promotion of sustainable agricultural practices. The following discussion will delve into these aspects in detail, elucidating their impact on the jute industry and broader implications for agricultural development.

5.1.1 Improved variety advancement and production expansion

Regarding improved variety, current research informed that farmers in Bangladesh are currently using some high-yield varieties in the field. They prefer the variety to get early harvest that will allow them to cultivate other crops in between next season. Existing literature has discussed different jute variety developments in the laboratory and their subsequent field trial (Khatun *et al.*, 2009; Mukul *et al.*, 2021). However, they failed to provide details about the improved cultivars that the farmers are using in the field. Putting light on this issue, some details of the variety were found in current research that is being used in the field application. Participants from current research mentioned that farmers are using GRO 52 jute variety in the field, which gives early yield. They have also mentioned about BJRI desi pat 10, which is being introduced in the field as a saline-tolerant jute variety. These advancements signify significant progress in the jute sector of Bangladesh, illustrating a growing commitment to integrating improved varieties into field applications for enhanced productivity and sustainability. However, the current study did not address advancements related to the expansion of cultivable land, a critical aspect discussed extensively in the existing literature (Hossain *et al.* (2020; Mahmud *et al.*, 2020). This gap presents an opportunity for future research to explore the actual land expansion practices within the Bangladesh jute industry.

On the other hand, participants mentioned that farmers mostly import seeds from India, which is validated by the statements from Islam and Ali (2017). Islam and Ali, (2017) stated that Bangladesh jute farmers are exporting cheap seeds from India. The research indicated this as a barrier in the advancement. In response to similar challenge, Lenaerts, Collard, and Demont (2019) have advocated for the establishment of a robust seed distribution system tailored to the needs of global jute farmers. The findings from current research reported that Bangladesh's jute industry intends to establish a seed centre to facilitate easy access of seeds to the farmers. Participants mentioned that the development of the seed centre is in progress. Hereby, it is evident that the industry is adhering to recommendations from existing literature and is making steady progress. This proactive approach not only aims to enhance the quality and availability of seeds but also underlines the importance of implementing strategic solutions to overcome existing barriers within the agricultural framework.

Current research also focused on identifying the potential of vertical and hydroponic farming in jute production. These innovative farming techniques are gaining popularity worldwide as a means to enhance crop yields in areas with land scarcity. Existing literature illustrates that various crops have successfully adapted to these farming methods, thereby enhancing production capabilities while promoting sustainable practices. Recent studies on hydroponic cultivation of jute have emerged, particularly in Nigeria, as highlighted by Olubanjo, Adaramola, and Alade (2021). Their findings suggested enhanced yields of jute species in hydroponic systems compared to conventional farming methods. However, respondents from a current investigation expressed conflicting views, arguing that both hydroponic and vertical farming approaches are expensive and lack effectiveness for jute cultivation. Participants noted that, while hydroponics may facilitate the growth of jute seedlings, it is insufficient for the complete development of the plant, which is essential for fiber harvesting once the jute reaches full maturity. As a result, researchers are inclined to conclude that hydroponics is not a viable solution for jute cultivation. Nonetheless, there remains significant potential for further research into various dimensions of hydroponic jute cultivation, particularly in the context of Bangladesh.

5.1.2 Advancement in retting approach

Current research identified no significant improvements in the retting system of Bangladesh's jute industry. Participants reported that farmers are primarily using the

ribbon retting process in their fields. This observation aligns with existing literature, which highlights a gradual shift among jute farmers from traditional retting techniques to the ribbon retting process (Ali *et al.*, 2015). However, some changes have come in between as per the comments from current research participants. It was reported that few industries are trying to implement artificial microbial retting on a limited scale. Prior studies have pointed out the benefits of microbe-assisted retting, which has been recognized as a more efficient alternative compared to ribbon retting (Rana *et al.*, 2024). Consequently, it can be inferred that the industry is starting to take into account the recommendations found in existing literature concerning the practical implementation of artificial retting methods.

Participants informed that the agricultural extension officers are actively working to introduce different advanced machinery to make the retting system cost-effective and efficient. Enlighten this, existing research in Bangladesh, including studies by Chakraborty and Begum (2023), provides evidence of various innovative retting designs. Notably, researchers advocate for the use of water tanks as a substitute for traditional rivers and ponds in jute retting, representing a strategic advancement. However, participants did not mention any specific strategies that are being implemented in the field. They only reported a notably favorable attitude among farmers towards these advanced retting techniques, suggesting a positive outlook for future adoption. This indicates that researchers are making significant strides in developing improved machinery and methodologies to address the challenges associated with ribbon retting. Furthermore, the enthusiasm among farmers towards these innovations underscores a readiness to incorporate such advancements into their agricultural practices. Nonetheless, it is imperative to undertake further investigation into the practical implications of these developments in the field to assess their effectiveness comprehensively.

5.1.3 Improvements in sustainable practices

Participants highlighted various eco-friendly cultivation methods being employed for sustainable field processing, including pathogen management, integrated pest management, and the use of biopesticides. The significance of biopesticides has also been discussed by existing literature (Ali, Haque, and Ahmad 2008; Haq, 2011; Srinivasan *et al.* 2019). However, respondents from current research noted that the

limited availability of biopesticides presents a significant challenge to sustainable advancement. It was stated that many farmers tend to prefer inexpensive and easily accessible pesticides.

On the other hand, participants noted that the implementation of ribbon retting and artificial retting at the industrial level is another sustainable practice, as it helps protect the aquatic ecosystem (Ranjan, Sow and Kumar, 2021). It requires less water, time, and cost to conduct retting compared to that of conventional retting. Conventional retting requires a substantial amount of water, which is a critical issue for the farmers in Bangladesh, who often reuse the same water due to scarcity. This practice has adversely affected local aquatic ecosystems (Roy and Hassan, 2016; Sarker *et al.*, 2022). So, the advanced retting approaches can be considered as another form of sustainable practice that is being followed at the field level. Besides, the industry is using different parts of the jute plant as by-products, namely jute sticks, to make fuel, charcoal ashes, carbon paper, and cosmetics, which further highlights its commitment to sustainability. However, participants in the current research expressed concern that, despite these sustainable practices, the industry lacks adequate recognition as a sustainable jute producer in the global market.

Moreover, recent research has highlighted promising advancements in the jute industry in Bangladesh concerning sustainable production practices. Notable improvements include the application of sustainable retting approaches, the effective utilization of various by-products derived from jute, and the incorporation of biopesticides in agricultural practices. Despite these positive developments, further improvements are essential to facilitate easier access to biopesticides and to bolster recognition of jute products in the global market.

5.2 RESEARCH QUESTION 2: HOW IS BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY PROCESSING THEIR PRODUCT TO SATISFY GLOBAL DEMAND?

The progression in industrial processing development has been marked by various factors that respondents have highlighted, paralleling the evolution of field strategy. Notable aspects include diverse processing strategies, the integration of advanced technology, the adoption of sustainable practices, and the diversification of jute products. These elements were identified as essential to framing the ongoing discourse surrounding industrial processing advancements and their implications for

the industry. Each factor contributes to enhancing efficiency, sustainability, and product variety, thereby fostering overall development within the sector.

5.2.1 Industrial processing strategy

In light of recent research, the industrial sector of Bangladesh's jute industry is primarily concentrating on reducing production costs as a means to enhance competitiveness. By strategically increasing the output of jute products while keeping expenses stable, the industry aims to lower prices and attract a wider customer base. This approach simultaneously seeks to elevate Bangladesh's position within the global market for jute products. Literature supports this strategy, with Pavel and Supinit (2017) proposing that cost leadership serves as a viable competitive strategy for penetrating the EU market. Additionally, Akter (2015) highlighted the potential effectiveness of a cost-based pricing model to boost the industry's global competitiveness. The documented success of cost leadership across various sectors reinforces its relevance; companies like IKEA, Walmart, Dell, and Ryanair illustrate how strategic implementation of cost-leadership can effectively dominate their respective markets (Jerab and Mabrouk, 2023). Despite these insights, a notable gap in information persists regarding the practical execution of strategic actions within the Bangladesh jute industry aimed at advancing production capabilities. Addressing this gap, current research reported the practice of cost-leadership in Bangladesh's jute industry assuming that it may enable the Bangladesh jute industry to achieve enhanced success and significant market penetration

5.2.2 Technological advancement in industrial processing

In the context of technological advancement within Bangladesh's jute industry, several participants in the discussion highlighted the country's reliance on imported machinery. Historically, Bangladesh sourced its jute processing machinery from Dundee, UK; however, there has been a notable shift toward imports from China and India in recent years. Islam and Ali (2018) identified key manufacturers namely Lagan Engineering Company Ltd, Milltex Engineering (P) Ltd, GSL (India), and Zhejiang Golden Eagle Co., Ltd, which supply machinery to Bangladesh. It is important to note that the majority of these companies are located in India and China. Participants felt that Bangladesh's use of the same technology as the exporting countries hindered any competitive edge in technological upgrades. Although this opinion reflects their perception of technological progress, it lacks supporting evidence to substantiate

claims regarding the country's competitive standing in this area. Furthermore, the discussion revealed that Bangladesh does not produce its own jute processing machinery, a factor that participants consider a barrier to competitive growth. Despite the existence of local manufacturers of jute processing machinery, as noted by Moazzem, Basak, and Rahman (2012), the reliance on external designs rather than the innovation of proprietary manufacturing processes significantly limits their potential. This reliance presents a challenge for advancing the technological capabilities of the jute industry within Bangladesh.

The technological landscape of the jute industry in Bangladesh appears to be significantly lagging behind that of competitive nations, particularly China and India (Hossain, Nishu and Freelance Researcher, 2021). Despite the apparent stagnation in advancements at the industrial level, there have been notable improvements in privately owned jute enterprises. These firms are increasingly adopting cost-effective technologies to enhance their processing capabilities. Stakeholders have emphasized the importance of additional funding and financial assistance from the government to support these initiatives and drive further technological upgrades within the sector. Such support could potentially bridge the gap and improve the industry's competitive position on a global scale.

5.2.3 Sustainable processing of jute

According to participant statements from the current research, the jute industry in Bangladesh has undertaken various sustainability measures in both agricultural practices and industrial processing. These measures include the implementation of dust collection systems, waste treatment plants, and environmentally friendly practices. Participants noted that jute processing is characterized by significant dust generation, releasing various micro-particles into the environment, which poses potential hazards to workers in proximity to machinery. To address these environmental concerns, dust collection systems have been integrated into jute processing facilities to capture dust and mitigate its impact on the surrounding environment. Furthermore, participants indicated adopting waste management treatments aimed at reducing waste exposure resulting from jute processing. However, it was highlighted that a considerable portion of the jute industry in Bangladesh remains unaware of these systems, which complicates efforts toward achieving sustainability.

Existing literature has indicated the presence of sustainable practices within the jute industry, primarily focusing on frameworks and mapping systems to evaluate the effectiveness of environmentally friendly processing approaches (Talapatra and Gaine, 2019; Quddus *et al.*, 2014). Nevertheless, it is evident from these studies that jute industries in Bangladesh are actively implementing measures aimed at sustainability.

In conclusion, based on participants' insights, while the industry has initiated some sustainable practices, further advancements are necessary for it to compete effectively in the global market.

5.2.4 Advancement in diversified jute product

Although the advancement in DJPs has been presented as an individual theme in current research, it was found to be more interconnected with industrial processing facts, which is why it is discussed further in this section.

Recent research highlights that Bangladesh jute industry has made significant strides in increasing its production of DJP compared to previous years. However, despite these advancements, production levels still do not meet global standards and demands, highlighting the necessity for further enhancements to fully exploit market opportunities. The main challenges to increasing production were mentioned as improper infrastructure, management system, machinery, lack of research center, and support from the government. It was identified that the involvement of entrepreneurs in DJP production is commendable. However, they are working in very small aspects. They are mostly targeting the local market for their product. Due to the presence of different export barriers (logistic port problem, pricing and marketing) and lack of subsidies from the government, the private entrepreneurs are getting demotivated from DJP. They are trying to avoid associated business risk with DJP. Islam and Xiaoying, (2016) analysed Bangladesh diversified jute market and stated different issues that are affecting the market negatively. Most of it was found to be associated with policies from the government and marketing limitations. Azad *et al.*, (2020) also stated different challenges in DJP development in Bangladesh. Supporting statements can also be found in the research conducted by Azad *et al.* (2020), mentioning the fact that Bangladesh is lacking in proper innovative ideas, market research, and

promotional agency. However, participants from current research did not mention any improvements solving the identified barriers.

Moreover, Current research findings confirm that advancements in DJPs are occurring in the industry regarding increasing the production. However, the existing challenges still remains as no initiatives to overcome this barrier were identified by current research.

5.3 RESEARCH QUESTION 3: WHAT COMPETITIVE MARKETING STRATEGIES ARE THEY ADOPTING?

Participants in the current research shared insightful perspectives on the advancement of marketing jute products. They identified proactive measures they are taking and strategic plans to enhance their marketing effectiveness. Their awareness of this field's obstacles and inventive solutions demonstrate their commitment to progress. Similar to the discussion for other industrial domains, this discussion on marketing advancement is also organized in topics that the participants prioritized.

5.3.1 Advancement in marketing actions with different training and exhibition facilities

The significance of a robust marketing strategy is critical for maintaining a competitive position in the global market (Hooley, Piercy, and Nicoulaud, 2008; Weerawardena, 2003). An effective marketing strategy can attract buyer attention, ultimately leading to an increase in product demand. Hereby, by analyzing the marketing strategies employed by the Bangladesh jute industry, its positioning in the global market can be estimated.

Recent research highlights various marketing strategies currently employed by the Bangladesh jute industry. Participants noted the importance of global and local trade fairs, conferences, campaigns, and exhibitions, where producers actively promote their jute products to attract buyers. These are the recent activities that Bangladesh jute industry is conducting to promote their product both in local and international market. Mohiuddin, (2015) also mentioned the same marketing approaches that is being undertaken by Jute Diversification Promotion Centre (JDPC) in Bangladesh to motivate and provide open marketing platform for jute entrepreneur in Bangladesh. It is surely a great initiative if compared to the past scenarios of the Bangladesh jute market (Mohiuddin, 2015). Respondents mentioned that with the improvement in

technology and globalization, it is easy to connect with buyers around the world. However, Marketing participant-2 asserted that such marketing opportunities are not very frequent to take place. It was suggested that frequent activities like this will help the industry to reach more buyers and increase the sale. So, the JDPC can pay their attention here to arrange more marketing activities in future. Islam and Xiaoying (2016) suggested the involvement of the government in this area to increase people's concern about jute products by arranging different product exhibitions and by imposing rules to use jute bags in the different governmental sectors. Besides, a governmental raw jute purchase center can be developed, as it has been suggested by Akter, Sadekin, and Islam (2020), to make marketing easy for the farmers to trade within the country. Current research participants mentioned that the involvement of farmers in knowledge development programs is currently being conducted by the industry. They informed that different programs are being conducted by the extension officers to educate farmers about new technologies and advancements in the system.

Moreover, Recent research has shed light on the innovative marketing strategies embraced by the Bangladesh jute industry. This study highlights these practices and identifies key improvements that could significantly elevate the industry's performance.

5.3.2 Digital marketing

In today's era, digital marketing is one of the essential tools towards success. It is a great way to attract buyer around the world (Li, Larimo and Leonidou, 2021). With the implementation of digital or E-marketing, industrial personnel or business owner can promote their product and in the same way, consumer can have easy access to the product information they want. Respondents from the current research highlighted the lack of e-marketing practices in Bangladesh's jute industry. It was mentioned that social media is dominating a huge of marketing in today's world. However, the jute industry in Bangladesh is still lagging behind in utilizing this effective marketing medium for its advancement. It was evident that, despite their awareness of the significance of E-marketing, the industry appears deficient in its implementation. Existing research on the Bangladesh jute industry has mentioned the importance of digital marketing in this industry. Islam and Xiaoying (2016) asserted that online shopping can be a great way for the buyer to get to know about the product and have easy shopping. It can be an effective way to attract buyers from around the world.

Therefore, it can be concluded that while research underscores the value of digital marketing and industry experts acknowledge its significance, the sector has yet to embrace its implementation fully. This presents a crucial opportunity for the industry to leverage digital marketing strategies and stay competitive in today's market.

5.3.3 Advancement in pricing strategy

Pricing plays a critical role in marketing strategies, especially within competitive industries. Recent studies have highlighted the positive impact that competitive pricing can have on influencing consumer behavior (Ali and Anwar, 2021; Sudirjo, 2023). In light of this, participants in the current research were probed regarding their pricing strategies in response to the global demand for jute. Insights gathered from industry participants revealed that the jute industry in Bangladesh purchases raw jute from the local market and exports jute products at a relatively low-profit margin. The industry receives considerable financial support from the government for exporting jute products, for instance, a 20 percent cash incentive when selling their products internationally (Mustafa, 2022). This support allows industrialists to reduce their export prices compared to those in the local market, as they do not receive any incentives for local sales. Consequently, they set higher prices for the local market, negatively impacting local demand.

However, the current global crisis of COVID-19 and the Ukraine war has changed the situation. There is market instability everywhere. The global crisis has negatively affected the global market for all kinds of products. Jute products are not different from it. Besides, jute products are not necessary and essential for living daily. People worldwide are now suffering to satisfy the demand for essential products. In this condition, the customer is not attracted to products they do not need daily. In addition, the crisis situation is also affecting the global supply chain, which has a consequent impact on the global market (Aday and Aday, 2020; Jagtap *et al.*, 2022). So, the global demand for jute is experiencing some ups and downs. However, the participant stated that the jute market is always unstable. This has an impact on buyers and pricing. In this condition, the jute industry in Bangladesh is currently implementing different pricing techniques even if they have few losses or low profits to hold the market. With reduced prices, they are targeting to grab more customer and keep their production steady. The validity of using a price strategy in competitive market development can be found in the research by Prdic (2016). It was identified in the research that a low-

price strategy helps to protect the local market and to increase consumers for the product. It can be one of the ways to present quality products in the market with low profit that aim for higher future interest in obtaining prospective product demand.

5.4 RESEARCH QUESTION 4: WHAT GOVERNMENTAL ASSISTANCE ARE THEY RECEIVING IN THEIR ADVANCEMENT?

The participants' perceptions of governmental support were thoroughly examined, leading to the identification of three primary areas of concern. Discussions centered around the government's role in policymaking, funding allocation, and various trade-related initiatives. Despite the potential for positive outcomes, current research suggests that participants predominantly held a negative view of governmental support. Specifically, they expressed dissatisfaction with the government's initiatives in both policy and financial assistance. Subsequent sections will provide further elaboration on participants' comments on governmental actions.

5.4.1 Advancement in policies and regulation

It was mentioned that various rules and regulations are present in Bangladesh regarding jute use and industrial processing (regular monitoring, sustainability, farming, jute processing, and using jute bags in shopping). However, the implementation of such rules is not very strong, letting the associated people disobey them. Paulsen (2022) also demonstrated the same scenario in the Bangladesh jute industry, where there are rules and regulations but no implementation. It was recommended by the researcher that Bangladesh needs proper implementation of its laws. Different factors have also been identified by existing literature that can be a cause for such issues. For example, ineffective public administration, lack of transparency, and corruption (Paulsen, 2022). So, the policymakers in Bangladesh urge for functioning policies that can bring changes in the overall system. It should be ensured that the rules and regulations are not only in paper and pen but also being implemented correctly. Enforcement of laws and regulations is far more important than only stating them. So, no advancements in government actions regarding the implementation of rules and regulations have been observed.

5.4.2 Governmental funding and financial support

Financial support at both industrial and field levels is not satisfactory as per the comments from participants. It was mentioned that the subsidies provided by government is very less that is not sufficient to assist industrialists in minimizing their prices. Farmer also being deprived of any financial support to increase their production. Azad *et al.*, (2020) mentioned that due to the lack of funding or financial support, farmers cannot afford to use upgraded tools, technology, seed and other cultivation facilities. This can have associated consequence on the quality of jute product. Besides, most of the jute mills have been closed recently in Bangladesh for which participants indicated a lack of funding and support from government as main reason. It is such a failure of the government to let the jute mills close while the demand for jute is expected to increase in the near future, and Bangladesh, as a top producer, could have great prospects in this area. Hossain, Nishu, and Freelance Researcher (2021) stated several reasons behind the closing down. The reasons are old infrastructure, technology, governmental policies, corruption, lack of proper management, skilled worker crisis, and poor marketing. Researchers suggested that the government should have reformed the structure of jute mills instead of shutting them down. According to the National Jute Policy 2014, the Bangladesh government aimed to reopen closed jute mills by 2021 and to upgrade them to meet global demand (Paulsen, 2022). However, the current scenario of closing down public mills indicates that the government failed to meet the target. Mostly, it's the private jute mills that are dominating Bangladesh's jute industry.

However, participants indicate that limited funding for research and development is accessible, contingent upon a comprehensive project plan. The administration has indicated its readiness to allocate funds as effective proposals emerge. Respondent also stated that existing research funding is not sufficient to carry out the standard level of research. So, it can be said that no improvement has taken place in the governmental financial support compared to the past statements from existing literature. The industry is still seeking economic assistance from the government to advance its condition.

5.4.3 Advancement in resolving trading barriers

Despite such negativity, few positive responses were found about governmental involvement in Bangladesh's jute industry. For example, participants mentioned that

the government is taking steps towards developing more trading ports, which will help to ease the logistic port problem that Bangladesh jute producers experience. The transportation system is also being improved, while earlier it was a challenge for Bangladesh's jute industry. Akter, Sadekin, and Islam (2020) mentioned that jute farmers had to pay high for transportation. Transportation is very important for Bangladesh jute farmers as they have a shortage of storage facilities. They need to transport their harvested jute as soon as they have it to minimize any associated loss (Azad *et al.*, 2020). So, with the improvement in road facilities mentioned by participants, the problem can be assumed to be well noticed.

On the other hand, compared to the past, most of the dealing and negotiation is now online, which helps the producer or seller to minimize their communication hassle. Participants stated that with the advancement in technology, it is easy to contact buyers. However, governmental actions were criticized in negotiating with international buyers or with other exporting countries. For instance, India recently imposed anti-dumping rules on exporting jute from Bangladesh, which caused the shutdown of many jute-related businesses in Bangladesh. It was mentioned that the Bangladesh jute industry mostly experiences different trading barriers in exporting jute yarn/ DJP but not raw jute. There are no rules and regulations in terms of exporting raw jute from Bangladesh to India. India imports raw jute from Bangladesh and then makes different jute products to trade in the global market. Participants stated this as a flaw in government to make profitable dealing with exporting countries. A recent study by Bhuyan and Oh (2024) also indicated the adverse impact of this AD issue of India against Bangladesh as with a negative impact on India itself. It is mentioned that the import of specified products from Bangladesh is declining with the imposition of such regulations. Besides, India is also experiencing imports from unnamed countries due to trade diversion from Bangladesh. Both the participant and existing literature recommended an urgent step from the Bangladesh government to resolve this issue.

The above-mentioned scenario of trading barriers aligns with the discussion by Rahman and Khaled, (2011). Rahman and Khaled (2011) also confirmed that the Bangladesh jute industry is experiencing different trading rules from different exporting countries that affect its marketing effectiveness. The exporting countries also demands specified packaging requirements that are difficult for Bangladesh's jute industry to meet and consequently fail to have competitive trade with the country. For instance,

the labeling requirement imposed by India caused Bangladesh's jute industry to incur extra costs to meet the condition. Besides, many countries impose complex custom clarification procedures that take extra time and cost and consequently affect overall profit. Hence, Bangladesh needs to pay sincere attention to resolving its trading barriers if it wants to become competitive in the global market.

5.5 MAIN RESEARCH QUESTION: HOW IS BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY WORKING TOWARDS ITS ADVANCEMENT (AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION, INDUSTRIAL PROCESSING AND MARKETING) TO MEET GLOBAL DEMAND?

The above discussed findings of current research in relation to the sub-research questions provides a valuable insight into how these outcomes address the main research question. Notably, each analyzed domain is undergoing significant developments. In the agricultural sector, there has been a marked shift towards the adoption of improved jute varieties, coupled with advancements in the retting process compared to traditional methods. Current research highlights the proactive measures taken to ensure an adequate supply of seeds to farmers, particularly through the establishment of dedicated seed centers. This progress simultaneously addresses the identified research gaps by offering updated insights into the agricultural strategies being implemented to increase production and meet global demand. In parallel, the industrial processing sector has also demonstrated progress, especially concerning its processing strategies focused on low-cost production and improvements in DJPs. Furthermore, significant efforts have been made toward implementing sustainable practices within this sector. Therefore, current research illuminates the advancements within industrial processing while indicating areas that warrant further improvement. Moreover, the research elaborates on various marketing strategies currently employed, including fairs, conferences, campaigns, exhibitions, and low-price strategies. Additionally, it points towards emerging strategies aimed at improving market conditions, like enhancements in trading ports and transportation logistics.

Therefore, it is evident that the industry is making significant strides in response to global demand. However, respondents have identified several critical issues that require urgent attention to accelerate progress and enhance overall effectiveness.

5.6 FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

One notable objective of the current research is to develop an action model that will direct industry stakeholders to implement essential initiatives. So, along with a broad discussion on how the findings meet research questions, the chapter also presents information regarding future actions.

To achieve the information, participants were interviewed to share their insights on the industry's future directions. Their comments were recorded to help create the action model (figure 8). Table 5 provides an overview of the actions and current challenges identified by participants in this research. It was noted that addressing these challenges will help the industry achieve its advancement goals. Structuring the recommended actions and challenges in Table 5 correlates with the research objectives, enhancing the understanding of future actions compared to the current practices adopted by the industry.

Table 5: Identified facts and issues in the advancement of Bangladesh jute industry following participant's comments

Research objectives	Advancement facts	contemporary challenges
Agricultural advancement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved variety in the field (GRO 52, BJRI desi pat 10) • establishment of the seed center is in process • Moving from conventional retting to advanced retting • Limited use of artificial retting • Using bio-friendly measures to control pest and pathogens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy access to quality seed and its proper distribution • Implementing improved ribbon retting strategy in the field • Implementation of cultivable land expansion strategies • Easy availability of biopesticides • recognition as a sustainable producer • Further research on jute hydroponic possibilities
Industrial processing advancement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working towards low-cost production • Improvement in private industries with advanced technology • Using different sustainable processing measures • improvements in increased DJP production (small-scale production) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manufacturing own machinery • Application of automated technology and robotics • Consistency and global recognition in sustainable practice • advancement in infrastructure, management system, and research centre for DJP

<p>Advancement in marketing strategy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Undertaking different global or local trade fairs, conferences, campaigns, and exhibitions • knowledge development program for farmers conducted by extension officer • Implementing low price strategy • Improvements in trading port and transportation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequency of global or local trade fairs, conferences, campaigns, and exhibitions • Extending open marketing platform for jute entrepreneurs and farmers in Bangladesh • Implementing digital marketing
<p>Governmental assistance</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement in transportation and trading port • regular audits are being conducted in few industries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfactory implementation of rules and regulations • Adequate financial support • Improvement in anti-dumping issues, governmental trading negotiation, packaging, and labelling

In addition to the recommended actions—agricultural strategy, industrial processing, marketing strategy, and governmental assistance—participant comments regarding future actions for research and education, as detailed in Table 4 of Chapter 4, have also been integrated into the action model represented in Figure 8. The advancement of research and education is essential for fostering improvements across all industrial sectors and emphasizes the necessity for government support to effectively realize these initiatives. Consequently, this aspect has been highlighted separately alongside the other recommended actions delineated in Table 5.

Furthermore, insights gathered from existing literature are incorporated alongside participant feedback to formulate a comprehensive final action plan depicted in Figure 8. The combination will offer a wide range of recommendations for the professionals. Since existing literatures has recommended a variety of actions for the development of Bangladesh's jute industry which are still unnoticed by the policymakers. So, current action plan can illuminate the overlooked facts while incorporating new ideas suggested by the participants. A broad discussion on the action model is presented below.

Figure 9: Proposed action model for the improvement in Bangladesh jute industry

5.6.1 Strategic advancement

The discussion regarding the industry's recommended strategic advancement has been systematically organized into three categories: agricultural strategy, processing strategy, and marketing strategy. This structured approach enables a detailed examination of each sector, as the research aims to delve into the specific developments taking place within these contexts. Consequently, the insights gathered can be effectively presented to provide a clearer comprehension of the initiatives being implemented within each respective domain.

5.6.1.1 Agricultural strategy to increase the yield

To improve the agricultural processing of jute, participants prioritized the establishment of a seed centre that provides farmers with easy access to quality seeds. Many participants highlighted that the distribution of quality seeds is one of the biggest challenges they currently face. Farmers are forced to purchase expensive foreign seeds from various dealers, which is diminishing their interest in cultivating jute. Therefore, any prompt action by the government to establish a system for distributing quality and affordable seeds would be beneficial for the industry's advancement.

Participants also noted that researchers are developing improved jute varieties, which are currently in the field trial stage. Implementing these varieties at the commercial level will help increase the current production rate. Existing literatures can be found to provide details of varieties that need further attention and commercialization. For instance, BJRI Tossa Pat 7 (MG-1) has demonstrated satisfactory yield in field trials and has been recommended by the researcher to use at the commercial level (Mukul *et al.*, 2021). On the other hand, to increase production, it is important to bring different climate susceptible lands under cultivation and use modified varieties. So, policymakers should pay sincere attention here to find improved jute varieties that can be brought under commercial use.

Haq, Ghosal, and Ghosh (2004) demonstrated the importance of waterlogged land in Bangladesh to bring under jute cultivation. Supporting the statement, Kaur *et al.*, (2020) also proposed different strategies for waterlogged cultivation. For example, adjusting the cropping date, surface tile drainage, and organic floating beds. On the other hand, existing research has proposed different cropping patterns that will allow effective land use and increase jute production (Hossain *et al.*, 2020). It is mentioned

that such an improved cropping pattern will allow farmers to cultivate jute in different regions of Bangladesh, including coastal regions, hilly regions, and agroforestry zones. Improved cropping patterns were proposed to include jute cultivation in the char land of Bangladesh (Mahmud *et al.*, 2020; Sarker *et al.*, 2022). Farmers in Bangladesh still need to adopt this proposed strategy to extend their jute cultivation.

Both participants and existing literature have provided valuable recommendations for enhancing ribbon retting. Comments from current research respondents indicate that farmers have a positive response to the ribbon-retting approach. It is crucial, however, for them to integrate improved ribbon-retting strategies into their regular practices to successfully address the challenges posed by traditional methods. Researchers are exploring effective retting techniques to help farmers minimize unexpected consequences and reduce environmental pollution. For instance, Chakraborty and Begum, (2023) propose the advantage of using a water tank instead of river and pond water in the retting system. Embracing these advancements will significantly benefit their operations and productivity.

Recent research participants have highlighted various factors hindering Bangladesh's sustainable agricultural advancement of the jute industry. One significant issue is the lack of accessible biopesticides, which prevents farmers from implementing sustainable cultivation practices. The lack of adequate knowledge and training on sustainable cultivation also discourages farmers from adhering to sustainable rules and regulations. It was also mentioned that the industry lacks proper recognition despite a few steps taken toward sustainable farming. This lack of acknowledgment demotivates farmers, as their initiatives go unrecognized.

Moreover, recommendations offered by current research participants were found to be more or less the same as the existing literature. However, existing literature was found with brief information where research respondents mostly provided a broad view. For example, existing literature recommended the use of water tank retting, and participants from current research stated that such implementation needs to be in regular field practice to get effective outcomes. On the other hand, the current research participants highlighted the importance of establishing seed centres, a concept that has not yet been addressed in the existing literature. This initiative could

significantly benefit Bangladesh's jute industry, helping it to enhance its global competitiveness by following the action model proposed in the current research.

5.6.1.2 Industrial processing strategy to meet global need

Participants in the current research informed that jute industries in Bangladesh mostly import machinery from other competitive countries. Therefore, the advancement level in their technological upgrade is not competitive. Considering this fact, it is highly recommended that the industry pays sincere attention to manufacturing their own machinery so that they do not need to rely on other countries. Participants (IP2, M2) and existing literature (Islam and Ali, 2018; IJSG 2012) have also discussed the importance of automated machinery to improve the state of technological advancement in Bangladesh's jute industry. Islam and Ali (2018) stated that with automated machinery, the industry would be able to improve the quality of products.

Regarding sustainable processing advancement, the industry was found to imply few sustainable actions. Existing literature has also worked to identify effective, sustainable measures that will bring prosperity to the industry. Biswas, Ridwan-UI-Risty, and Datta (2019) presented a sustainable and integrated plant plan to help Bangladesh's jute industry become sustainable in jute processing steps. The plan includes using a Dedicated Effluent Treatment Plant (ETP) that will help reuse water already used in jute fiber processing. However, participants stated that they need proper recognition as this has also been highlighted for sustainable agricultural practice. Industries will be motivated to follow sustainable processing strategies if they get proper recognition and certification.

Existing literature studied different management and processing strategies to assess their effectiveness in improving the quality production of Bangladesh's jute industry. For example, Haider and Rafiquzzaman (2023) recently demonstrated the significance of using Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) practices in enhancing the overall performance of Bangladesh's jute sector. Researchers recommended enhanced practice of such a strategy to allow quality production. On the other hand, Peu (2019) also recommended the establishment of Management Information System (MIS) and composite jute mills in the advancement of the industry.

Both existing literature and participants from current research indicated that Bangladesh's jute industry needs further advancement in improving the quality of its

DJP. To compete with other countries, they need to aim for diverse products in their production system and to assure quality products in the market. It was indicated by the participants that the industry needs proper infrastructure, management system and research centre to advance their DJP. Further recommendations can be obtained from existing literature to work on innovative ideas, market research, and promotional agencies to advance current state of Bangladesh's DJP (Azad *et al.*, 2020).

Moreover, a thorough analysis of current research data and existing literature uncovered a range of compelling recommendations for advancing the processing quality of Bangladesh's jute industry. Significantly, the findings regarding the enhancement of DJP (Diversified Jute Products) and manufacturing machinery present a valuable opportunity to strengthen Bangladesh's jute industry's competitive edge. By embracing these advancements, the industry can position itself for greater success in the global market.

5.6.1.3 Marketing strategies

Participants in current research discussed product exhibitions, fairs, training programs, campaigns, digital marketing, and pricing as their advancement in marketing strategies. However, it was stated that the frequency of such local and international exhibitions needed to be increased compared to their current occurrence. It provides a great platform for the producer to attract customers and improve networking. Many entrepreneurs are taking the initiative to get engaged with the jute industry. So, the current research participants suggested that such an open marketing platform will enormously help entrepreneurs prosper. Recent research by Akter, Sadekin, and Islam (2020) has directed the importance of governmental raw jute purchase centres in this regard that will allow easy local trade of jute products. It can be added to the recommendations from current research participants to develop an effective marketing system for the Bangladesh jute industry.

The importance of E-marketing has already been discussed in earlier chapters. It was identified that despite the significance of digital marketing in the recent marketing era, existing literature lacks information regarding the advancement of the Bangladesh jute industry in digital marketing. Considering the identified research gap, the participants were asked about their knowledge and experience in digital marketing. It was identified

that the professionals are well aware of the rise in the digital era but with no actions to advance their system. Mohiuddin (2015) suggested notable advanced actions in social marketing long ago, which still seem absent in the industry. It was mentioned that the Marketing Intelligence System (MIS) and Jute Bulletin in Bangladesh can assist in improving their marketing system. Researchers also stated that with the use of features in different magazines, particularly interior-decorating magazines, the Bangladesh jute industry can improve its marketing status. Furthermore, rural radio or bulletin to make important information available to the farmer and agriculture-based mobile service to farmers are prospective opportunities to improve the current marketing status of the industry (Rahman, 2017; Rahman and Hossain, 2014).

Taking these important steps is essential for driving the future marketing success of the Bangladesh jute industry.

5.6.2 Governmental assistance

The most recommended action for the future advancement of the Bangladesh jute industry is to ensure the proper implementation of existing rules and regulations. Participants consistently pointed out that, despite having these guidelines on paper, the real challenge lies in their execution. The shortcomings in enforcement are evident across all areas, including sustainability, pricing, trading barriers, marketing strategies, and agricultural production. By addressing this issue, we can unlock the full potential of the jute industry and drive significant progress. On the other hand, participants emphasized the vital role of government financial support in driving future progress. Adequate funding is crucial for farmers, researchers, and traders, as it can significantly enhance the overall system. They pointed out that pricing challenges are directly tied to the absence of government assistance. Furthermore, the lack of subsidies for local jute product trade hampers growth and viability in this sector. Any financial assistance from the government can help them to reduce product prices at both local and international levels and to extend the market. Rifath (2018) suggested that implementing easy loan services for farmers from the government would help them utilize quality seeds and other necessities in jute production.

Participants highlighted the critical issue of anti-dumping measures that are obstructing the industry's growth. With India as our closest trading partner, the potential for a mutually beneficial relationship is immense. However, India's recent

anti-dumping regulations against Bangladeshi products are stalling trade progress. To overcome this challenge, participants emphasized that a proactive approach from the government could lead to fruitful negotiations with India, ultimately fostering a more prosperous trading environment for both nations. Recent researchers (Bhuyan and Oh, 2024) also discussed the fact as a potential adverse impact on the industry.

Additionally, the industry is encouraged to focus on properly labeling and packaging their products for the international market. It was stated that the industry lacks proper recognition or branding as a sustainable jute producer. Both the participants from current research and existing literature (Rahman and Khaled, 2011) have prioritized this fact to improve the industry's position in the global market.

Moreover, the implementation of rules and regulations, financial assistance, anti-dumping issues, product packaging, and labeling were the facts that were mentioned in the recommended governmental support discussion. It was mentioned that the industry is taking the required action to develop its seed centre. However, the research participants desired further assistance from the government in speeding the process. Participants also suggested strong collaboration between government and non-government organizations to speed up the advancement. They are both inseparable parts of each other to reach industrial success. Therefore, it was mentioned that they should work together towards the advancement. Finally, participants emphasized that sustaining research efforts and translating findings into action is a crucial challenge for the industry. Numerous studies focused on the Bangladesh jute industry are underway, yet the crucial step of following up on this research is lacking. Addressing this gap is essential for driving progress and innovation in the sector.

5.6.3 Research and education

During the interviews conducted for this study, participants expressed significant concerns regarding the inadequacy of research and educational facilities that are hindering the advancement of the jute industry in Bangladesh. Although there exists a substantial body of literature on this sector, the participants emphasized that many research findings have not been effectively translated into field applications. Emphasizing the importance of ongoing research and its practical application is vital for accelerating industrial growth through the adoption of recommended actions. This perspective is supported by the work of Islam and Ali (2018), which highlighted the

pivotal role of comprehensive research in fostering advancements within the jute industry. Even recommended future work on mechanical and chemical machinery development in Bangladesh's jute industry suggested by Islam and Ali (2018) still remains neglected. Current research identified that the industry lacks improved machinery developed by its own local manufacturing sector.

It was also mentioned that the country does not have adequate research institutes to facilitate advanced research on jute to motivate young researchers to join the industry. They highlighted the lack of financial support as a core reason behind this issue. So, future assistance from the government to provide financial support in this sector was urged. Asrafuzzaman and Islam (2021) also underscored the necessity for enhanced government investment to foster research and innovation within the jute industry. Furthermore, participants suggested that collaboration between different organizations and countries in research could benefit the quality of research in the jute sector.

5.7 CHAPTER SUMMARY

This chapter comprehensively reviews and critically analyzes the research findings. By aligning the results with the established research objectives, it clearly demonstrates how the study successfully achieved its goals. Moreover, the in-depth discussion of these findings in relation to existing literature highlights their significance and underscores their potential impact on advancing knowledge in this field.

Recent research has identified several agricultural advancements in the industry, including using improved jute varieties, implementing advanced retting techniques, technological upgrades, a bio-friendly cultivation approach, and progress toward establishing seed centres. Additionally, participants identified that a cost leadership strategy is being implemented in the industry to compete in the global market. They believe this approach will enhance the industry's ability to thrive in global competitiveness. It was also mentioned that Bangladesh's jute industry has significant improvement in DJP (Directly Justified Production) compared to the past. This shift has attracted numerous entrepreneurs who recognize the potential of DJP, highlighting the urgent need for further enhancements. Participants have shared valuable insights into the industry's marketing advancements, which are crucial for

capitalizing on global demand. For instance, implementing tailored pricing strategies and organizing various educational and training programs for farmers have proven to be effective steps forward. Besides, the government's initiatives to upgrade trading ports, streamline transportation and storage, and conduct regular performance audits have shown promise in elevating industry standards.

Nevertheless, current research also produced a comprehensive action plan that emphasizes key recommendations from participants and current literature. This action plan is designed to empower future researchers and policymakers to identify critical areas for improvement and ensure the successful execution of necessary actions. The industry can experience meaningful progress and create lasting impact by utilizing these insights.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION

The chapter summarizes current research, including its findings, contributions, recommendations, and limitations. It begins by outlining the research objectives and summarizing the study's outcomes. Following this, the chapter discusses the current research's contributions, along with the recommendations and limitations that can guide future research efforts.

6.1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

The world is increasingly shifting towards eco-friendly practices in all areas of operation. The negative effects of synthetic products have prompted many to seek alternative, sustainable options that contribute to a greener planet. In this context, jute is emerging as a competitive and sustainable fiber with diverse applications, including geo-textiles, bio-plastics, and bio-composites (Choudhary, 2013; Shahinur *et al.*, 2022; Nayab-UI-Hossain *et al.*, 2023). Due to its environmentally friendly properties, jute is being considered a viable substitute for plastic. As the second most beneficial natural fiber after cotton, it is gaining attention from researchers as a potential replacement for synthetic fibers in the future (Nayab-UI-Hossain *et al.*, 2023; Syazwani *et al.*, 2022).

The rising demand for jute presents an unparalleled opportunity for Bangladesh, one of the leading jute-producing countries, to reclaim its position in the global jute market. Bangladesh can significantly bolster its economy by effectively meeting the growing international demand for sustainable materials. Moreover, the country possesses favorable environmental conditions for jute cultivation (Sheheli and Roy, 2014). Therefore, by implementing changes in production and processing strategies, Bangladesh's jute industry has the potential to strengthen itself and compete effectively with other exporting countries worldwide.

Existing literature mainly discusses the opportunities and challenges faced by Bangladesh's jute industry, but it provides limited insights into how the industry is currently adapting to global demand. Regular monitoring is essential to promote prosperity within any industrial sector, which helps identify areas needing improvement (Dziallas and Blind, 2019; Larsson, 2017). This gives a comprehensive understanding

of the current situation with which decisions can be made for the future. Hereby, current research aimed at understanding the progress of Bangladesh's jute industry to guide future improvements. The research set its objectives to assess different domains (production, processing, and marketing) of the industry that are associated with overall advancement.

6.2 RESEARCH SUMMARY AND OUTCOMES

Chapter 3 provides a detailed exploration of the research methodology aligned with the established research objectives and questions. The researcher emphasized the necessity of conducting an in-depth assessment of the jute industry to gather essential insights into its current conditions. Guided by a qualitative research philosophy, the researcher opted for a semi-structured interview technique to facilitate meaningful discussions with industry experts. A total of 16 participants were carefully selected from pertinent sectors within the jute industry to share their perspectives on the ongoing developments.

The analysis of the gathered data employed thematic analysis, highlighting significant findings regarding the advancements within Bangladesh's jute industry. The results indicate that the sector is evolving to meet global demand, showcasing notable improvements over previous practices. Furthermore, participants highlighted several key actions requiring immediate focus and attention. Below is a brief discussion of the research outcomes in relation to the research objectives.

The first research objective was to develop a conceptual framework detailed in Chapter 2. Analyzing the existing literature concerning the evolution of Bangladesh's jute industry was instrumental in shaping this conceptual framework. It delineates the core concepts that underpin the research.

Secondly, the research evaluated the advancements in agricultural strategies that the jute industry in Bangladesh is adopting to meet global demand. Participants discussed various aspects of the agricultural practices that are evolving and require further attention. It was noted that farmers are using different high-yielding varieties in their fields and adopting improved retting techniques to ensure the quality of raw jute. Additionally, participants highlighted the implementation of several sustainable practices in the field. One of the most noteworthy points raised by the respondents was the establishment of a seed centre. Existing literature indicates that Bangladesh's

jute industry faces significant challenges in distributing adequate seeds to farmers (Islam and Ali (2017)). Therefore, the development of the seed centre will ensure easier access to seeds for farmers.

The third objective of this research aimed to evaluate advancements in industrial processing within the context of the jute industry. The findings suggest that the industry is adopting a cost-leadership strategy, which is considered essential for navigating the challenges presented by the current crisis. By prioritizing low-cost production, firms are positioned to compete effectively in the global market (Akter, 2015). Participants in the study emphasized that this strategy is critical for the industry's survival, allowing operations to continue despite facing low-profit margins. Conversely, the research identified limited progress in terms of competitive advancement related to technological innovation. It was noted that the industry tends to rely on imported machinery rather than developing a competitive technological strategy internally. However, an important shift toward the adoption of sustainable practices was observed, with the industry making efforts to align with global standards. Participants also reported a notable improvement in the production of Jute Diversified Products (DJP), indicating that Bangladesh's jute industry now contributes more significantly to DJP than in previous years. Nonetheless, it is important to highlight that this enhancement primarily occurs on a small scale, signalling a need for further advancements to sustain growth and competitiveness in the future.

Current research focuses on evaluating advancements in the marketing strategies employed by the jute industry in Bangladesh. Marketing plays a pivotal role in any industry, providing essential insights into overall developmental progress. Participants in the study discussed various marketing strategies that have been previously documented in the existing literature. They emphasized the need for more frequent application of these strategies to achieve effective outcomes. Additionally, respondents highlighted price-related strategies that the Bangladeshi jute industry is implementing to remain competitive in the global market. Alongside a low-cost production approach, the industry is employing a low-pricing strategy to bolster its competitive stance.

The final objective of the research focuses on formulating an action model to recommend strategies for the industry's future growth. This action model is the product

of synthesizing recommendations derived from both current and existing studies. As previously mentioned, participants discussed the development of the seed centre. However, it was noted that this process is still ongoing. Further monitoring of the progress will help expedite its establishment. Participants also recommended that policymakers introduce improved varieties for commercial use. Additionally, they can work on the agricultural land expansion, as outlined in the existing literature, to increase yields. Different advanced retting approaches are also being suggested by the existing literature that need field implication to get the desired outcome. Participants also noted that farmers' actions towards sustainable cultivation require proper recognition to motivate them. This recognition will help increase the product level in the global market. In the context of industrial processing, participants suggested various actions, including implementing automated machinery, adopting competitive technology, certification for sustainable processing, developing proper infrastructure, a robust management system, and establishing research centres for DJP. On the other hand, existing literature highlights concepts like Total Productive Maintenance (TPM), Effluent Treatment Plants (ETP), innovative ideas, market research, and the role of promotional agencies in enhancing the current state of industrial processing. Additionally, both sources provided improved suggestions for marketing strategies. It was noted that the industry requires more focus on digital marketing, a Marketing Intelligence System (MIS), the Jute Bulletin, rural radio, and agriculture-based mobile services. Finally, current research has provided recommendations for governmental actions that the industry is eager to see implemented. It is highly suggested that the government take the initiative to strictly enforce rules and regulations while providing financial support to foster advancements in the industry. Notably, existing literature emphasizes the importance of establishing accessible loan services for farmers, enabling them to thrive. Furthermore, the issue of anti-dumping requires immediate and decisive action from the government to protect Bangladesh's jute markets. Participants have clarified that fostering a robust collaboration between government and non-governmental organisations is vital for advancing the industry. Additionally, the significance of advanced research and its ongoing application has been emphasized as critical for the industry's prosperity.

6.3 RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Contributions and recommendations of current research in theoretical, knowledge and practical aspects are discussed below.

6.3.1 Theoretical contribution and recommendation

Current research was underpinned by value chain and strategic management theory. The research assessed Bangladesh's jute industry value chain from production to marketing to understand strategic advancement in each section that aligns with the global demand. Existing literature indicates that strategic advancement is required in the Bangladesh jute industry to meet global production demand (Islam and Ali, 2018; Sharna and Kamruzzaman, 2020). Therefore, strategic management theory was used to guide the way of advancement assessment in the industry. It was noticed in the research that both theories have impacts on each other. The implementation of strategic management actions (cost leadership) eventually improves the product value by adding a competitive advantage at a low price. In addition, it was also observed that different strategic actions undertaken by the production, processing and marketing section of the industry eventually improve the overall performance of the value chain. On the other hand, assessing the value chain also assists in identifying places for improvement in strategic management. The relation between these two theories has been discussed in existing literature. Ketchen Jr, and Giunipero, (2004) studied the overlapping relation between these two theories based on the extended theoretical discussion. Compared to this, current research identified the relationship between the theories from the practical perspective by discussing their implementation in industrial advancement. So, current research contributed new understanding of the relation to the literature by demonstrating their overlapping association from the perspective of industrial implementation. In addition to this contribution, it was also identified by the researcher that current research has used the value chain theory to structure the research which is absent in existing literature from the perspective of Bangladesh jute industry.

6.3.2 Knowledge contributions and recommendations

Chapter 2 delivers a comprehensive examination of the existing literature related to the jute industry in Bangladesh, highlighting significant knowledge gaps. Notably, there is a scarcity of thorough research that addresses the current state of the jute sector, especially in light of the rising global demand for jute products. While a number of

studies have identified prospects and potential opportunities in the industry, there is a clear shortfall in the updated information regarding the industrial advancement to meet global demand. Prior research was found to focus on the preliminary phases of suggested initiatives. However, it is important to assess the current state of practice within the sector to make action plan for future. Additionally, participants in the current study have articulated concerns about the insufficient continuity of research in Bangladesh's jute industry. Therefore, to effectively guide the industry towards success, it is imperative to closely monitor its advancements in response to global demand and make informed decisions accordingly.

To bridge the information gap, current research conducted an in-depth knowledge assessment of the professionals related to the Bangladesh jute industry to understand their current advancement actions in meeting global demand. Based on the findings as discussed in chapters 4 and 5, the research succeeded in identifying considerable improvements in the industrial system that are being implemented to satisfy global needs. It was also noted that the industry is progressing in line with opportunities recommended in existing literature. However, this progress is steady and requires further efforts to accelerate. Therefore, current research findings contribute to the literature by highlighting various actions that the Bangladesh jute industry is implementing and can undertake in future improvements. Future researchers can use this knowledge to identify the missing actions and develop innovative ideas accordingly.

6.3.3 Practical implications and recommendations

The current research has made substantial contributions to the jute industry of Bangladesh, particularly by developing an action model tailored to the industry. As presented in Chapter 5.5 (Figure 13), the model synthesizes insights from participant input and existing literature, thereby elucidating the advancements necessary for the industry's future. This model serves as a critical tool for driving systemic improvements and ensuring the industry's sustainability moving forward. The findings discussed in chapters 4 and 5 outline essential actions across all segments of the industry—including production, processing, and marketing—indicating a comprehensive approach to improvement. Considering this, the model proposed actions as strategic advancements prioritizing these industrial segments. Some other actions were also proposed for government and future research.

Following the strategic advancements actions for agriculture, it can be found that the proposed actions like establishment of seed center, improved variety used at the commercial level, cultivable land extension, commercial use of advanced ribbon retting, knowledge and training facilities are beneficial for farmers. With such actions in place, farmers can advance their production and knowledge in sustainable jute farming. The action towards future research in jute hydroponic possibilities will enhance the opportunities for farmers to cultivate jute even in the scarcity of cultivable lands. Furthermore, the strategic advancement actions plan for industrial processing, for example, implementing automated and competitive machineries in the industry, implementation of ETP, TPM and MIS, facilitating the recognition of the industry as a sustainable producer of jute products, advancing the infrastructure for DJP, bringing an innovative idea to the industrial production, establishing composite jute mills and promotional agencies for jute industry will assist the industrial professional to bring advancement in their current processing approach. In addition, they will be able to improve the quality of production by implementing the proposed plan in place. The strategic action plans regarding marketing advancement will be a beneficial guideline for the jute marketers' exporters in Bangladesh to expand their marketing opportunities by establishing an open marketing platform, raw jute purchase center and digital marketing platform for jute in Bangladesh. Besides, they can use different forms of marketing tools that are absent in Bangladesh like jute bulletin, rural radio and agriculture-based mobile services to advertise the jute product within the local area. Considering existing literature and participants' comments, bringing improvements in packaging and labelling was also found as a crucial fact to focus for Bangladesh jute marketers.

Governmental assistance was indicated as one of the concerning points to focus on working out future action plans. As participants mentioned that rules and regulations need to be implemented rather than just being in pen and paper. Adequate financial support from the government has also been mentioned as one of the facts to further look into. Government is the center for the country's development. Therefore, the government of Bangladesh must come forward with a positive attitude and actions in advancing the jute industry. The assistance from the government will help professionals from all segments of the industry (farmers, industrial professionals and marketers) to advance their actions.

Finally, the action plans for research and education to establish further research institutions for jute, proper funding, collaboration and continuation of research will help the jute researcher to bring advancement in Bangladesh jute research. Consequently, it will improve the overall jute industry to progress with advanced research in their field.

To ensure effective implementation of the actions, a roadmap is developed here. Roadmap has been stated as a tool or strategic framework indicating activities to successfully implement action (Butt, 2020). The roadmap presented here is divided into five phases. Each phase has activities that will lead the action to the next phase and finally towards the successful implementation of the actions. Details of each phase are given in table 6. The perception of phases was adopted from Tiwari et al. (2023) and McLean et al. (2023).

6.3.3.1 Roadmap for action implementation

Tiwari et al. (2023) stated that the pre-implementation phase in a roadmap is occupied with different decisions that will eventually help to identify and establish the pre-implementation necessities for the pilot project. According to the action plan proposed in current research, the pre-implementation decisions can be regarding the source of funds and its arrangement process, location selection for infrastructure development, training and educational program arrangement in preparing the workforce, strategic procedure particularly for being sustainable producer, getting the implementation order in place and finally to getting required policymakers and stakeholders involved (table 6). Following the pre-implementation phase, conducting a pilot project is proposed by the roadmap. The pilot project will provide the opportunity to conduct planned actions on a small scale which will be evaluated in the next phase of the roadmap to assess its validity and feasibility. Based on the evaluation, the modified plan can be prepared for final implementation. This phase will assist in removing any drawbacks and challenges that the pilot project experiences. The final implementation then can take place with the improved plan. An additional phase has been added to the roadmap compared to Tiwari et al. (2023). It was identified from the research by McLean et al. (2023) that 'sustain' is one of the important phases in the action roadmap for manufacturing industries to ensure continuous improvement in the implementation. This can be conducted with regular monitoring and auditing, in addition to continuing required training and development activities.

Table 6: Description of the phases in the roadmap

Phases	Description
Identifying and establishing necessities of the action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making arrangements for the funds • Location selection for any infrastructure development • Arranging appropriate training and educational programs if necessary • Paper processing or identifying the process of recognising as a sustainable producer • Getting the order in place • Getting appropriate policy makers, stakeholders and third parties involved
Pilot project	Conducting the actions on a small scale to evaluate outcomes, feasibilities and viability of the action
Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modify plan based on the feedback • Removing any intermediates or challenges that identified • Dispute resolution • On-boarding and off-boarding strategies • Identifying further needs for training • Evaluate outcomes against the demand
Final implementation	Conducting the action in a complete scale after evaluation
Sustain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keep it going forever • Regular auditing • continuing required development and training

Following the phases, the roadmap for proposed actions is presented in figure 10. An indicative timeframe has also been mentioned in the roadmap for each phase. This is just a projected timeline by the researcher that might take to complete the actions. Actions for strategic advancement in the industry will go through all of the mentioned phases. However, the actions for governmental assistance and research education will directly go for final implementation without any pilot project. The actions for governmental assistance mainly need obtaining implementation orders from the government along with the participation of other stakeholders. On the other hand, actions for research and education can also go directly for the final implementation to

keep regular monitoring of the advancement in the sustain phase. The strategic advancement actions including the seed center establishment, commercial use of the improved variety, implementing strategic actions in industry, jute bulletin, open marketing platform and all of the other actions will benefit from a pilot project to evaluate its validity and feasibility. The sustain phase will be the long-term plan for each action to keep them continuing and advancing the industry.

Figure 10: Roadmap for action implementation

6.4 LIMITATIONS OF CURRENT RESEARCH AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Identifying limitations is a crucial aspect of any research, as it helps assess the reliability and validity of the findings (Ross and Bibler Zaidi, 2019). Reflecting on these limitations allows researchers to explore alternative approaches that can be adopted in future studies to minimise constraints and achieve more accurate outcomes. The results of the current study are constrained by several factors that should be considered before applying the findings in a practical context.

6.4.1 Research approach

Current research was conducted using a qualitative research approach. While qualitative research holds similar importance to quantitative research, it has often

faced criticism regarding its validity and reliability (Leung, 2015). A mixed research approach could have provided the researcher with broader aspects to analyze the facts. It also has a higher validity level when comparing findings between the approaches. For example, the research could have been performed along with a survey or real case study to obtain more information and validate the research outcome. A combination of both qualitative and quantitative research is a great way to assure the validity of a research outcome where the qualitative part of the research provides in-depth information about the research phenomenon (thematic network), and the quantitative part of the research provides an opportunity to test the finding (Imran and Yusoff, 2015). With such a mix of research approaches, limitations in one research approach can be optimized by applying another. Future researchers can continue the research using different research methods to evaluate outcome variations.

On the other hand, current research has employed data triangulation and an intra-coding approach to ensure the validity and reliability of the data. However, existing literature suggests further methods that could enhance research findings' credibility, validity, and reliability (Sutton and Austin, 2015). For instance, the study could have utilized additional triangulation approaches like method triangulation, theory triangulation, and investigator triangulation, to strengthen the validity of the collected data further (Jonsen and Jehn, 2009).

6.4.2 Absence of questionnaire pilot test

The current study lacked any pilot test to assess the effectiveness of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was prepared and used immediately in the final interview session without evaluating its effectiveness in gathering the necessary information. A pilot test is crucial for any research to assess its data collection instrument and to make necessary adjustments before the final implementation. It enhances both the efficacy and feasibility of the data collection protocol (Hassan, Schattner, and Mazza, 2006). A pilot test can provide researchers with insights regarding the strengths of the questionnaire or data collection tool they intend to use. The pilot test results can also inform participant recruitment strategies, which can improve the overall data collection process (Cope, 2015). Therefore, it is evident that the current research lacked prior knowledge about the strengths of the questionnaire. Conducting a pilot test would have made the results more reliable and valid.

6.4.3 Manual processing of the data

The research primarily involved analyzing and processing data manually rather than utilizing software or online tools. However, several software programs and websites can assist in the analysis of qualitative data. One of the most widely used software options for qualitative data analysis is Nvivo (Zamawe, 2015). Computer-assisted data processing provides outcomes that are noted for their accuracy and transparency. Additionally, this approach is time-efficient, allowing researchers to code large datasets relatively quickly (Welsh, 2002). Data processed using software is often considered more rigorous than manual processing. Therefore, it can be concluded that the current research findings may be limited in accuracy and rigour due to their reliance solely on manual data processing. Future research could address this limitation by employing Nvivo for coding and thematic analysis of the dataset.

6.4.4 Interview language

The language used in interviews has been identified in recent research as an important factor affecting data validity. In this case, the interview was conducted in Bengali and subsequently translated and transcribed into English. This process can impact the accuracy of the data. For instance, certain expressions used by participants in Bengali may have been missed or overlooked during translation into English (Alshenqeeti, 2014). Additionally, different languages have distinct oral expressions and writing structures, which can influence the content in the transcript during the translation process. Therefore, it is difficult to guarantee that the transcript accurately represents the participants' verbal speech.

6.4.5 Number of participants

Current research interviewed a total of 16 professionals from the Bangladesh jute industry. While a solid justification for the choice of this participant number has been provided earlier, it is generally advisable to include more participants to validate the findings and gather more comprehensive insights. Therefore, future studies may consider including additional participants from different levels of work associated with the Bangladesh jute industry to get a more comprehensive and comparable picture of the phenomenon.

6.5 CHAPTER SUMMARY

This chapter serves as a comprehensive summary of the research, addressing its background, objectives, findings, contributions, limitations, and recommendations. It

underscores the study's significant theoretical and practical implications, establishing a valuable framework for future research endeavours. By elucidating how this work contributes to the advancement of knowledge, the chapter also provides actionable insights that can be applied within the industry, making it a vital resource for both scholars and practitioners. Moreover, the chapter thoughtfully outlines various limitations encountered during the current research. This analysis will assist future researchers in planning their studies more effectively, allowing them to anticipate and mitigate similar constraints. Overall, the chapter reinforces the importance of this research while paving the way for subsequent investigations.

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APPENDIX I

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Researcher name: MD TOUHIDUL ISLAM

Institution and position: DBA student at University of West of Scotland

Research title: ANALYSING CURRENT STATUS OF BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY: ASSESSING ADVANCEMENT FROM FIELD TO EXPORT

Research purpose: The research is aimed at analyzing current advancements in the jute industry of Bangladesh. Bangladesh is well known in jute production from long time. It is also among the top jute exporting countries. However, several factors have been affecting the jute market of Bangladesh that can be a great concern for this country. With the implementation of appropriate actions, Bangladesh can again reach its top global market position in jute that will help the economy of this country. Recent case studies indicated that some of the Bangladesh jute industries are applying required actions. Hereby, the study will explore current situation of Bangladesh jute industry to evaluate its progression towards improving position in global jute market. The study will help to identify any lacking and to suggest future actions that can be adopted to standardize Bangladesh Jute market.

Participation in the interview: Your participation in the interview is voluntary activity. You can withdraw or stop responding at any time you wish, or you can deny participating at all. If you want, you can skip any question as well. If you want to participate, then you have to provide your consent by signing in the consent form attached with this information sheet before stating the interview. I would like to request you to read the consent form thoroughly before signing it. It will be helpful if you can confirm your participation and availability within next 2 weeks by emailing or calling me (email and phone number has given below) so that I can book the schedule for you. The interview will take approximately 1hr.

Signing in the consent form indicate that you willingly allowed me to process your information for the research purpose. Full confidentiality will be maintained in the research to process information obtained from the interviewee.

Your contribution in the research: As per the research question and objectives, you will be asked to answer some questions related to current jute production and jute

market of Bangladesh. You will be expected to answer the question from your experience and knowledge. As a professional in related field, your answers will be valuable to interpret current scenario of Bangladesh jute market.

Possible personal risk factors associated with the participation: The research questions are designed very carefully that will not cause any personal or professional risk to anyone. Hereby, you can be assured that participating in the interview will not cause any risk to you. Besides, the research will maintain necessary action (data protection regulation) to avoid any misuse of the information provided by you. Full confidentiality will be maintained for the data. On the other hand, you are allowed to leave or withdraw the interview at any time you wish.

Information processing: As mentioned earlier, the information will be processed with standard data protection regulation and maintaining information confidentiality. The information obtained from interviewee will only keep for shorter period. As soon as the purpose of interview data is accomplished, it will be demolished shortly. No one except the interviewer or research will have access to the data till then. So, you can be assured of safety or confidentiality of the data.

Many thanks for your time to read this instruction. May you have any question, please contact directly with me (the researcher: MD TOUHIDUL ISLAM) in the email address provided here. I will be more than happy to answer any queries you have regarding the participation and my research. If you are participating in the research and willing to know its result, then you may have to wait till it is completed. Once the research is finished, I can provide you the full research upon request.

I would like to show my gratitude again for your time and interest in my research. Hopefully will have further conversation with you in the interview.

Researcher

MD TOUHIDUL ISLAM
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235 Southwark Bridge Road
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Chief Investigator details:

Chief Investigator: Dr David Burl
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CONSENT FORM

Name of department: School of Business and Creative Studies, University of West of Scotland

Title of the study: Analysing current status of Bangladesh jute industry: assessing performance from field to export

- I confirm that I have read and understood the research purpose and my participation in the research.
- I confirm that the participation information sheet was satisfactory to understand the research and researcher also helped to understand it by providing information for any other queries that I had.
- I acknowledge that I understand the privacy policy that the research will follow for participants (information processing, information storing policy etc.)
- I understand that the research will maintain information confidentiality and my personal details as participant will not be exposed publicly.
- I understand that it is a voluntary participation. I am allowed to stop or withdraw at any time of my participation with or without providing any reason.
- I understand that I am allowed to erase (from the transcript or recording) any personal related information that I have provided to the researcher at any time I intend. However, I am not allowed to withdraw information that does not recognised or indicate me (anonymised information-information related to research topic), that has already been included in the research.
- Hereby, I give my consent to consider me as a participant of the study and I give consent to record my information for the study purpose.

(NAME)	
Signature of Participant:	Date:

INTERVIEW INSTRUCTION

Good morning/ afternoon, I am Touhidul Islam, Doctorate student at University of West of Scotland, welcoming you to this interview. This is a part of my DBA research, and I am very grateful to you as you agreed to provide information as per the questionnaire

that will help me in my research. As you know, this is a data collection process of my research. So, I will be thankful if you can provide answers to the questions as per your knowledge and expertise and remain truthful throughout the interview. In the questionnaire, there are two sections. Section one will ask you question about your background like profession, working institute, work position, your age, gender etc. Questions in other section will be related to the research topic. Overall, it will take approximately 1hr to finish all the questions. So, I would like to request you to keep patience and follow me (the questionnaire) the till end if it is possible for you or if you want to. As you know, we can withdraw or stop the interview at any time you wish as it is a voluntary participation. Just let me know if you are uncomfortable with any question.

A recording of the conversation will be conducted in this interview. It will help in efficient data analysis and will reduce the chance of losing any information. However, the recording information will be dealt with standard data protection act and confidentiality. There will be no misuse of the data.

QUESTIONNAIRE

- **PART A-DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONS**

Name:

Age:

Profession:

Institution:

Job position:

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

.....
.....

Some of the responsibility in your job position:

.....
.....

- **PART B- QUESTIONS RELATED TO RESEARCH PURPOSE**

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry? (Ferdous and Ikeda, 2018; Onyango, 2021)
2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past? (Swazan and Das, 2022)

Production strategy

3. What strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute sector is adopting in terms of increasing their production (both field strategy to produce raw jute and industrial strategy to process) and meeting global jute demand? (Ferdous and Ikeda, 2018)
4. What do you think about Bangladesh jute industry in global jute market with such strategies in next 10 years? (any recommendation)
5. What are the steps being taken by jute cultivators to produce more jute against climatic barriers? (Improve seed/ genetically modified cultivars/ cultivation strategy etc.)?
6. How jute cultivation in Bangladesh is planning to increase with extending cultivation area?
7. What is your thinking about hydroponic and vertical farming in terms of jute cultivation to increase the production?

Diversified jute product

8. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with **diversified jute product**? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their production/sale of diversified jute product?
9. What is your suggestion about diversified jute products that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?

Current technology use

10. What upgraded processing techniques are Bangladesh jute industry following to increase quality production?

11. What is the technological situation of Bangladesh Jute industry in marketing sector? How are they planning to improve?
12. What is the technological improvement in jute cultivation and field processing?
13. What is your opinion about technologies that is being used in Bangladesh Jute industry? Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries? (Van Der Walt, 2020)
14. How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?
15. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute sector can adopt to improve their current position?
16. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?
17. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

Pricing

18. How you establish both internal (local) and external (export) pricing? What facts do you consider in establishing pricing?
19. What do you think of competitive pricing and how jute industries in Bangladesh are working in this?
20. What is the pricing strategy to increase export profitability in jute sector? (De Toni *et al.*, 2017)
21. What is the local pricing strategy to keep market flow inside the country?
22. What is your suggestion about improvements in existing pricing strategy that will increase profit?

Marketing strategy

23. What marketing/sale strategies are currently implementing in Bangladesh jute industry to stand in competitive global market?
24. How you advertise or promote jute products to the buyer countries?
25. What is your strategy towards attracting customer towards new diversified jute product? (Tomasin *et al.*, 2013)
26. How do you think Bangladesh jute industry can improve their marketing system?

Trading barriers

27. What is your thought about different trading barriers that Bangladesh jute industry is experiencing?
28. How is Bangladesh jute industry tackling with such barriers?
29. What policies Bangladesh jute industry applies when experiencing any logistic port problem?

Involvement of government

30. How Bangladesh Government helps with its rules and regulation to overcome logistic challenges experienced by Bangladesh jute industry?
31. Is there any other support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute industry? What are they?

Sustainable performance

32. How is Bangladesh jute industry working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

33. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable? (Caiado *et al.*, 2019; Winter and Lasch, 2016)

34. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?

INTERVIEW TRANSCRIPTS

PARTICIPANT: INDUSTRIAL PROCESSING EXPERT 1

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: Above 50/ Male

Profession: Industrial processing expert

Institution: N/A

Job position: General manager

How long are you working in this job field? / your experience level in this job field:

≥20

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: If we consider the birth of jute, the quality of jute then I can say that Bangladesh is in top place. Bangladesh achieved the highest rank in the world for Jute by its quality. Jute mainly produce in Bangladesh, India and China. No other countries like India or China has good quality jute as Bangladesh. The reason behind of its best quality is soil, weather and Environment. Soil, rain, sunlight is the main component for producing good quality jute. Faridpur, Mymensing district has the best suitable component for Jute cultivation. In exporting jute and Jute made product Bangladesh has achieved great success than India because of its quality and large volume of production. In Export, there is also Bangladesh achieved the first place for jute. In world jute means Bangladeshi jute. There is also India but India can not beat Bangladesh.

Mills under BGMC is mostly being closed but some private mills in Bangladesh are working well and exporting jute products. We have market *all* over the world to export out jute product.

We have some diversified product. This is not like that we do not make diversified product. We make it but not as many as other country do. We also export these diversified product. We are exporting jute bag, yarn, fabric to Netherland and many other country. UK, Iran, Japan, Australia and many other countries are importing yarn from us.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

We are exporting different jute product all over the world, the volume of exporting is increasing. We are exporting yarn for carpet, different types of jute bags etc.

Production strategy

3. What strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute industries are adopting in terms of increasing their production and meeting global jute demand?

Answer: Production and other costing is very high in jute sector. This is a problem for Bangladesh. Bangladesh Govt. Trying minimize the costing so that we can produce more in the same cost and export. Because buyer from various sector always want to buy in minimum cost, if our production cost remain high we lose buyer. So with lowering the production cost we can also attract buyer with reduced price and more production. That's why Bangladesh Jute industry adopting these strategies. Though we less research work, but different institute are trying to do research how to produce more jute in low cost. If we attract the world towards us then it can be more profitable to export jute and jute diversified product

4. How do you think about Bangladesh jute industry in global jute market with such strategies in next 10 years? (any recommendation) future of such strategy

Answer: By increasing use of jute product and reducing production cost Bangladesh can do far better in global jute market. By producing diversified jute product we can attract more buyer. Using more jute product will increase the demand in global market. So focusing on it will be better.

Diversified jute product

5. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with diversified jute product? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their production of diversified jute product? progression

Answer: I don't have any exact idea but I can say Bangladesh not only exporting raw jute but also exporting diversified jute product like yarn to Iran, Netherland, Australia and so many countries. Different Govt and private organizations are taking action towards improving diversified jute product. However, I think that comparing to India, Bangladesh is lagging behind in diversified product production. India is ahead of us by technologically. This is

obviously because of low technological knowledge among people and there is not much research work about it. Bangladesh jute development board doesn't have so many activities on this issue. If Government and other institute put their concentration on it then development can be possible. We have to focus on not only jute diversified product also. We have to take steps to produce more diversified product. There are many alternative of jute product are increasing day by day and these are low in cost. This is a problem for us.

6. What is your suggestion about diversified jute products that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?

Answer: To increase the diversity in jute product. Government and other organization should pay attention towards improving technical and technological skill, skilled worker (training, knowledge) to produce diverse jute product. There are several substitutes low-cost products of jute is being invented. So, it is also a challenge for jute market. We need to lower the cost of jute product to compete with that substitute market

Current technology use

7. What upgraded processing techniques are they following to increase quality product production?

Answer: Processing techniques are same as before. I think some actions are taking to upgrade this that will help us to improve product quality and production. However, most of the industrial personnel and even government is reluctant to upgrading the processing system and bring upgraded technology. It is I think lack of awareness.

8. What is your opinion about technologies that is being used in Bangladesh Jute industry? Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries?

Answer: Bangladesh used to import machine from UK, dandee. However, recently we are importing machine from China and India but I don't think Bangladesh has any of its own effort to improve the technology or processing. They mostly follow and dependent on the machine imported from other country. So, whatever improved machinery they have, we are using the same technology. But we do not have our own machine manufacture. Jute born in Bangladesh, we were supposed to take strong position in jute but we could not. Because we do not have sufficient machineries.

9. How are these improvements helping Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: Since it is the same technology, we all are using, we are not competing here with other exporting country. However, other country has their own manufacture facilities, so they might have improved techniques comparing to us. However, in my opinion Bangladesh is top one exporting country. As India need to satisfy its own jute demand and then export. But Bangladesh with its huge jute production can export more and even India import from us.

10. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute industry can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: We need to improve quality to attract more buyer. Hereby, public and private sector should come forward to make technological improvement in Bangladesh jute sector. They should make plan-policies and implement it, actually they should take necessary steps as soon as possible.

Not only in industrial technology, we also need to improve field technology (retting processing) to lower the overall cost and to attract more buyer. We have huge buyer, but with only reducing the production and processing cost, we can sell the products as many as we produce.

11. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Answer: Bangladesh fully depend on natural process for jute plant to become raw jute. Jute sector should use modern technologies to make this sector more profitable. But alas, Govt. and private both sector do not taking this issue seriously. There are many plan and policies but no implementation. Govt. and private both sector are using and importing alternative product of jute from different countries because we do not have upgrade machineries or technology to make jute product. If we can make huge production then we can attract more buyer.

12. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

As I said earlier, with the involvement from government and public bodies, we can improve out technological situation in jute industry. We just need to grow our awareness and look around to have idea about technological upgrade in other countries. With such action, I think Bangladesh can behold competitive position in global jute market with its upgrade in technology implementation.

Involvement of government

13. Is there any support from government in improving current processing of jute in Bangladesh? What are they?

Answer: Currently there is no support from government to improve current processing of jute in Bangladesh. It seems like government has no interest in the area. Although government show some interest in different new feeds, but in reality, no action is here. Government tried to motivate people towards using jute shopping bag instead of polythene, however, there was no consistency in the policy or in its implementation. Mostly we have problem in the implementation of our laws. We have them but no apply. We people are also responsible here as we do not care about our environment and policies provided by the government. So, it is both the government's and our duty to follow the legislation what we have here to save our surrounding.

But Bangladesh govt. should develop quality of jute and focus on costing with high priority. Research is being performed but no implementation.

Sustainable performance

14. How is Bangladesh jute industry working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: Plastic is very harmful to our environment. I can say that we got a plus point to having jute to make our environment more sustainable. But other materials are cheaper than jute that's why people are not using jute. They are now mixing those plastic fiber with yarn in carpet making. So requirement of jute decreasing. If we increase the price of other materials and decrease the costing price of jute. I think then people will jute as a sustainable product and demand of jute will increase. Then people will interest on jute. We have to keep practice of using jute made product and avoid plastic materials to keep our environment sustainable.

15. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: there are no govt policies or rules yet now to become sustainable. I think, Govt. have to make rules and regulation and to ensure that everyone is following it to become sustainable. Govt. Can make many policies to avoid plastic and replace it with jute. We are conducting several conference and meeting to aware people about sustainability and jute use, however, this are not being implemented in practical life. We are doing seminar that we will not use plastic product or synthetic product, but in reality we are not doing such thing. This is the problem.

16. What is your suggestion in this term to improve performance in future?

Answer: Many research and seminar should be held to aware people about diversified jute product. Govt. and private sector has to come forward. Educational institute can increase interest of students to do research on this subject. In this way we can hold the first position of jute sector in the world.

PARTICIPANT: INDUSTRIAL PROCESSING EXPERT 2

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: Above 50/ Male

Profession: INDUSTRIAL PROCESSING EXPERT

Institution: N/A

Job position: General Manager

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

≥20

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: Not in recent, the jute market is not stable in the last 10 years. I can say, what time we are passing, we are passing a very hard time in the jute industry. The reason can be the covid. Though it was good in 2021-22 session but in 2022 it become horrible, especially in the yarn market (major market) (carpet). But on the other hand, the packaging market is in good condition. There are two types of bag, one is hessian and other is sacking . This packaging market was not good in few months ago. But now this is in good condition. This is happening because of globalization. Hessian market is a very small market in Europe. But the major market for us is yarn market. On the basis of my experience, I can say that the yarn market is the largest market and after 2008 Bangladesh could not perform the best here. On the basis of my 30 years' experience in this sector I can say that jute will remain forever as well as the ups and down. Once there was a huge market in UK for jute and we exported a big amount of jute (carpet yarn) there. But now demand are not as same as previous.

Jute production is increased in farmer level, in field. In 2020-21 year and after that jute market was very high and farmer was very happy. Quality deteriorated but production increased. This year quality has very much deteriorated. Quality deteriorated due to lack of rain water and in lack of retting. This year rain was not sufficient.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: Current situation is not good comparing the past because of the covid, Ukrain-Russia war and other reason. Situation is against of jute market. On the basis of my experience I can say that this situation will continue to next two or three years. The jute market was never stable and will not be in the future. Ups and down is a regular scene. Market are sourcing alternative of jute because last year price of jute was highest in the history.

Situation is not stable because-Except packaging the major use of jute is in carpeting. However, carpeting is not something necessity. It is decorative product. As we are experiencing ups and downs in our economy, so the demand for decorative product is. During 2020-2021, the price of jute yarn get excessively high which leads our customer to go for other substitute product (cotton). Carpet industry used substitute yarn rather than using jute yarn.

Jute demand is only increasing in terms of packaging. Packaging demand is 25% and other demand like yarn is 75%. There was 39 govt. jute mill in Bangladesh. But now almost are closed and stopped their activities.

Production strategy

3. What strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute industries are adopting in terms of increasing their production and meeting global jute demand?

Answer:

70% jute industry export raw yarn. We are exporting raw jute to India, China and Pakistan. They are using this jute for inhouse usage. They are using it as diversified product. Our government has ordered to use jute packaging in every sector but how many of us are obeying this. Very few of us are using jute as packaging in inhouse.

Production of the jute is increasing from 2021 again. But last year the quality was not satisfactory because of the less rainfall. Except for the govt. one, there is no research centre for jute in the private sector. But in India, we can see that they are doing a lot of research on it. We need to do a lot of research work for the jute industry. Govt. are taking lots of strategies to increase the production.

4. How do you think about Bangladesh jute industry in global jute market with such strategies in next 10 years? (any recommendation)

Answer: Most of the government jute mill has been closed these days because of their loss year after year. In this crisis time of Bangladesh Jute industry, some private sector or owner has come forward to involve in this business. The private sector of Bangladesh jute industry is contributing huge to increase the production and to hold the position of Bangladesh jute industry in global market. They have increase the diversification of jute product, but not rapidly, slowly. The yarn market condition was horrible in last one year. However, it will take time to take the country to the top position in the world. We need to focus on diversified product to improve the situation in next 10 year. Our jute industry mainly grow for the carpet market in Turkey, UK and others countries. We have to concentrate fully in diversified product. Walmart taking raw jute material from us and using them for diversified product and doing good business. We also think of these type business and market place.

Diversified jute product

5. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with diversified jute product? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their production of diversified jute product?

We don't have proper infrastructure or management system that will initiate towards producing diversified jute product. Tried to encourage the use of jute bags in different aspect (shopping, food storage etc.). However, we are still relying on polythene. Nevertheless, we have some

diversified jute products, and it is improving but not rapidly, its slow improvement. Private sector has done lots of work in this sector, but govt. has not a visible contribution. There is a jute mill which running for 54 years. They are still can continue because they had focused on the diversified product. But other jute mill has lot their existence because they only had focused on one item. Either its carpet yarn or its jute bag. That's why I am saying that every sector should focus on this. Recently we are making fabric from jute and then we are using it in many aspects.

Recently we are dyeing jute to make diverse product. Some industries are dyeing jute to beautify its product. They are trying to get the market with something different with jute. Some industry is also dyeing blended jute products to satisfy customer demand. We don't have proper research centre or facilities that will work on improving diversified jute product or to improve our jute industry. India has many research centre. I think we should develop our research system. We have opportunity in this sector. We produce jute in our own country, we have low labour cost and other facilities are very good in our country. So we should research more and more for jute. From last few years we are trying to improve our retting approach as we are not having enough rain to retting the jute. We are working with different Universities to solve this problem through. However, government has no involvement here. I think, government should take more responsibilities and action towards improving our research and jute development.

6. What is your suggestion about diversified jute products that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?

Answer: We cannot mix this jute with cotton to make cloth, it will be very expensive. We can only use jute in packaging and showpiece as a diversified product. Blending jute with other product (cotton) to make fabric is not a feasible idea. It will be expensive and I don't think will be accepted in Bangladesh market. I don't know elaborately about this issue. May be they are doing something to blend jute with cotton for other countries.

We need to be more diversified in jute product. We need to come out from making only yarn. Different small entrepreneurs are making diversified jute product but it need to be more. We should not only focus on making one product...but diverse product

Current technology use

7. What upgraded processing techniques are they following to increase quality product production?

Answer: We used old model machineries in previous time. But now we are using new model machineries, which is improved version and are also being used by China. New machines are almost same as old ones but this machine has increased the production and quality product. Old model was not as good in production. With the old machine knitting company produced 5-6 ton product but with new one we can now produce 8-9 ton product. We are now developing inverter machineries. Before as past we are bringing machineries from abroad, (China), we do not have our own machine.

We mainly export machineries from China. So, we mostly depend on them for the machineries. I think whatever machineries they have; we are also using that. We are trying to develop our machineries to improve our productivity. Comparing to past the world is going being more

advanced and moving towards technology rather than manual or conventional work, so as we. We are also trying our best to bring technologies or machinery whatever you say. But as a developing country and considering our financial support, you know it is bit hard to become like the modern countries. Still I will say, we are not behind, from our position, we are doing whatever we can to overcome the challenges.

8. What is your opinion about technologies that is being used in Bangladesh Jute industry? Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries?

Answer: Comparing to past, we are using upgraded machine. We are trying to develop our technical side, but China is using the best quality machineries. There is also lots of talk about automated machine upgrade which can be a new ear to explore

9. How are these improvements helping Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: We are doing well in using technology but I heard from different source that India is doing better than us. They are starting to use robot and automation in this whole system. But we don't think like this. I think we are not lagging behind than India.

10. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute industry can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: In terms of skilled worker, we also need more skilled person or researcher to work with us. In my opinion, students in Bangladesh are not that interested in jute industry. They want to work in other sector rather than jute. Recently we are trying to engaging textile students in this sector. It is disappointing. Jute sector, as its current condition in Bangladesh (closing down of many factories), messy workshop, financial drop etc. After completing graduation, a textile student expectation do not match with the reality of jute industry. people are not interested to work here. So, we need to encourage them to come and contribute their talent here in our jute industry.

We need to increase our quality product in reduced cost. This is the only way to develop jute sector. We need to improve machineries and encourage skilled worker to work for us.

11. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Answer: lack of manpower, skilled manpower. Last 10-15 years, very less skilled person has been involved with jute sector.

We have to develop our product quality. For this we have to upgrade our machineries. We have to reduce cost. We are using inverter-controlled machine but I think need more upgrade. Our machines are very old model. We need to upgrade our machine. To overcome these challenge we have to involve educated people in this industry.

12. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

Answer: Other research saying that jute sector will do lot of development in next 5 year. But with my experience I can say that it will not happen. Because demand is decreasing day by day. I have visited many time in Japan. I have discussed with them. They said 20 years ago

there was demand for jute is 1 lakh ton. Now it becomes 14 to 15 thousand ton. Jute only used in packaging and carpet and very few showpieces. I don't think that with these three products there is any possibilities to experience increased demand of jute in future. Now people are thinking about the product cost that how it can be reduced. We have surveyed in retail market. Here I have seen that a very little portion of jute is being using there. A plastic bag price and a jute bag price has a huge difference. Jute can be used as plastic substitute but expense in the most important think in market. Comparing to polyethene, the cost of jute is excess. So, people will ultimately prefer plastic (low-cost product), not jute (expensive). Many jute mill has been closed permanently just for the rising of cotton price. India also has the same scenario. We export jute yarn in two grade. Low grade and medium grade. They use low grade jute to make sacking bag or rope and in carpet making they use the medium grade yarn.

Research may say that demand will increase but in practical I don't see it. Most of the jute factories are closing day by day due to the less demand of jute as it is very expensive to consumer.

Involvement of government

13. Is there any support from government in improving current processing of jute in Bangladesh? What are they?

Answer: Govt. are taking lot of step to improve current position. They are making plan and policies to protect the jute sector but in reality, implementation are not happening. The subsidy from government is also very less. I don't think our government is thinking about jute sector as they closed down so many jute industries at once. It seems like government has no interest in the area It is not good for our jute market.

Government should increase its subsidy and support diversified jute product production. India has policy to buy jute product from industries to increase market. But we do not have such policies here implemented from government to increase our production.

Sustainable performance

14. How is Bangladesh jute industry working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: yes, we are following sustainable production. The packaging we produce from jute is sustainable product. We are using dust collector system to reduce dust that comes from jute processing. We have treatment plant for waste management

15. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: Govt. has made lot of rules and policies but most of the factories are not maintaining it. To become sustainable, we should follow the policies.

16. What is your suggestion in this term to improve performance in future?

Answer: To improve performance in future we need effective manpower. More and more training and research need in this sector. Government should increase its subsidy and support DJP production. To improve performance in future we need effective manpower. More and more training and research need in this sector

Marketing

For marketing, we have different worldwide fair to attract customer and buyer. A big fair held in Germany every year. We participate there to promote our product. There is also a big fair held in China. We have also a big fair in our country called international trade fair. We also promote our jute in there. Every year we have such fair where different jute industrialist from Bangladesh, we exhibit our product. Within Bangladesh, we also attend different jute fair and campaigning to promote our product.

PARTICIPANT: INDUSTRIAL PROCESSING EXPERT 3

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: Above 50/ Male

Profession: INDUSTRIAL PROCESSING EXPERT

Institution: N/A

Job position: General manager

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

≥20

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: According to current scenario, Bangladesh is the Second largest producer for jute. I think India is first and China is in the third position. Probably Jute is now the most important and natural fiber because of being biodegradable and compostable. As eco friendly and natural product the potential of jute and jute goods are increasing day by day. This is very important if we can emphasis on this side or in these industries. However, if we consider recent

development in the industry, it can be said that the improvement is better comparing to the improvements happening in other countries. Bangladesh has come a long way from its initial position after the fall off to reach current position. Within this short period, Bangladesh has improved its jute product varieties, qualities and production as well to meet global demand.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: If we compare the improvement with past, then it is not improved as we expected. We expected more development which did not take place because of many reasons. It should have improved much more but the lack of using technologies and lack of awareness and skill manpower. I think we are much behind that we should progress. Yes we are improving a little bit with the globalization.

Production strategy

3. What strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute industries are adopting in terms of increasing their production and meeting global jute demand?

Answer: Actually restructuring all the sectors are long overdue as like exceeded previously. The government are apparently committed to move with new plant or the process will have to prove that the success of the plan together with the private sector. It is very good work that government has taken the plans to start the official to make growth in textile and also jute ministry to go all out to promote the growth of jute and jute product. Somehow Bangladesh's mission is also in accord about to give the necessary advice to promotion of jute and jute products. So I can say that the strategic level of government is strategic but there is no educated people in this sector so I think they should take initiative step about this.

Many private industry is getting involved in making jute product. This is good sign for Bangladesh as the government mills are closing down recently.

4. How do you think about Bangladesh jute industry in global jute market with such strategies in next 10 years? (any recommendation)

Answer: In my opinion Bangladesh should emphasize on this side as well as Bangladesh has put good attention in textile and RMG sector. Bangladesh also emphasized on jute side and take vision for the next 10 years. Because once jute was the golden fiber of Bangladesh and still it continues. We should emphasize on it by growing the technology, educating the new innovations, encouraging, balancing organizing, expanding and rehabilitant. Bangladesh should totally increase their attention to this because this is biodegradable and sustainable. Now sustainable economy is very much important to all of us. If we can make this system sustainable there will be no pollution also. Bangladesh can invest here and to complete the globalization they have done already. He can follow the new technologies to develop.

The contribution of private sector can help huge to increase production and supply

Diversified jute product

5. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with diversified jute product? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their production of diversified jute product?

Answer: I can say that diversification is very much important for this industry. Any product from jute like jute ornament, jute carpet can be used globally. We have to aware people also about this. They need to grow their attention to this. It can be done in large impact if we use the technologies. To improve this sector there should be product development, process development and lot of research. There is not so much improvement in jute diversification. Government's plan is good initiative but implementation is slow and not sufficient because of lack of technology, skilled man power and regular research. There is a jute diversification promotion centre established in 2002 and they are started their work already. This is a good progress actually.

6. What is your suggestion about diversified jute products that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?

Answer: The challenges of jute diversification sector are lack of technology, skilled man power and regular research. From my side I can say that the challenges need to overcome or at least start to target some progress that we can do in near future. Entrepreneurs of the jute sector can take financial support from the bank. Government can provide some subsidiary to this sector.

Current technology use

7. What upgraded processing techniques are they following to increase quality product production?

Answer: I can see least amount investment in this sector and technologies are not like as our neighbour country. This sector needs to be updated, need to adapt new technologies. This sector also needs investment from the government. Comparing to past it is improved, but comparing to current global situation, it should be more updated. Our current world has gone so far with technology, but we are still far behind.

8. What is your opinion about technologies that is being used in Bangladesh Jute industry? Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries?

Answer: This actually needs to be updated. It is totally not updated. We can only see a little bit update but with the globalization the progress is not satisfied.

9. How are these improvements helping Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: Firstly we need skilled man power. We can open relatable courses in institute. We train people for the product diversification development and manufacturing program. Quality product need to be updated.

10. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute industry can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: Like I said we need skill man power, updated technologies. Latest machine, latest technology, latest processing can be improved. We need to adapt upgrade machinery. We need to train our people to run them. We need to ensure financial support. There should be some research in product diversification and manufacturing process to upgrade the volume of the product and quality of the product. I cannot name the specific technology but I can say that latest technology is needed.

11. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Answer: We need to encourage our farmers. We need to look after our farmers. Farmers need to be awarded, farmers need to be financed. We can arrange some seminar to encourage them. There should be some community to develop these things. Because already some govt. jute mill has been closed.

12. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

Answer: Technologies that is coming we should adapt this and train our man power. We should use machinery in maximum value. In this way we would get the most production and least wasted.

Involvement of government

13. Is there any support from government in improving current processing of jute in Bangladesh? What are they?

Answer: There is lot strategy from government but lack of implementation of the strategies. Implementation of these strategies needs to be cleared. There is support from government but support is not adequate yet. Skill man power is very important. We have many cheap labour but they are not sufficient to run operation.

Sustainable performance

14. How is Bangladesh jute industry working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: Jute industry will be sustainable as it is eco friendly. It is the second largest processing country for jute. This sector is already sustainable but to make it more sustainable as I say there should be some steps. Whole system need to be in a shape and in a strategic good planned manner that can efficient for next five years. The industry should be sustainable and Sustainability can help this country with the circular economy of this country also. Both sector should take steps. Private and govt bot. govt. should come forward first. We are already using different machineries that are sustainable in their action. We also have measurements in processing our dust and residues from jute processing that help us to hold the micro-particles and waste from mixing with the environment.

15. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: Both government and private sector should come forward to make this sector sustainable. Of course there is some rules and regulations and I think Bangladesh is maintaining it, but there are some other factories who are not maintaining it. It can be said that even though we have policies and rule, it is not strictly being followed. So, here government has some scope to bring improvement.

16. What is your suggestion in this term to improve performance in future?

Answer: My overall suggestion will be to focus on skilled man power and upgrade technologies. It should be welcomed by the government and private sector. Also Banks have to come forward to lend money. Government should make plans for sustainability and circular economy for next ten years for Bangladesh. Diversification of jute product can help our country. We can overcome the challenges and reached of the first position if we actually follow the plan.

PARTICIPANT: INDUSTRIAL PROCESSING EXPERT 4

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: Above 45 / Male

Profession: INDUSTRIAL PROCESSING EXPERT

Institution: N/A

Job position: General manager

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

≥20

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: you know Bangladesh jute quality is number one in the world, other than Bangladesh, India and China also growing jute. Their quality and production are not as good as Bangladesh.

However, Bangladesh mostly exports raw jute and the competitive countries ahead in DJP than us. Basically, Bangladesh climate and soil are suitable for cultivating jute. So, we can grow huge amount of raw jute which we can export. I think world knows Bangladesh for its jute product. It was once the renowned place for jute. The global jute market is getting demanded, I think. I have recently seen lots of groceries in our country supplying jute bags which really feel good. There are few small shops by different entrepreneurs are raising around the country who are selling different products including some jute product, which is really impressive. When I was abroad, I have also noticed the jute bag and different DJPs made with jute. However, it was sad that not all are labelled that produced from Bangladesh. I think India and China has a great contribution in global jute market, especially for the DJP. But it is the good news that we advanced a lot comparing to past to promote the jute product. We learned to use jute differently so that we can increase the market demand. A significant change that I have noticed recently is the sector of private run jute factories. They produce significant amount of jute product and exporting rest of the world.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Considering past both jutes growing, processing and export increase. We export different product to the different countries in the world. Covid and Ukraine war and now war in middle east are affecting our jute market badly. Many of our jute industries are also getting shut down because of their bankruptcy. With all of this situation, industries whatever is left are now mostly focusing on surviving. Right now we are trying to survive. Its really critical time for this sector.

Production strategy

3. What strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute industries are adopting in terms of increasing their production and meeting global jute demand?

Answer: Production, processing and other cost is very high in jute sector. Raw jute price is always fluctuating a lot, it's never stable. This year raw jute price is significantly up because farmer struggled to retted their jute. This year has low rain fall and less water in the lake and river. If our buying price going up, we need to sell in higher price but the buyer does not want to pay higher price. Basically, now we are trying to survive. We are trying to minimize our cost as low as possible and in the same time we trying to produce more. So that we can offer our buyer competitive price, not to lose our buyer. We are importing improved machineries from other countries to improve our production. We are also getting training to apply upgraded processing strategy. With the imported machineries, it is now easy to focus on quality product

4. How do you think about Bangladesh jute industry in global jute market with such strategies in next 10 years? (any recommendation) future of such strategy

Answer: I think it's quite sustainable strategy for Bangladesh, continuous improvement by using upgraded machine, technology and reducing production cost can do much better in the upcoming future. We can see now demand is up trend by still now it's not that much. When demand will increase globally and domestic then can will change our strategy i think, we will switch our strategy to profit maximization and work on more valuable product. You know diversified jute product we can attract more buyer and market and it will help us increase the

jute demand in globally. Government has some positives activities in diversified jute product production. Now government giving has some subsidies for exporting DJP. I think it will be better for this sector.

Diversified jute product

5. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with diversified jute product? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their production of diversified jute product? progression

Answer: i think we are bit behind compared to China and India. China is dominating now in DJP market. We need move quite a bit; we are just at the beginning stage. We need to develop technology and machineries to produce industrial scale because most of the DJP is being produce in smaller scale. They are the small intrapreneurs and are taking steps towards advancing DJPs of Bangladesh. However, to optimize the financial loss, they are mostly starting this production and processing at small scale. With proper support from the government and other associated industries, such innovation can be extended and will help to satisfy global demand. We need develop knowledgeable people, not much research work is going on. We need to increase funding on it. We not only export raw jute but also jute yarn, jute bags. Jute yarn basically using carpet back clothing. Already people know about Bangladesh as jute and jute product exporter. If we can make industry base policy and focused on it i think we could do much better.

6. What is your suggestion about diversified jute products that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?

Answer: if we want to dominant the global market for DJP. We need to pay attention towards increasing number of products, improving technology and machines and skilled manpower. There are several organizations and individuals develop different product and also low-cost jute products are being invented. Need to be nursing them and allocate fund for them so that they can carry on their research. Government needs to bring more skilled people in this sector. Not only for DJP but also, we need develop low-cost process for jute product. Continuously developing low-cost jute substitute product are also introducing, its the biggest threat of this sector as well we need keep in our mind.

Current technology use

7. What upgraded processing techniques are they following to increase quality product production?

Answer: Processing techniques are same as before, but we are using upgraded machines. By the using upgraded machine we are getting more production and also better quality. As you know we do not have machine manufacturing company most of our machine are from China. What they are using we are also using the same machine. Before machine need to be controlled by hand now, we are trying to introduce inverter-controlled machine, which will be much better controlled. As i know India also using the almost same kind of machines as well. You know

Bangladesh, China and India this are the country supply most of jute and jute related products. So that they do not have upgraded machines than us but i think we should have at least one machine manufacturing companies so that they will not have competitive advantage than us. It is also a matter of concern that the privet industries are showing more positive attitudes and initiatives towards upgrading their machineries and technology comparing to government industries. The privet industries are more competitive in attitude as they want to make a good position in global market. Whereas, government industries are mostly following old approaches and not that much keen to take initiatives. Government has a big role to play here to make them trained and aware. We need to do concentrate on research really, government organization those are dedicated to jute and individual researcher are reluctant to upgrade the jute processing technique.

8. What is your opinion about technologies that is being used in Bangladesh Jute industry? Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries?

Answer: as I have already told you, we are using almost same processing technique but upgraded machines. Most of the machines are coming from China or India. They are the main competitor of jute industry in Bangladesh. So that we can tell that we are also using the same machines and technology, but we do not have competitive advantage. We should have machines manufacturing unit so that we can do better improvement. Jute basically born in Bangladesh, and we introduce jute to the rest of the world, in this long time we should have done lots of improvement.

9. How are these improvements helping Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: since we are using modern machines, we were getting extra produce which make do for our industry. We can offer better price to our customers which help us to retain our customer and compete the competitor. you know our jute quality is much better than other country, we do not have that much consumption locally, however country like India they need to satisfy their own demand first then they export rest but export the most. I think it will help us to dominate the jute export market.

10. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute industry can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: We need to improve our quality and quantity to fulfil the existing demand and attract more buyer. Jute price and quality always fluctuate lot. Both government and private sector need to work together to down the price. We need to upgrade our technique and technology not only in industrial level but also need to develop from field level to everywhere. Otherwise, it is not possible to minimising the cost and attract more buyer and dominate the world market. we do not only compete the prise and attract the world, always we need to compete with cheap alternative as well.

11. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Answer: we need more funding, which movement can do that. We need to upgrade our technique from field to processing and need to invent new technology as well. Need to do more research. Both government and private sector need to take it more seriously and need to work accordingly.

12. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

Answer: I think with 5 years most of the factories will upgrade their machines. We need to invent new technique i do not think it will be possible with in this time period but i hope it will be very soon. We just need to improve awareness.

Involvement of government

13. Is there any support from government in improving current processing of jute in Bangladesh? What are they?

Answer: very little support we are getting from government which is 10% cash incentive for exporting jute product and 15% subsider for DJP. Almost no support for research to improving the jute sector. I think government do not have any interest on it. Need to make tread deal with different countries which is completely missing. We have some jute friendly policy but no implication, government is reluctant on it.

We need to ensure the financial support. Without adequate financial support, it is not possible to compete with developed countries. Many industries around here are interested in upgrading their technology but lack of fund from government. So, this is one of the important facts that is hindering advancement in technology upgrade.

Sustainable performance

14. How is Bangladesh jute industry working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: Jute is natural one of the fibers. its process is almost sustainable. In field level need extra water for retting otherwise rest of it sustainable. In the industrial level most of the factory are export oriented we need to follow the local law as well as compile with international law. When I am saying international laws, I want to mention about labour law, and particularly child law. You know how some people of our country misuse children against the child law. Abandoned children are working different places which is against child law. However, we as jute industry in Bangladesh, we are trying to comply with global labour law. We are trying to respect the law made for child labour. Most of the factories are sustainable.

15. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: basically, we are following the local law and international law like labour law, using ETP and child law and so on as I have already told you. You know if you do not compile with the law and regulation, it is not possible to manage the factory now. Most of the buyers has guideline, you have to follow if you are wants to work with them. In terms of environment sustainability. Besides, some of the industry has auditing facilities that assure in regular basis

that they are working in the manner as they should be. Like our industry has governmental audit every year which keep us in track and motivate us to follow sustainable manners in our industry. This has started from recent few years that I really appreciate personally.

t16. What is your suggestion in this term to improve performance in future?

Answer: Different conferences and seminar occurs occasionally to inform us about recent practices around the world and to aware us about sustainable production process. However, I do not think such action are being implemented. We are learning about the effects of different sustainable production processes, but not implementing them in real life. It requires training, skilled knowledge, and most importantly adequate budget to undertake the actions.

PARTICIPANT: AGRICULTURAL EXPERT 1

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: 35-40/ Male

Profession: CROP SCIENCE RESEARCHER

Institution: Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (BJRI)

Job position: Senior- scientific officer

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

≤10

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: On the basis of literature and news, Bangladesh has the second position in jute production and India got the first position. On the basis of industrial importance jute is just after the cotton. However, in actual scenery, Bangladesh is first in production although there is no authentic evidence for such position of Bangladesh yet. On the other hand, in terms of export, Bangladesh is the first among all other countries and India is second.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: I have joined in Jute Development Board at 2017 and then I heard from our senior staff that 8 million behl jute was cultivated from 8 lakh hector field. Now cultivation land amount has decreased. Now around 7.4 lakh hector field is used for jute cultivation. the yield/production has not increased that much, nearly same. However, the cultivable land is being decreased. So, we can say that we are getting more production from less land. Intensity of production per land is increasing.

Production strategy

3. What field strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute sector is adopting in terms of increasing their production and meeting global jute demand?

Answer: Firstly i can say farmers are losing interest to cultivate jute. The production cost is so high that farmer not getting back the cost after selling jute. Not meeting desired market price. This is a problem. Some type of jute need 120 days time to harvest. But if they can harvest it in 100 days then they can cultivate other crop in same season. But this is not possible, they missed the season for other crop and lose interest for jute. Weather is also a big fact for jute cultivation. Suppose when we need rain we do not get it. It effects on retting. Jute production varies region wise As per weather, market value, man power and other relatable component.

we are importing 80-90% seed from India. We are trying to get the 100 days harvest seed. BADC are taking seed from us. We are trying to supply our own seed and use our own to have better use and quality. To produce more seed so that we can fullfill our seed demand and increase production.

Mechanisation- we developed some new machineries to reduce labour cost. In ribbon retting the jute stick get broken during retting processing and we used to get the jute fiber as output. But now we are activating new machinery that will break a bit of jute stick and we can get the fiber. So, we get fiber without breaking stick. We have also different retting techniques that is cost effective/ reduced cost so we can get prefeed market price. We are taking different actions in corporation with BJMC and other jute market related associations to settle our jute market and its price.

4. What are the steps being taken by jute cultivators to produce more jute against climatic barriers? (Improve seed/ genetically modified cultivars/ cultivation strategy etc.)?

Answer: We have mainly two commercially jute species (deshi and tosa jute). Deshi jute is more climatically adapted comparing to tossa. The diameter of desi jute (near to the bottom) is more comparing to its other part of stem. So, we get more fiber from the bottom part of the stem. And the quality of fiber is not so good. On the other hand, the quality and quantity of fiber from tossa jute is higher than deshi. So, farmer of our country usually cultivate and prefer tossa rather than desi jute. So, we are try to do some mutation, salinity tolerent and drought tolerant variety of tossa jute. However, it will take some time (2-5 years) to develop and implement such variety in field. Still in laboratory and testing process.

5. How jute cultivation in Bangladesh is planning to increase with extending cultivation area?

Answer: Few days ago i submitted a report where I said World Bank going to take a project through us where they will research how jute cultivation can extended in climatic variety area. We have already submitted information related this. They are working on it. Still we are giving plan for the extension....

6. What do you think about Bangladesh jute industry in global jute market with such strategies in next 10 years? (Any recommendation)?

Answer:

As jute is not a food crop, it is commercial crop, so the preference of jute cultivation will be same not more. So, we need to utilise the land and resource what we have but in effective way. I believe if Bangladesh Jute Corporation can develop the stress tolerant variety (biotic and abiotic), specially the drought, salinity, etc stress tolerant, then we can get 1.5-time higher jute production in 10 years. Besides, With producing own seed, we can fulfil our seed demand and increase production.

The most import variety we need now is to get jute yield in less duration. With this we can use the existing available land and get more yield. With such increasing intensity production, we can get whatever we need from reduced land.

7. What is your thinking about hydroponic and vertical farming in terms of jute cultivation to increase the production?

Answer: We have already tried hydroponic farming on jute, one of my friend came from Thailand and tried these but not succeeded and also this is a costly system. Only high valued or consumable crop is suitable for hydroponic cultivation. Crop that we can harvest in short-term. However, Jute is a long-time crop and it needed proper lighting. With proper sun light and timing can get high length fiber from jute. Besides, the root system of jute is also not suitable for hydroponic. It has tap root system, but for hydroponic we need vertical root system. Hydroponic farming is not for jute. With *buyer from various sector always*, I only was able to get seedlings of jute from seed. When they were growing more, they didn't survive. We do not need only seedling of jute, to get fiber, we need whole plant. So, in my opinion, hydroponic is not proper alternative growing system for jute to increase yield in land scarcity. We may get some yield from hydroponic or vertical farming (vertical farming with genetically modified jute crop that will have low height but quality fiber) with further research and initiatives. but not may fulfil our target production.

Current technology use

8. What is the technological improvement in jute cultivation and field processing?

Answer: technological improvement is happening in Jute cultivation and field processing. We are collecting ribbon from raw jute by using technology. We are not depending only on pond for retting. We are doing in artificial environment to get good quality and color. In the artificial environment we can use different microbes that we need to improve fiber quality.

9. Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries? How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: There are lots of improvements happening in Jute sector comparing the past. Jute industry is upgrading machineries, increasing production etc. This upgrade will help Bangladesh to compete with other countries. We did genome sequencing of jute that will help us improve jute variety with genetic modification.

India has lots of scope to produce jute seed. The seed we import from india, mostly comes in illegal way. Farmers buy it in very cheap price from broader market. This helps india to keep their business and jute market. So, we need to take action here to stop it and sell seed legally. We can try to produce our own seed to have the market.

In our country we have nearly 15-20 mills that use jute stick as charcoal. The charcoal produced from jute stick is inactive charcoal. Some country even imports this charcoal from our country (china, brazil) and process this into active carbon to use as ink of printing machine. So, if we can use this technique in our country then we can save a lot of expense from buying ink for printing machine. We have some running projects that are working on this but still if we get more support and more initiatives then Bangladesh can do great in jute market.

10. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute sector can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: I can say Bangladesh is doing well than India in using technology. Researches in genetically sector are giving us better quality jute. It will help us to get more stress tolerant and quality full jute. We have to improve quality and ensure the market price, reduce production cost.

We have to make our own seed. Maintaining/setting accurate market price is also a challenge. Government should take action to tackle the market price (seed, fiber, product) inside Bangladesh that will remain in preferable range for both buyer and seller. We need to reduce the production cost. We need to encourage modern farming (weeding, harvesting-modern technology, retting-artificial retting). In addition to all these, we can arrange different training program and relatable courses in different institute to encourage people towards technological development in jute sector.

11. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Answer: We need to take many projects. Farmers need training. Govt. Have to organize these training. We have better variety than India. But farmer import seed from them as we have seed scarcity. This is our major problem. However, I think in future new projects will come up from both BADC and BJRI to increase our seed production and provide farmer with quality seed. Another major challenge in our jute sector is the skilled manpower, which we are lacking. Most of the people involved with this sector needs to upgrade their skill. Besides, we are lacking of well communication between related institutes to coordinate our projects.

12. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

Answer: I think Jute production and jute field will increase in next 5 years by upgrading technology. Seed problem also will be solved then, and we will get some more variety.

Involvement of government

13. Is there any other support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute sector? What are they?

Answer: Project running is a difficult work. Skilled manpower needs to run any project. Govt. is very friendly about any project and research. They support to do the best. Govt. has positive attitude. We just need to do it properly.

We do not have appropriate technical manpower to implement such project.

We have around 280 diverse jute product that we are exporting worldwide. However, government is not doing this. It is being done by different small entrepreneur. They may have got some subsidies from government, but government can do more. Like arranging programs to train their skill. It will expand our opportunity

Sustainable performance

14. How is Bangladesh jute production working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: We have some bio friendly way that we are working on like using biofriendly techniques to protect plant from pathogen, artificial retting (with microbes to do the retting in efficient ways and in an ecofriendly way) to avoid hazard to aquatic eco-system etc. However, we do not have any way to show such activities that we are sustainable, to represent us as sustainable. Like there is organic cotton, but we do not present organic jute

15. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: It is possible to avoid chemical if the land management, fertilizer management remain ok. In past caterpillar made damage jute plant. To save jute from them chemical is being used. If we could use any bio pesticides, then we could reduce the chemical use on jute and make it more sustainable. Govt. needs to look into this matter.

Currently there is a mite (insect) that is most occurring pathogen of jute. However, we are using different bio friendly techniques against this pathogen. However, for other fungal disease we use some chemical.

16. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?

Answer: Bangladesh has lots of opportunities to better in jute sector. This country needs to make some policies and rules to improvement the present condition and ensure the implementation of it. As mentioned earlier, research and seminar should be held to aware people about DJP. Govt. and private sector have to come forward. Educational institute can increase interest of students to do research on this subject

Mostly farmer do not want to understand this bio safety issues. They just want to get rid of the problem. I think the agricultural extension officer can help here to make farmer understand and train them accordingly to maintain bio friendly system.

The retting process is not always sustainable if we are using pond water. River water is not a problem, and it is running. So, here we can use ribbon retting or artificial retting to become sustainable. Our farmer needs more training about this to make it sustainable. If we do the rotting process in river rather than pond, I think it will be more sustainable.

PARTICIPANT: AGRICULTURAL EXPERT 2

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: 35-40/ Male

Profession: CROP SCIENCE RESEARCHER

Institution: Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (BJRI)

Job position: Senior scientific officer

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

≤10

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: Everyone knows that Bangladesh is 2nd in jute production and 1st in jute export. All demands of jute are fulfilled from Bangladesh and India. You will find in maximum written 'made in India'. Bangladesh's jute growing progress is better than other countries. But jute production has decreased than past. In 2018-19 year jute production was 88 Lakh Metric Ton. But now it has been decreased in 66 lakh metric ton. Jute production increase and decrease depending on jute price. When thin is high, farmer feels more interested towards producing jute. This year's production will be better than last year.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: Progress is better now than past. Even though we have expected to have more improvement in the sector. We succeeded now to develop system where jute matured with 100-120 days which can be another reason for the progression (taking less time to harvest). However, Jute is not being harvested in every area. It has its own area to harvest. Jute mainly cultivated in the north and middle of the country. South side of the country cannot cultivate it because of the high salinity level. Jute seed doesn't germinate in that area. However, recently a variety has been founded (BJRI deshi pat 10) which can tolerate the salinity. It is in field application. Nevertheless, it is not being used that much still now as its just came in market very recently. Agricultural extension officers are still in process to introduce the variety to farmers.

Production strategy

3. What field strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute sector is adopting in terms of increasing their production and meeting global jute demand?

Answer: There is a variety (GRO 52) comes from India that can give yield 20 days earlier. So, farmer is more interested to that variety than using our own developed variety. With this earlier variety they can harvest early and cultivate another crop in the field. However, we have a variety developed (ROBI 1), that is better than the Indian variety. It gives higher yield than GRO 52. Nevertheless, farmer needs around 5000-5500 lac metric ton seed and we are not being able to provide such amount of seed to the farmer. In Bangladesh, total seed management is controlled by BADC. Farmers are not interested to take seed from BADC. Because there is less demand for jute. So, they prefer to take the seed from india. But we have the demand for Robi 1 variety seed. Farmer wants this seed but we are not able to provide it properly. We applied for a government project for huge seed production, if it is granted then hopefully we will be able to produce more seed and satisfy our farmer's seed demand. We have planned to build a seed production centre, where we will only produce jute seed. With such activities, we will be able to satisfy our seed demand and increase production

4. What are the steps being taken by jute cultivators to produce more jute against climatic barriers? (Improve seed/ genetically modified cultivars/ cultivation strategy etc.)?

Answer: Farmers in Bangladesh are using improved variety of jute to avoid any uncertain experience. They are more interested to use short duration variety with high yielding attributes comparing to their past used varieties. They want the yield within short period so that they can move onto next crop in the field rather than keeping the field occupied with only one crop in a year.

We have already some very good varieties developed that are stress resistance. They have also the attribute of very good quality fiber. Jute is a natural crop. Natural disasters are not occurred in the same way every time. These are very unwanted and uncertain. There is some goal to develop a variety. These are about heat resistance, salt tolerance, etc. However, we just need to make sure that we have enough seed for these varieties to provide farmer and we need to take them in field application. We are also working on developing further modified variety.

We already have different project work going in this aspect and more is about to get permission to work on.

5. How jute cultivation in Bangladesh is planning to increase with extending cultivation area?

Answer: As I said Jute production increase and decrease depends on jute price. If we can increase the market price and ensure the suitable environment for jute cultivation, then we can extend area for jute. There are no proper water source for retting jute.

The main reason of farmer's reluctance in jute cultivation is retting difficulties. With the water scarcity and unavailable proper condition, farmers are getting away from jute cultivation. They don't want to cultivate jute in their field and then struggle for retting.

Yes, we have ribbon retting system, but is it still not being used in everywhere. It has some problem as well with jute fiber. It breaks the jute stick which reduces the market price and increases the interest for the machine.

6. What do you think about Bangladesh jute industry in global jute market with such strategies in next 10 years? (Any recommendation)?

Answer: There is no alternative of jute product as eco friendly product. So I think jute production will increase in next 10 years. Because there is a demand for jute in world market.

7. What is your thinking about hydroponic and vertical farming in terms of jute cultivation to increase the production?

Answer: still in research level. Some institutes in Bangladesh has been started research and now in second generation of their research.

Researchers are searching for a new genome which can increase the hydroponic farming. Bangladesh atomic research institute is doing research by using gamma radiation. I have very little knowledge about this. They started it last year and still working on it.

Current technology use

8. What is the technological improvement in jute cultivation and field processing?

Answer: In past we don't have machineries for jute processing. But now we are developing and upgrading machineries to get better result. We have ribbon retting machine. We are also creating more jute diversified product than past. We are also launching charcoal production by using jute which will create less harmful Carbone. Can be used in printing machines as ink. In past, we did not have any diversified product. But now we are making diversified product day by day. We have started collaborating with industries which has been started already making diversified product. Recently we are working with them on Charcoal project.

9. Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries? How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: We have main problem in jute seed production. If we can overcome it we can compete strongly with other countries. If we focus on jute diversified product then it will help Bangladesh to compete with others. We have to spread this diversified product throughout the

market. Jute bags are eco-friendly but not washable. This is the reason people are not interested in using these bags. Besides plastic bags are much cheaper than jute bag. If there would be any rules and regulation then using bag will be increase.

10. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute sector can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: We have to produce more diversified product and for this we need to upgrade machineries in textile mills. They should work in collaboration with us. We have back dated machine. We need to update these machines. We can also bring improvement by proving required training to the farmer and other professional level regarding technological upgrade.

Everyone is interested about other food crop. Jute is not a food crop. So, farmers are not interested in it. But we need to make them interest. Agricultural officer should talk to farmer, make them understand and encourage them.

11. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Answer: Agriculture officers are not performing their duty properly. Govt. is friendlier to overcome any challenges but because of the irresponsibility's of few we are not being succeeded. We have to provide more training to farmer and officer. Every extension officer only discusses rice with the farmer. They need to discuss about jute more .They need to inform them about the demand of jute.

12. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

Answer: In present we are focusing on bio pesticides. We are trying to use environmental friendly ways to treat jute. We are going for a sustainable agriculture now which will not harm the environment. Govt. are taking various steps to reach this goal.

Involvement of government

13. Is there any other support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute sector? What are they?

Government is happy to give fund, but we need to make project plan. We need to make appropriate plan and then government will fund us. In my opinion, government has the willing to support but at least we as researcher also has the responsibilities to provide excellent project plant that will worth the funding to bring advancement in our system Govt. is very friendly about any project and research. They support to do the best. Govt. has positive attitude. We just need to do it properly. We have around 280 diverse jute product that we are exporting worldwide. However, government is not doing this. It is being done by different small entrepreneur. They may have got some subsidies from government

However, there are more scope where government can help the sector to improve its condition. The help can be in financial sector where government need to add more subsidies for jute professionals to encourage increased production and sale.

Sustainable performance

14. How is Bangladesh jute production working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

.no sustainable manner is being followed and represented

15. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

We are trying to use bio friendly system in jute pathogen treatment. However, still there are more scope that we can follow to be sustainable.

16. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?

It need proper training to farmer level, product supply, funding etc. Farmer wants easy and cheap way to work

PARTICIPANT: AGRICULTURAL EXPERT 3

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: 45/ Male

Profession: CROP SCIENCE RESEARCHER

Institution: Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (BJRI)

Job position: Senior- scientific officer

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

≤15

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: Jute is one of the natural fiber in the world. If we consider the case, it's in second position after cotton. It is very strong fiber so that it can be use in different case. Once it was golden fiber of Bangladesh and which brought most of the foreign currency for the country.

Cheap and user friendly polyethene replace most of jute market. But environmental cost of polyethene is high. So, now a days jute demand is showing uptrend. Bangladesh one of the jute producer and processor in the world. In jute cultivation Bangladesh is second after India but in jute export Bangladesh is first. Bangladesh and India growing 90% of total jute in the world. We believe jute demand will increase significantly in upcoming days.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: In our point of view current progression is significantly better than past because we have nearly same raw jute production however jute growing land is decrease day by day. We manage to invent new jute variety which have better yield. We are continuously working on it.

Production strategy

3. What field strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute sector is adopting in terms of increasing their production and meeting global jute demand?

Answer: most of the available jute variety takes long days to cultivation. So farmer missed one crop in a session if cultivating jute. Including jute they can cultivate only 2 crops instead of 3. so, farmers are more towards some varieties or agricultural strategy that will offer them short duration cultivation and harvesting facilities. We develop some variety which are possible to grow comparatively in less time. We are currently testing the varieties in the field. I think they are not available in the market so far. some Indian varieties are available in the market, which gets more attention from farmers due to their short-duration cultivation facilities over our local variety. However, our department has taken effective steps to solve this problem. We are trying hard to bring upgraded varieties to the market and to make them easy for farmers or agricultural dealers. Our government is also taking action in this regard to motivate enough seed distribution at the farmer level. Farmers are interested in adopting improved varieties that will benefit them by allowing them to yield sooner. They are also exploring different cultivable lands to see if they can cultivate jute differently. However, farmers mostly prefer to stay in their safe zones where they know that they will earn money. So, the agricultural extension officers have a great role here to encourage farmers to explore and adopt different new strategies to increase production.

In terms of advanced technological strategy, I think it is not that much improved. But I will surely appreciate the effort that our professionals are giving in to bring some advanced technology in the system to make it easier and profitable. You know, today's world is the technology-best world. We need to upgrade our technology at the field level and make it available for use. We developed different useful machines that can save labour. Now, we are trying to make them available for use. Jute cultivation is labour intensive, so if we can reduce labour, it will reduce cost. We also developed reteeing machines that can help with water scarcity.

4. What are the steps being taken by jute cultivators to produce more jute against climatic barriers? (Improve seed/ genetically modified cultivars/ cultivation strategy etc.)?

Answer: Jute is very sensitive crop to climate variation. It needs proper climatic condition to give yield. So, changing in environmental state or any change in cultivation needed to be considered. The global climate change is one of the important issue in adequate agricultural production. In Bangladesh, farmers are not that much aware of these issues. However, they just look for profit. They want to follow strategies that will profit for them. Researchers are continuously working to find out way to deal with different climatic adverse situation. However, not all of them are being applied. In Bangladesh, we are trying to provide farmers with different stress tolerant varieties and high yield varieties that will give required yield. However, we have our limitations here as well. The agricultural extension officers are helping farmers in different area of the country which is not suitable for jute cultivation, to introduce possible cultivation strategies that can be undertaken to produce jute. Farmers are really doing great, showing their interest. However, they need further motivation and if possible some financial assistance as well to start new cultivation strategy with associated risk.

5. How jute cultivation in Bangladesh is planning to increase with extending cultivation area?

Answer: Not all the lands in Bangladesh is favourable for jute cultivation. There are few areas where we cultivate jute most, such as Jessore, Meherpur, Kustia, Faridpur, Jamalpur and so on. Recently many more districts are cultivating jute with the improved cultivation strategy. However, we are still not using areas where the jute crop is challenging to grow. Mostly in coastal areas or drought areas. We need water to cultivate jute but in drought area this is promising. However, researcher and field workers are trying out different strategy to get these areas under jute cultivation. We just need more time and research application to further advance this sector. Farmers will definitely be interested in this improvements if we can provide them with some strategies that offer them easy cultivation. We can extend the cultivable areas in a place where still jute is not being cultivated and is not suitable to do so. SO, we are planning in this aspect to increase the production

6. What do you think about Bangladesh jute industry in global jute market with such strategies in next 10 years? (Any recommendation)?

Answer: In my opinion, the industry will see significant changes in the system if it gets proper support from professionals and the government, particularly in terms of implementing improved variety and seed distribution. So, I recommend field experts related to jute continue working for the betterment of our industry and to maintain consistency in the advancement.

7. What is your thinking about hydroponic and vertical farming in terms of jute cultivation to increase the production?

Answer: These two are really important for future agriculture. As the availability of arable land decreases, we must explore methods for vertical cultivation that do not rely on land or soil. In my personal interest, I have read a lot of articles on hydroponic. But I never came anything for jute cultivation. This can be really a great opportunity if we can do so. But thinking of the physical attributes of jute plant, I think it is challenging. But we are so advanced in technology today, we are improving very fast in our crop genetic mutation. So, I think if researchers want, they can take this challenge and work towards it. It will bring a great revolution in research.

Current technology use

8. What is the technological improvement in jute cultivation and field processing?

Answer: Farmers are showing great acceptance towards cost-effective advanced retting techniques to get preferred market price. The agricultural extension officers conducting different program to introduce new retting techniques to farmer and they said that the acceptance rate is very good. I think farmers have moved from their conventional retting to ribbon retting by now. We are improving jute cultivation and processing with new technologies. Instead of just using ponds for retting, we create artificial controlled environments to get better quality and color from the jute. These environments allow us to use different microbes that help improve the fiber quality

9. Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries? How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: yes, compared to the past, we have more varieties that we can use in the field to overcome the challenges associated with seed scarcity. In future we will get more. The other competitive countries has advanced more than us. But we are not sitting still. Our team is working really hard to bring improvement in the industry. I have not mentioned earlier I gusses, but our achievements in DJP is one of the significant fact that is definitely in the list. With the improvements in DJPs we will surely make a footstep in global market. We have variety of jute products now comparing to past. We are working on these product to market them internationally. Besides, our researcher are also working differently to identify how we can use jute in alternative way rather than just using as bag.

10. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute sector can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: The jute industry in Bangladesh has an exciting opportunity to grow and improve with better technology! By investing in modern research tools, we can really boost our research capabilities. With some support from the government, we can upgrade our labs and conduct more advanced studies in a shorter time. It's also important to think about our hardworking farmers. They are eager to use new technologies that can make their farming practices even better, but affordability is key. Right now, many machines out there are just too expensive for them. We need to focus on creating cost-effective solutions that fit their budgets. By tackling these challenges together, we can make the Bangladeshi jute industry more competitive on the global stage. Investing in research and affordable technology will not only help our farmers but also strengthen our position in the international market.

11. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Answer: technological upgrade is one of the most important aspects in the current world, I think. The advanced countries are really experiencing a great time with innovative technology. However, as an underdeveloped country, you can imagine our comparative technology compared to other countries. I will not say that we are advanced but yeah improved than before. As I said our economy is one of the biggest challenges in our development. We need huge

funding to set up the advanced technology and skilled man power as well. If we only have the technology without a skilled person to run it, then there is no point in having it. Some of our industries or institutions are bringing upgraded technology, but as I said, lack of manpower is an obstacle to its effective processing. It happens mostly in governmental organizations. They need more professional people who know their work. Adequate funding will also help the industries to pay for advanced technology. Also we need to find out the technology that we need. It is not that we export any machineries and there is no use of it. So, a skilled person is also needed there to identify our needs and to improve technology accordingly.

12. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

Answer: In the coming 5 years there will be a huge change in the practice. We have lots of plan in the process that need approval and implications. So, within the time period, I think we will be able to apply the upgrade in field and to see the improvement.

Involvement of government

13. Is there any other support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute sector? What are they?

Answer: The government is providing great support, but there is still scope to extend the actions to a better level. They need to be determined to improve the current condition and remain consistent in helping the sector. The government provides different support to the farmers by arranging different knowledge development programs. Besides, government research centres are also contributing a lot to recent research advancements. The government gave certain targets to fulfill in the advancement of the industry. However, the recent action from the government to shut down many jute industries is really disappointing for the development of the industry. They should have thought a solution for the problem. Obviously, there was some reason to do so, but I think the government needs to be very cautious about the vulnerability of the Bangladesh jute industry and should take appropriate steps to take the industry ahead in the global market.

Sustainable performance

14. How is Bangladesh jute production working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: We have some sustainable practice that can be considered like bio pesticides and artificial retting. But I do not think that these practices get recognition when government is trading the product. Anyway, there is positive responses from farmer to follow such instruction. They need more training and facilities (financial) to conduct such practice in huge scale. As explained, jute processing requires huge amount of water and farmers are not using different improve techniques which you can also consider as sustainable action. Farmers are well educated of environmental pollution than before, however, it is different question that how they are applying their knowledge and how motivate they are.

15. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: Sustainable is a big term for farmers, they do not know the meaning. It is an expensive term for them. Farmers want some strategy that will be cheap, cost-effective, and easy to apply, with what they can get early yield. However, recently, we have been promoting different sustainable measures to the farmer, and farmers are always welcoming to new strategy. However, they need some training so they can use it effectively. and many industrial-level cultivation are also giving field guidelines to follow sustainable measures. Mostly, they use less pesticide, and some are made with natural products, which you call bio-pesticide, but it needs more sincerity from to maintain this consistently in the field. The rules and regulations are not that strict, which will make people follow them. So, people in our country easily avoid it and do as they prefer it to be done.

16. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?

Answer: Lots of things can be done differently to improve our condition. However, I think it is better to finish the action that we are already aiming at rather than starting at every point and delay. Even a simple and small improvement can be better than doing nothing. So, my suggestion will be to 'continue what you are doing' do not stop. Success will come.

PARTICIPANT: AGRICULTURAL EXPERT 4

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: 35-40/ Male

Profession: CROP SCIENCE RESEARCHER

Institution: Bangladesh Jute Research Institute (BJRI)

Job position: Senior scientific officer

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

≤15

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: The current state is better than the past, I guess, even though the government recently closed many of the jute mills. However, the production is still satisfying demand and we are seeing lots of improvements taking in place. Due to our economy, I think the overall condition is bit slow, but the place of Bangladesh jute industry in global market is still holding the place with prestige. Bangladesh stands out as the second-largest producer and a primary exporter of jute, a versatile natural fiber. The country has traditionally led in jute cultivation. In recent years some fluctuation was seen in production, due to different global issues. The price of jute product also modulate the production rate. This year, it's expected that jute production will rebound compared to last year. Nowadays jute demand is showing an uptrend. however jute growing land is decrease day by day.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: The jute sector is experiencing some exciting progress these days! Thanks to new innovations in cultivation techniques, farmers are now able to use a system that speeds up the maturation process of jute plants. This means they can harvest their crops more quickly and efficiently. However, it's important to note that jute growth is mostly limited to certain areas. This fibrous plant really thrives in the lush northern and central regions of the country, where the soil conditions are just right. Unfortunately, in the southern regions, high salinity levels in the soil can make it quite challenging for seeds to germinate and grow. In great news for the industry, researchers are working hard to develop new jute varieties that can handle tough weather conditions and be more adaptable to different growing environments. These promising new varieties are currently in field trials, but they're still quite new to the market. To help introduce these exciting varieties to farmers, agricultural extension officers are on the ground, ready to educate and support them. They're committed to guiding farmers toward innovative practices that can boost yields and promote sustainable jute cultivation. It's an inspiring time for the jute industry!

Production strategy

3. What field strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute sector is adopting in terms of increasing their production and meeting global jute demand?

Answer: We are applying different strategies that are better than before to increase production. For example, you can see in the field that farmers are using new machinery to process field products after the harvest. Earlier, they used to do everything manually, but we have some advanced technology that minimizes the workload and makes better-quality products. Farmers are more relaxed with jute processing now, and it is even less polluted. Before, the jute

processing from field used to be done in pond, still it is being, but in better version. We are also trying to introduce new improved techniques to the farmer and they are really interested to improve the quality product. Particularly advancement in retting. We have some improvement in another sector of agriculture, you can see that farmers are more knowledgeable than in the past. We took the steps to educate them. The agricultural extension officers are working more to work with farmers and to give them latest information.

4. What are the steps being taken by jute cultivators to produce more jute against climatic barriers? (Improve seed/ genetically modified cultivars/ cultivation strategy etc.)?

Answer: Our team is developing new types of jute. These jute varieties can resist climate stress. Jute is a natural crop but is vulnerable to natural disasters. These disasters can hurt jute production. We aim to create jute that is heat-resistant and salt-tolerant. It is important to provide enough seeds from these new varieties to farmers. This will help farmers plant them and increase their yields. We are also focused on improving these jute varieties continuously. We have ongoing projects to enhance jute plant qualities. We hope to get approvals for more ambitious projects soon. Our goal is to help farmers succeed and promote sustainable practices in the jute industry.

5. How jute cultivation in Bangladesh is planning to increase with extending cultivation area?

Answer: We have already extended the areas of jute cultivation compared to the past. Now in more places, the jute is being cultivated. Farmers around all over the country are willing to include jute to their field. However, it needs more actions to motivate them and to include different uncultivable lands into the jute cultivation. The main problem with it is its long term cultivation. It causes problem to involve any other crops in the same field. So, researcher can suggest farmers with some cropping strategies that they can apply to cultivate other crops along with jute then it will be a great advancement.

6. What do you think about Bangladesh jute industry in global jute market with such strategies in next 10 years? (Any recommendation)?

Answer: With the speed of current improvement, the jute industry will advance more in the future. Lots of strategical improvement is present here in the field that is increasing the production. However, farmers and researchers need to work more to find easy solution of the challenges. Some industries in Bangladesh has started the artificial retting to avoid the challenges associated with conventional retting. And in industrial level, you know they need quality product. So, some industries are using different artificial retting techniques. However, it is in limited use since it needs special training and acceptance by the farmer to get it in field level. With such training, the industry will be able to apply this competitive strategy in their system in near future.

On the other hand, I think the seed distribution problem is another concern that the authorised people need to pay attention. Farmers are forced to buy expensive seeds which ultimately reduce their interest in jute farming. The easy availability of quality seed is very important, which is missing in our jute system, I guess. Farmers are in field to grow the crops but it is our responsibilities to assure that they *get all* the facilities in effective cultivation.

7. What is your thinking about hydroponic and vertical farming in terms of jute cultivation to increase the production?

Answer: I do not have much knowledge of this, and I haven't heard anything related to it. But it seems promising. I guess it can be a great area to work on.

Current technology use

8. What is the technological improvement in jute cultivation and field processing?

Answer: As I have already mentioned about artificial retting in industrial application. It can be considered as one of the technological advancements. Using this modern technology with microbes, the hassle in pond retting of jute is getting less. On the other hand, farmers are also accepting different advancement in retting approach with some provided strategy that cost them less and provide with higher quality of jute. They are mostly using ribbon retting but the artificial retting and other cost effective rettings are introducing as new advanced one. However, if you are directing towards proper technological advancement, like machineries in industry to process jute, I do not have that much knowledge on that. Some improved machineries we are using in field to process raw jute. The technological advancement is also in the aspect of using modern technology by the dealers like email, phone, transportation to make deal for raw jute to the industry.

9. Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries? How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: Jute industry in Bangladesh is the renowned one and old sector to earn foreign money. In past, we were very popular for our raw jute and some other jute products. We are still in the top position for raw jute. However, we need to improve the quality of product to advance in global market. Recent improvement in our jute product is really deserve appreciation. It brought huge changes in the quality and diversification in product as well. We can proudly compare the quality and quantity of our jute with other competitive industry. The agricultural practice associated with jute has experienced a huge change. Farmers know a lot these days. They are learning different strategic practice that will increase their yield and production. The technological advancement that I mentioned earlier is also great to say that we are advancing.

10. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute sector can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: In my view, the jute industry in Bangladesh needs to improve its technology to create better jute products. Modern strategies exist that can help speed up the production and processing of jute. However, these modern methods are not widely used yet. Farmers show interest in these new techniques, but they face several challenges. One major issue is the lack of skills; many farmers are not trained in using advanced technology. Financial support is also a problem, as not all farmers can afford the necessary tools and resources. Additionally, farmers are used to traditional methods and may be hesitant to change. While they are eager to try new techniques, they require proper guidance and support to make this transition. Improving technology is important, but it is equally crucial to implement it effectively. If we fail to apply these improvements in the right way, then the development will not bring the desired results.

Proper training and resources are essential to ensure that advancements in technology truly benefit the jute industry.

11. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Answer: As I have mentioned that financial support is a big problem in the upgrade. To implement new technology, need to finance in that sector. Besides, finding out the necessity is also important. We need to go through the current application to identify which technology we need in the future so it will provide effective use of the financial support.

12. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

Answer: There will be significant upgrade obviously. As you can see lots of upgrade is happening now comparing to past. So, it is clear that we will see more. But for this we need to follow the recommended guideline. Researcher can provide us with latest knowledge, and we can follow the path for improvements. Government and policy make can also take valuable action here, otherwise the improvement will be longer.

Involvement of government

13. Is there any other support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute sector? What are they?

Yes, the government is supporting the industry in the improvement of its DJP varieties and marketing. There is a governmental DJP institute that is working on to improve out DJP state and to take this in global market. However, I am not very clear about their recent activities. But in my knowledge, they exist and may be doing some great things. Government is also undertaking a big steps towards making promising improvement in seed distribution. The target is to provide easy and quality seed to the farmer. So, if we succeed to do so, we can use our own seed in the field to increase production in cost effective way.

Sustainable performance

14. How is Bangladesh jute production working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

The production of jute in Bangladesh is following different upgraded strategies along with some old strategies. The early strategies of retting jute were not that environmentally friendly. It was not good for the water environment. However, farmers are moving from that culture and trying to use something new, according to advice from agricultural experts. In the industrial level of jute cultivation, some other environmentally sustainable manners are also being used, such as using natural pesticides that do not harm the environment and help to avoid pests as well. So you can say these activities are sustainable actions, I guess; I am only aware of this many actions that I can mention to you. However, you can find more if you discuss some agricultural extension officers to know what they are proposing.

15. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

I do not think there are any rules and regulations in terms of following the sustainable measures. If there are then I will say they are not being applied properly.

16. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?

As you said, we should have some rules and regulations to maintain this at the field level, and the government also needs to impose this law so we can present ourselves as sustainable producers in the global market. It will help to rank us more.

PARTICIPANT: MARKETING EXPERT 1

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: 40-50/ Male

Profession: MARKETING EXPERT

Institution: N/A

Job position: Marketing manager

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

10-20

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: Bangladesh has 1st position in global market of jute. It considering the production, export and all. Whatever you are talking about jute, Bangladesh is in the top with its quality jute production. The 'Golden Fiber' is Bangladesh's own product.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: In past everything was maintained by government. But after the huge loss, now private sector started to run jute industry in Bangladesh. Private sector is doing well in jute industry in

last twenty years. Maximum govt. jute mills have been closed. Adamji, the biggest one has already closed. Besides it some other jute mill in Khulna and Jessore are also closed. Now private mills are active. Bangladesh jute sector progressing after private sector involved into this. In terms of exporting, Bangladesh is exporting more in recent years I guess comparing to past.

Diversified jute product

3. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with diversified jute product? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their sale of diversified jute product?

Answer: Our closest competitor is India. Many country are importing our raw jute but India imports huge amount raw jute from Bangladesh and make diversified product, then export it to other countries. Because the quality of raw jute of Bangladesh is far better than India. This is our big problem because India already controls the diversified global market. This is the new challenge for Bangladesh jute industry after going in private hands. Last three years we couldn't do proper business because of covid and war. This is the reason we are not in good position in market. India also imposed anti-dumping legislation on only diverse jute product from Bangladesh, not on raw jute. Which also hampering our private sector which are making different diversified product. India only taking the raw jute.

We have some diversified jute product, but yarn is the most exporting jute element. Comparing to past, Bangladesh is improving in diversified jute product. We are now more in the market to advertise our product with the advancement in online marketing. Lots of private firms are taking initiatives to do online business with both local and international buyers.

4. What is your suggestion about diversified jute products that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?

Answer: We have to over come all the barriers about export diversified product. Now we have to search new market for jute. Natural fiber has always a demand, but Buyers are now interested in plastic product because of the higher price of jute. Cost of the raw material has been increased and that's why the price of yarn increased. This is the reason of increase in overall production costing. Buyer from different places is losing interest on jute product in the presence of cheap substitute. So, we just need to minimize the price of jute product to hold customer. We need to minimise the production cost and increase sale. This is the reason for market falling. In previous year, buyer gave us 1000 dollar per ton yarn. Now they are giving 2000 dollar per ton yarn. This is huge rising of cost. We have to create the demand for jute and minimize the cost if we want to improve the sale. We need to offer attractive price to the buyer. We need to provide subsidies to the farmer so that they can produce more. The cost of container that carries product from Bangladesh to another country is getting higher. Suppose I am sending a container from Bangladesh to America, I had to pay 5000 dollar per container. But now I have to pay 15000 dollar per container. This is because container production has been interrupted by covid-19 situation. One container can not be used after five years of its making. Many shipping line is also getting closed due to current global situation. So we need to pay high in export.

We need to increase our production to tackle price. For the present situation of world, people are concentrating on basic need product. Jute made product are for basic need. These are for hobby or decoration. This is the reason people are getting uninterested to buy such things. They are minimizing their cost due to global crisis. By overcome these situation we can increase our production.

Current technology use

5. What kind of new marketing technology are you using? How can they planning be improved?

Answer: Buyer from different country comes to visit and we also visit them. Maximum are depend on this. This is how we attract them by showing them our production are. While visiting here, they can have first-hand look in our product and can assess its quality before buying. On the other hand, when we visit them, we can also have an idea about their requirement and can show our products during our visit to them. So, this is how we communicate sometimes to improve interaction between us and to increase sale.

We have to attend different fair which are held in different country (china, Germany, dubai). Mainly this fair is about carpet. Although this is a carpet oriented fair so our concern people visit there and promote our industry. Our concern people need to visit these fair.

To improve the situation of marketing our govt. have to come forward along with private sectors and some association, specially our Chamber of commerce need to help us. They should combine together and go to those country who are interested in jute and convince them and arrange some seminar for them.

6. How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: Other competitive country has government support. They have also pressure from government. From my own experience I want to say something, once I was in Thailand for a fair and there I came to know that there are a huge demand for jute made bag. But we are getting the buyer, India getting. If we follow their minimum duty we can improve ourselves. Government should focus on these issue. There are huge demand of jute bag in China, Thailand, Indonesia and other country. Our government to collaborate with them to capture the market. We are using the same category upgraded and improved machine as other countries doing. So it is certain that there is no competition in terms of technological use. It is nearly same for all the exporting countries. It is about the availability of skilled manpower who are operating the machine.

7. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute industry can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: Those who are involved in Jute industry and export maintenance association, has to come forward to improve the entire situation. They have to take some steps, arrange some seminar with buyer to improve current position. We know where we have our jute industries.

So, if we can arrange seminars at that location for buyers then it will be so helpful to attract buyer and take them to the industrial area.

Besides, we can have our own manufacturing industries that will provide us required machineries for the development of diverse jute product. We have opportunities to produce more diverse product, but we do not have the proper machineries and skilled man-power. If we can import machineries in lower price or make them by ourselves then we can reduce the production cost as well, which is very important currently in meeting global demand of jute product at lower price. Importing machineries from other country is expensive and affect the overall market price of our product. To operate the modern machineries and technology, skilled manpower is also required who have knowledge and experience in the area. Only experienced or knowledgeable person can operate the machineries and use technology effectively.

8. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

we do not have the proper machineries and skilled man-power

9. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

If we can import machineries in lower price or make them by ourselves then we can reduce the production cost as well, which is very important currently in meeting global demand of jute product at lower price.

Besides, I will suggest that if it is possible for us to make our own machine in Bangladesh, this will be the best option for the sector improvement. We can make desired machineries and can make it competitive to other countries.

Pricing

10. How you establish both internal (local) and external (export) pricing? What facts do you consider in establishing pricing?

Answer: When we pricing for local market, we know that we will not get any subsidy from government so local price become high. But in export pricing we consider the subsidy matters and price become low.

Government is not taking actions towards making the carrying container cheap or ease available. This has ultimate impact on the overall pricing. If we can carry or transport our product easily at lower price then the overall product price will also become less.

11. What do you think of competitive pricing and how jute industries in Bangladesh are working in this?

Answer: If we can sell jute randomly in a particular market then we can stay one step ahead than other country in pricing. But we can continue it randomly.

12. What is your pricing strategy to increase export profitability?

Answer: If we get back our previous market and can control the market then we can increase the export profitability. We need high sale to get profit. If we do not have any sell we will not get any profit. If we lose the market we have no issue with these price rising, quality things. So at first what we have to do is to keep control on the market. We can also enable duty free marketing of our product. It will bring some profit and improve the marketing.

13. What is the local pricing strategy to keep market flow inside the country?

Answer: If we got any subsidy from government then we could keep the market flow inside the country. Government has taken project against plastic bag and made policy to sell jute bag. But implementation was not done properly. There are some industries who buy yarn from local market at lower price and sell different diverse product only in local market at high price. So, they meet their price demand. But it is not same for big industries who sell both locally and export outside.

14. What is your suggestion about improvements in existing pricing strategy that will increase profit?

export commission bureau can make arrangement and deal with other countries to sell our product in their country at standard price.

Trading barriers

15. What is your thought about different trading barriers that Bangladesh jute industry is experiencing?

Answer: Our jute industry should research what other country are doing to overcome barriers and follow it.

16. How is Bangladesh jute industry tackling with such barriers?

Answer: Private sectors are trying to solve the barriers. They are visiting other country, business fair and learning from them. Recent environment is very good in private sectors. That's why they are sustaining. Then they are applying it to tackle such barriers. No can improve the situation alone. All sectors should come forward together.

17. What policies Bangladesh jute industry applies when experiencing any logistic port problem?

Answer: In past it took almost one week to reach CTG port but now with the help of government we can reach CTG in short time. So I can say that we already overcome the logistic port problem. Government look into this problem and solve it. In previous it took 7 days to reach CTG port, but now-a-days it is taking 24 hours to reach. There are no problem now. Every logistic work has been online based.

Involvement of government

18. How Bangladesh Government helps with its rules and regulation to overcome logistic challenges experienced by Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: Now every work is online based. So we face fewer problems than previous. That is only because of government help. But there is also a problem. We have only one international port. So sometimes here we face schedule problem. Government are already taking necessary steps to overcome it. If they make more international port then it will be easier for us, we can work smoothly. Otherwise, there will be huge pressure on one port.

19. Is there any other support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute industry? What are they?

Answer: Govt. has not so many things to do. But what already they did to support to jute industry we should thank for it. And we have convince government to do more support in future.

Government should take necessary step to hold our quality raw jute in home, we can do one more thing to not to export to India. We should keep it to us. We have barrier to export yarn, other jute product but no regulation on raw jute export.

Need to remove these barriers from exporting yarn and DJP so we can export them easily

Sustainable performance

20. How is Bangladesh jute industry working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: Bangladesh jute industry working in a sustainable manner. We don't use any chemical. That's why jute industry is not threaten to environment. This is a very natural process.

21. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: Time to time government visit our factory and ensure the sustainability. They make lot of rules and regulation to keep it sustainable. We have to submit report on various thing time to time. Our labour ministry always monitor these things. We have to maintain also the international rules for sustainability. We are exporting, so we have to maintain international rules and regulations.

22. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?

Answer: We are still in market because of our quality. So we have to keep and maintain the quality. Not only personal and private attempt, government need to help to open door for new jute market in Europe and America. Now Europe market has been closed for us. In past we export to them directly but they are buying via third party. This is the reason we are not benefiting more. So if we can maintain these things I think we can improve performance in future. Government should increase its subsidy and support DJP production. To improve performance in future we need effective manpower. More and more training and research need in this sector

PARTICIPANT: MARKETING EXPERT 2

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: 35-40/Male

Profession: marketing expert

Institution: N/A

Job position: Marketing manager

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

10-20

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: In the global jute sector Bangladesh got the first position in production and second in export.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: Comparing the past, there is a lot of progress happening in the jute sector of Bangladesh. Production is increasing. Genetical development is happening. Export is increasing

Diversified jute product

3. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with diversified jute product? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their sale of diversified jute product?

Answer: Current position of Bangladesh with diversified jute product is not that good comparing to other country. However, as a new idea and concept, Bangladesh is doing good. Many handicraft industries are growing based on this diversified product. The jute development board are arranging some fair to increase sale.

4. What is your suggestion about diversified jute products that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?

Answer: Government needs to come forward on this issue. They should focus on marketing globally. Government, Jute Industry, and Jute Development Board need to arrange some seminars to aware people about this diversified jute product.

Current technology use

5. What kind of new marketing technology are you using? How can they planning be improved?

Answer: Many companies and related persons are visiting different international fair and taking part in there to promote our diversified jute product. This is a very good way to attract the market.

6. How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: If Bangladesh's jute industry can keep the good quality continuously, I think it will not be difficult to compete with others.

7. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute industry can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: Bangladesh jute industry can adopt new technology like new model machinery, Skilled manpower, etc. The modern world is very much depended on updated technology. If we do not adopt it now we would not compete with others.

I am not expert in machineries, but I think if we move towards automated machineries like the modern world, then we can save labour cost and time in jute processing. But obviously we need to assess if it is cost effective for us or not.

8. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Answer: Finance I think the main challenge and also the co ordination between different departments. Government can help with the subsidiary in this issue.

lack of manpower, skilled manpower, not proper machineries

9. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

Answer: Technology upgradation is necessary. It should be developed in future. I think if we can have enough financial backup, then we can move forward in exporting updated technologies and machineries. Social media advertisement is new era of marketing comparing to past. So, more attention is needed here.

Pricing

10. How you establish both internal (local) and external (export) pricing? What facts do you consider in establishing pricing?

Pricing depends on variety of factors, production cost, profit, subsidies from government, market demand etc.

Governmental subsidies for local sale is not in place which make us to increase local jute product price while we have good amount of subsidy from government in terms of export. So, it modulate the price setting in both local and export.

With the global demand of quality jute product, and to compete with other countries, it is now important for us to improve our product quality. If we are able to do so then we can hold the market and our position in competitive global market. So, it think is it now time for us to have focus on improving our product quality. We can have discuss with our agricultural expert to improve jute fiber quality in processing, and also to the industrial processing experts who deals the matter. They are the main personnel who need to come in front to take the initiatives. Only then we as marketing expert can take our product and present them to the world. I have seen product from many countries and in my opinion we have lots of opportunity here in our country as well which we can use to compete with them.

There is another factor which I will mention, that is the transport expense and time required for jute product delivery. Both in local and international trade, if we work on this, it will also help use to reduce the price and make it competitive. Here, government can take steps in reducing the transport cost, and to make it easy for the traders.

Technology and machineries cost is another additional fact that control the price up down. We do not have that much improved technology, but what we have, has the space for improvement. It can reduce the associated cost with jute production and product processing.

Trading barriers

11. What is your thought about different trading barriers that Bangladesh jute industry is experiencing?

Answer: There are lots of trading barriers. Port problems, financial problems, coordination problems, etc. Bangladesh is facing all the problems.

As I have discussed earlier, We have barrier to export yarn, other jute product but no regulation on raw jute export. It is governments duty to resolve such problem and make negotiation with countries where we can sale our product. However, our government has lacking in this sector. Negotiation with exporting countries is not good enough to sell our product there without any hassle and in good price. Need to remove these barriers from exporting yarn and DJP so we can export them easily

12. How is Bangladesh jute industry tackling with such barriers?

Answer: recently the government has taken some steps to overcome the barriers. They have opened a new international port in Mongla to solve the port problem.

13. What policies Bangladesh jute industry applies when experiencing any logistic port problem?

Answer: I have little knowledge about it. But I think there are definitely some policies to solve the problem.

Involvement of government

14. How Bangladesh Government helps with its rules and regulation to overcome logistic challenges experienced by Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: I have little knowledge about it. But I think there are definitely some policies to solve the problem. Government is taking actions accordingly to solve logistic problems, removing export barriers like negotiation with buyer countries, product carrier in international export etc. The representative of our government in buyer countries are being helpful to identify associated challenges and to solve it. So, we can say that government in doing its job ok, but still can be better yeah? They are trying their best to help us and to help the industry. But in terms of subsidies and funding, they can do more I guess.

15. Is there any other support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute industry? What are they?

Answer: I don't know in details actually. But as I said, there are some actions are being taken but poor implementation I will say. People sometime do not follow the instructions and there is not strict rules and regulation.

Sustainable performance

16. How is Bangladesh jute industry working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: The whole system of jute processing is sustainable and eco-friendly.

17. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: Yes, there very little using of chemicals in this processing system but if we use biofertilizer then we can solve the problem.

18. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?

Answer: We need more research on jute. Others country are doing huge research to do better but you can see we have no such things. People are not interested. We should attract people. We should tell them that how important jute is for our country. Educational institute should

enlist this topic to their study. Government also needs to focus on this. Then we can get better result in future.

PARTICIPANT: MARKETING EXPERT 3

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: 40-45/ Male

Profession: MARKETING

Institution: N/A

Job position: Marketing manager

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

25 years

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: Once jute was golden fiber of Bangladesh, however with time it become memory. Because of cheap substitute of polythene. But still today people know Bangladesh as jute exporting country. Still our jute has demand worldwide and we are number one in world considering jute exports, because of our quality. We could have done better if we put enough concentration on it. We need to do

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: Comparing past, I think our export has increased. However, with this corona and all this war we have some negative effect with jute demand. But still we are doing good. Government shut all of jute mills, only private run factories are running now. They are leading this sector quite well.

Diversified jute product

3. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with diversified jute product? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their sale of diversified jute product?

Answer: We are improving our DJP sector, we do not have that much product so far, we are just in the beginning stage. Basically, Bangladesh export raw jute, jute yarn and jute bags. Country like china and India importing raw jute from Bangladesh and converted into DJP then they are making huge profit. They already establish their market, most of the buyer knows them for their DJP but nobody knows about Bangladesh. They are making profit from our jute but we are left behind. India imposes antidumping on jute product but not with raw jute. Because they need our raw jute, our jute quality is far far better than them. On the other hand, our government do not have any activities on the jute sector. Do not have any negotiation with other countries about trade barriers or so on.

We sometime take actions to promote our product to global and local market. |Such as, we are attending different seminars and fairs around the world to exhibit our product. We take different diversified jute product to the fair to attract buyer. It is kind of a fair where people from around the world come to showcase their product. Such program is also present within our country where we take some of our nice product to attract people. We also exhibit different poster to let people know about our industry and its production. Sometime, we go to rural area to educate people about the advantage of jute product over another alternative biohazard products. We invite different industrial personnel to discuss our product development and to discuss future possibilities. It is good to have discussion and to plan for future and to know each other in the same field. We have different professional institute where we do such kind of activities for networking.

4. What is your suggestion about diversified jute products that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?

Answer: we need to work all of the stages so that we can minimize our cost. Without minimize and consistent price we will not be able to hold our market, also we will not be able to expand the market either. Government needs to put subsidies to the farmers so that they are interested to produce more jute and they are getting their price for their jute as well.

Government needs to work on to overcome all of the trade barriers we are facing now. It will be great help if they are able to do that rest of the things we can handle that. Lost of buyer losing their interest from jute because of price, they are looking cheap jute substitute product. We need search new market as well.

Current technology use

5. What kind of new marketing technology are you using? How can they planning be improved?

Answer: Most of the buyer know us as jute exporter so they come to visit us and told us their demand and their expecting price we also give our best price to them and try to negotiate. So that it works both of us. we also visit them time to time. Jute product related fair also arrange in different country, where we join as a exporter and different buyers also join to look what is new coming next. So we exchange our knowledge, need and quality same time we understand their desire as well. You know its conventional way off marketing but still we are depend on it because already we have quite good relation with buyers. But i think we need to adopt different technique with conventional one specially if we want to attract new buyers. Now we are live in digital world, we need to learn digital tools for marketing like social media marketing. Its really helpful if we are interested in consumer level marketing and brand development. However most of the export oriented factories are engage in business to business. To be honest with you we have huge Lackage. I can share my experience, i have seen lots of companies do not have proper website, in this time its totally unacceptable. As you have already know Government run factories are shut down now but private run factories they are doing well.

6. How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: Yes our marketing system is quite conventional but its still working good because Bangladesh is well known as jute producing country. We need upgrade our market forecasting, raw jute price fluctuates too much so we have to incorporate with the price. Sometimes we lose our customer because of price or we need to sell less than our breakeven to retain our customer.

In marketing government need to support jute sector, need to make better tread deal. I have seen our competitor countries has better tread deal than us. So they can meet the price but we can not. If we want to make new market we need to focus every single thing, now we are using same machines and same technology. Trade deal is very important

7. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute industry can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: Basically we are using same technology like other countries. But we need more technologically sound manpower. So, Government and private organization can arrange training Sessions on the on the other hand we need to attract more textile graduate in this sector. For marketing point of view we need know and use marketing tools. In jute sector we do not use any forecasting method to forecast demand or production. We do use our experience and commonsense. Bangladesh in the jute marketing from very early days but still we fail to develop brand. We need to emphasise on developing brand, need to use modern marketing tools like social media marketing and low-cost production. So that we can have more buyer, we able to develop new market and we can cover more people.

8. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Basically, we are using same technology like other countries but we have shortage of skilled manpower. I think technically sound manpower is our main challenge. Few other problem we have as well like we do not have machine manufacturing companies, need long time to get loans and so on. Government should work on to overcome it, we already have machines and tools manufacturing company which is run by government just need to expand their operation.

9. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

I think within 5 years most of our machines will be upgraded so that we will able to increase our production in same cost. Costing is very important in jute sector.

Pricing

10. How you establish both internal (local) and external (export) pricing? What facts do you consider in establishing pricing?

Answer: First of all when we make price, we consider our purchase prices then we add overhead cost, utilities and profit margin, for company policy i cannot disclose those numbers. Since Corona and those war, we are running breakeven or sometimes we have little bit loss. But still we need to hold our buyers. We need to consider we will going sell in local market or export. In case of export we can get cash rebate but for local sell we will not get any things. So local price get bit higher. Local buyers mainly purchase from locals' manufacturers not from export-oriented factories because of prices.

11. What do you think of competitive pricing and how jute industries in Bangladesh are working in this?

Answer: Our price are very competitive but we have different problem like trade barriers. We provide less price than other countries like india or china but they has duty-free excess but we do not have ultimately our price become expensive. So, we lose our market. Government need to negotiate better trade deal with other countries.

12. What is your pricing strategy to increase export profitability? (Onyango, 2021)

Answer: Basically we operating factory now in breakeven to hold our buyer and market. If we are able to hold our market we will able to increase our profit by increasing sales in minimising cost. I think very soon we are able to overcome the saturation. Now container prices are also very high i hope it will drop as well.

13. What is the local pricing strategy to keep market flow inside the country?

Answer: some local factories they sales yarn or fabric to the local market, then it goes to the diversified product manufacturers. Export oriented factories like us very difficult meet the local's prices because we are not able to get any cash rebate for sales which we get from export. Government has police to increase jute demand by banning single use plastics and plastic bags

but no implementation. If it is possible to implement the policies it will be great for our jute future.

14. What is your suggestion about improvements in existing pricing strategy that will increase profit?

We can adjust our price to make profit but problem is government need to make better tread deal otherwise it will be very difficult for us to hold the market. If we can gate back our previous market and possible to extend then jute will have great future ahead. Our competitor countries like India or China they have much better deal with exporting countries.

Trading barriers

15. What is your thought about different trading barriers that Bangladesh jute industry is experiencing?

Answer: Bangladesh jute industry facing different trading barriers such as some country imposing duty in our jute product but india has duty free entry, so obviously our price goes up. this duty varies country to country. Our infra structure still underdeveloped, we are building our deep seaport but they already has more than one, we have only one sea port so far some time take long time loading and unloading. Container price is double now etc. There are lot say.

16. How is Bangladesh jute industry tackling with such barriers?

Answer: Private sector trying to overcome those barriers, but you know only private sector will not be able to solve all problems government need to come forward. Private sector they are visiting different countries, different fairs and gathering experience. In this time all the stakeholder need to work together.

17. What policies Bangladesh jute industry applies when experiencing any logistic port problem?

Answer: now bit better because government develop the road network with Chittagong port, do not take too long now few years back need week to reach the product in Chittagong port now takes a day and most of the work can be done by online. You know sometimes we face some problem, need to go there in person otherwise its ok.

Involvement of government

18. How Bangladesh Government helps with its rules and regulation to overcome logistic challenges experienced by Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: We do not have problem with rules and regulations, its already there. Now most of the work are online so need not to go there, it saves lots of time. We have only one international port sometimes its has long ques difficult get schedule. However, government take necessary step to develop deep seaport and also developing road network.

19. Is there any other support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute industry? What are they?

Answer: Governments need to do lots of things, better trade deal with exporting countries, need to give tax rebate and subsidies industries and also farmers so that price and qualities will be convenient. Lots of raw jute goes to different countries mostly India, they also impose antidumping in our jute yarn and jute related product. Need to stop raw jute exporting to India and need to negotiate about antidumping.

Sustainable performance

20. How is Bangladesh jute industry working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: Jute industry is natural and almost sustainable, we do not use that much chemicals here. However, we have ETP. It does not have any threat to the environment. We also maintain national and international compliance.

21. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: It's an export-oriented factories, we export most of our products. Government, third party organization and Buyer representative visit and perform audit time to time in our factories. Labour ministry also does audit to the factory otherwise will not be possible to run the factories.

22. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?

Answer: We need to keep mentioning our quality in every stage. Private and government need to work side by side to improve this sector specially to overcome the trade deal with other countries. We need to retain our market and also expand our market which will not be possible without getting help from government.

PARTICIPANT: MARKETING EXPERT 4

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: 40-50/ Male

Profession: MARKETING EXPERT

Institution: N/A

Job position: Sr. Marketing manager

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

20 years

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: Once jute was golden fiber of Bangladesh. However, it over its golden time. If we compare to the recent time, we are doing exceptionally good. If we consider export and everything Bangladesh is holding first position. Still today people know Bangladesh as jute exporting country.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: If we compare to past there are significant difference because before jute sector are run by only government mills but now its run by private sector. Government shutdown most of jute processing factories because those factories incur huge amount of lose for mismanagement. Private sector doing quite well. They are using new machineries and technology, and they are also making profit. Yeah, they also facing different kind of problems and they are working to overcome it.

Diversified jute product

3. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with diversified jute product? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their sale of diversified jute product?

Answer: We are far behind in DJP. DJP product market mainly dominating by China and India. Both China and India import raw jute from Bangladesh converted diversified jute product then market to the other countries. They already build their market this is the main problem now. They already bit ahead of us and most the importing countries know about them. We are in developing stages now need to give some time. Till now, we mainly export jute yarn, jute bag etc. Now a days we are developing DJP and start exporting. Country like India put antidumping last 15 years for our jute products and jute yarns but importing our raw jute. Our government doing nothing, not doing proper negotiating other countries to make convenient deal to expand our jute.

Most of government run factories are shut down now only private sector are working. Yeah, we are doing good now. Using new machines and technology. However, diversified products mainly produce in SME or micro business still not in industrial scale. Need to develop machines and arrange long term loan so that they can expand their business.

4. What is your suggestion about diversified jute products that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?

Answer: Government has to come forward to make better trade deal, without better deal nether we will be able to hold the market nor possible to expand. We need better deal. Need to allocate

more found for reserch on jute product, developing jute machine and technology. we have to ensure consistent price and quality. So, need to work from field to every level in jute. Need to arrange subsidiaries in farmer level. We have some other barriers like only one seaport need underdeveloped infrastructure however, government are working on it. Hopefully, it will solve very soon. Besides, it can be another way to attract customer by lowering our trading cost for JDP. I know this is bit difficult to get profit with lowering trading price. However, this can be one of the ways to get market for our product at initial level. Just to start the market and make people interested

Current technology use

5. What kind of new marketing technology are you using? How can they planning be improved?

Answer: Basically, we use traditional marketing technique which quite effective. We visit different fair and buyer from different countries come to visit our factories. Explain their need so that we can satisfy their needs.

If we want to improve this sector, then both private and public sector need to work together. Otherwise, it is not possible. Need to overcome the barriers which i have already mention you

6. How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: You know we are still in the market because of our jute quality. We are using same machines and seme technology. We have quite good chance this sector. If goverment make better tread deal with different countries that will be enough for us rest of things we are able to do that.

7. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute industry can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: We need skilled manpower, so that need to develop it. It can be arranged both private sector or government. Need to attract textile graduate in this sector, they will have skills and knowledge. We need machines manufacturing units so that we can develop machines according to our need.

8. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Lot of challenge we have face to upgrade the technology firstly, need proper planning and execution. Where we are very week. Need long term and low interest loan only government can arrange it.

9. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

I think in near future all our machines will be upgraded because all of the jute manufacturing industries are private run, they want to make profit with consistent quality. I think we need

machines manufacturing unit then we can produce machines according to our need on the other hand we will have competitive advantage on it. Need to invest but problem is our market are not very big. So need government assistant.

Pricing

10. How you establish both internal (local) and external (export) pricing? What facts do you consider in establishing pricing?

Answer: Most of our sales order come from export. When we make price we need to consider raw jute parches price, wastage, overhead, labour cost and profit margin. I really sorry i cannot disclose the figure. Its a company policy. Last few years we are running just in breakeven or little bit loss because of corona and war in ukraine and middle east. However. We get some incentive on our export but in local sales we have not get anything. Sometimes local price goes bit higher than the export price. Most of the local factories buy from local sources as all. I think government need to consider this, otherwise local producer will not get high quality product.

11. What do you think of competitive pricing and how jute industries in Bangladesh are working in this?

Answer: Our price quite competitive than our competitor most of the time we provide best price. our jute quality is exceptionally good that is why we are still are in the market. We need to work to overcome from our trading barriers. Where government need to work hard with our counterparts.

12. What is your pricing strategy to increase export profitability?

Answer: Our first priority is our quality. If we can maintain our quality, we will able hold our market and also we will be able to expand it. We can make profit as well.

13. What is the local pricing strategy to keep market flow inside the country?

Answer:

However, our quality much better than the local manufacture. If government give cash incentive for both national and export i think it will help us both like local market and manufacturers like us.

Our price sometimes bit higher in local market than the export because order volume is smaller in local market and also we do not get any subsidies from government

14. What is your suggestion about improvements in existing pricing strategy that will increase profit?

We need to restore our market and expand it at the same time. So that need to consistent price with quality. So we need to work together in every stage. We have different organization like EPB, BJRI, BJMC and jute ministry need to work together to expand our market by making trade deal with different countries.

Trading barriers

15. What is your thought about different trading barriers that Bangladesh jute industry is experiencing?

Answer: We are facing different barriers such as duty-free entry, sometime we need to pay duty on the other hand country like India need not to pay the duty, so they get advantage, ultimately their price goes lower. Some countries we have duty-free entry in textile but jute is not included. So we could not get duty-free entry. We have only one seaport and road is under development it causes problems. However, government is working to build infrastructure and building deep seaport I think near future it will help us.

16. How is Bangladesh jute industry tackling with such barriers?

Answer: we try to make our prices as low as possible with higher quality. As you know our labour cost is bit lower than our competitors. Our quality is better that is why we are still in the market.

17. What policies Bangladesh jute industry applies when experiencing any logistic port problem?

Answer: if we face any problems in port, we have agent there, they basically solve the problem for us. Most of the things in the port are online now it is hand. So far, we have only one seaport some time it has long line takes extra time

Involvement of government

18. How Bangladesh Government helps with its rules and regulation to overcome logistic challenges experienced by Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: still now only one seaport is working and our road network is weak as well. However, government is working on it to overcome it. It needs time. We have rules and regulation like every other country but we have weakness in implementation.

19. Is there any other support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute industry? What are they?

Answer: Whatever barriers we are facing now, most of them government can help us to overcome it, maybe not only by government but also public and private sector together.

Sustainable performance

20. How is Bangladesh jute industry working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: Jute process is fully natural so it's sustainable and we need to use ETP as well because we have jute dyeing. We need to incorporate all local law and also international law.

21. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: we need to comply with all the local and international law because we export our products in different countries.

22. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?

Answer: you know jute is already sustainable we need to do marketing accordingly. Government has band single use plastic if we can implement in every stages ultimately it will increase jute demand.

PARTICIPANT: JUTE RESEARCHER 1

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: Above 50/ Male

Profession: Jute researcher

Institution: N/A

Job position: Research Fellow

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

10-20

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: No one can compete the China. Bangladesh's position is better than Pakistan and Sri Lanka, but not better than China and India. If we compare with India, we do not have sufficient raw material like India. India is in advance level. Bangladesh is also in good position. India has reached to the highest technology and other things. India and China has their own technology, Bangladesh has not reached to it yet. Technology means machinery or other technology suppose software development, then product development, research work, these things are not available in Bangladesh now. Product development work is not happening in Bangladesh. You are researching on jute, not garments product? Ok. Bangladesh is doing well in Jute. I can say some jute product are really good but Bangladesh can not compete with India. Though some research work are happening but same thing I will say again that no actual research work is

happening. Product diversification, specially the composite thing has the big market. India rich in technology than Bangladesh. Bangladesh does not have much product development work, software development, research work. This is the reason for Bangladesh's lacking. There is some work going on research and development, product diversification, but still can't compare them with India and China.

Jute is the second largest production for natural fiber in the world. Bangladesh is producing huge amount jute. The EU countries and other countries who are very much aware of climate change and carbon emission, are saying that Jute is the alternative of Plastic use. Sustainable biodegradable plastic. Jute cannot be same as plastic in mechanical properties aspect but do some help as alternative. Synthetic fiber. Has some non-structural (indoor application, car dashboard, door panel) application market. In Bangladesh, there are some research works going by BJRI, but I wonder if they are any close to that development that we can use jute in non-structural application. I do not think that there is enough funding from government to do such standard level of research.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: Production is not remain same as past. Production has decreased in a large amount. Development is not so much happened comparing the past. Production is not improved but diversification has been improved than past. People are working on diversified product. Work is going on different jute diversified product like bag. Huge portion of jute is using in carpet. Synthetic product has captured the whole market. Recent world is more attracted because of sustainability feature but we need to promote our product more and to minimise the price. If you go to the market now you would see that every shop has jute bag as their product.

Production strategy

3. What processing strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute sector is adopting in terms of increasing their production and meeting global jute demand?

Answer: I don't have vast knowledge that what are government actually doing but I don't think government taking any strategies for increasing of jute production. Dr. Mobarak Hossein recently invent the golden bag which is using in market now. This sector is being ignored from past. All the government factories are being closed for many years.

4. What do you think about Bangladesh jute industry in global jute market with such strategies in next 10 years? (Any recommendation)?

Answer: We have research centre. We need to concentrated on research work and monitor it properly. Need monitor what are researcher doing in research, are they focusing on inventing new product or are they focusing on product development work. We need to monitor these things. We have to make some strategy to make then research on product development. Even If we do not consider the outside market, we can still creat market inside our country. We have to find new market for jute. We can make local market to increase sale. We can make jute composite by mixing with other product to attract market. Government have to give proper guidance to this sector. If we follow all of these we can do better than now in next few years.

diversified jute product

5. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with diversified jute product? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their production of diversified jute product?

Answer: Now I can not say the details strategy of Bangladesh. They may have strategy in product development but what is it exactly I can not say. This is the problem that collaboration with other country is not so easy for Bangladesh. There is some complexity. Bangladesh has not sufficient financial fund to collaborate with other country. Bangladesh's position is not so good in diversified jute product. There is not so much improving also. For example, some new macheneries, may be only in limited basis, I am not that sure, but I heard of some. I think it is better if the country can bring some improved machineries competing with other countries to step ahead in the competition. But in world demand of diversified product is increasing day by day. We have to focus on this matter promptly. We have some funding difficulties and need to over come it.

6. What is your suggestion about diversified jute products that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?

Answer: Every country has some proper research work and product development work. If government take some steps to collaborate with other country because without collaboration this is not possible to improve in jute sector. They have to take some initiative. People who are doing Phd in other country, they also can not keep the collaboration with the country from which they are doing phd. Some documents and permission are need to make these collaboration and this is so tough to put these thing together. People lose their interest to make collaboration with other countries. Funding difficulties, corruption need to overcome. Government should think that people are doing something for jute industry so they should come forward. If government and other association like Jute Corporation, Jute Development Board come forward to help this diversified product sector, I think it can attract the global market. Manpower is available but we are shortage in skilled man power. Proper machineries are also not available in Bangladesh to produce quality DJP. There is no continuation of research. Bangladeshi People who are doing PhD from other countries are not applying their skill in this field further anymore. The main problem is in funding.

Current technology use

7. What is the technological improvement in industrial jute processing?

Answer: Conventional equipment is available but new equipment is not available yet. We don't have new technologies yet for jute processing. We are still using the old one. We do not have new machineries for diversified jute product. I think the industry is applying cost related strategy to produce same amount of product but in less cost so they can benefit. Otherwise, it is really difficult to compete with global market and current pricing situation.

8. Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries? How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: What can I say about this? Comparing the past Bangladesh still using the old version technologies in jute and diversified jute product. China and India has better technologies than us. They are improving this sector from many years. Private mills are making the same product since the past.

9. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute sector can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: We produce product on demand basis. If we can make jute product more demandable then we can find way to improve it. If you turn jute into a non-oven product then costing will be less and we can more product from it. We have to bring some change in product diversification. We have to make product based on market demand to compete with other countries. We have to research which product has much demand in market, what process are other country using. We have to do a lot survey. I have seen a video where people are blending jute to cotton. We have to adopt new technologies to improve this sector. People are losing interest in jute. We have to bring their faith on it.

We need to bring technological changes in processing. Not mandatorily making fiber from jute but it transform jute in other way to diversified product.

10. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Answer: Bangladesh has jute research institute. People who are working in these institute, they have to find out what changing are happening and what process are people using outside, If we want to make product like them then what procedure we should follow and monitor these things. We have man power, we have plan. Now we just need to use this man power as planned. Jute has some processing challenges to make composite with cotton and other product. We need to find out fesiable way to process jute in which we can use in it composite technique. Cheaper and easy process. Researchers use flax, but jute can be cheaper if we know exact processing technology.

Bangladesh jute sector are not getting proper research work. Most of the talent students are not interested in this sector. If they can find interest in it we would get strong research work. Funding is also a big challenge to improve technological sector. Government have to help to over come it.

11. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

Answer: Technology upgrade should bring to this jute sector. Farmers are not getting fair price for jute. That's why they are not cultivating jute anymore. If farmers get appropriate price for it then production would increase. Government may spend to improve technology in jute sector but Implementation should be monitored. Many people are work in this jute industry. Government need to monitor their work. Research work are open now. If government follow up the research work then it will be beneficial for jute industry. Government have to ensure the maximum use of man power. If government set the target to fulfil in product development

sector, it will help to achieve the success. There is no accountability in this sector. If we establish accountability then people will do their job properly.

Involvement of government

12. Is there any support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute sector? What are they?

Answer: As I said before I can not tell the exact figure of the budget which is government using in this sector. Government need to provide training to people and set a target to fulfil it.

Government also needs to provide financial support. There is not much support from government to progress in industrial processing, particularly in diversified jute product development. Different machineries required for some diversified product, which we do not have and if government give financial support then we can import them and have progress in our product. With the financial support from government, we can also bring updated machineries to our industry and reduce labour cost. It will consequently help us to sell product in reduced price which is the main demand of the buyer.

Sustainable performance

13. How is Bangladesh jute production working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: Jute production and cultivation is a sustainable process. Retaining process, in which we are still using the conventional process is not much sustainable. We are still depending on natural water for retaining. We are using fertilizer in jute processing. If we use bio fertilizer to process jute then it can be in a full sustainable manner. We can avoid using fertilizer if we go for organic.

14. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: To become sustainable, yes there are some rules and regulations. Government is making plans to make it more sustainable. However, the apply of such rules is not satisfactory. Even, it is not present in all case. Most of the time, due to the lack of proper implementation of policies, people are also reluctant in following them”.

15. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?

Answer: Product development, research is needed to improve. Bangladesh government doing some work, providing fund but implementation of these courses are not so good. We need to monitor the whole system and improve it. Government is giving many opportunities to develop this jute sector. Government is giving prime minister Scholarship to bring back interest in research work. Different organization are offering scholarship and arranging fund to do research. All we need to do is focus in this sector. We are still using the old technologies. We have to leave these old technologies and move forward to the new era.

PARTICIPANT: JUTE RESEARCHER 2

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: 40-50/ Female

Profession: Jute researcher

Institution: N/A

Job position: Senior Scientific officer

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

≤10

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: Bangladesh got the third position in the global jute industry. China has the first and India has the second position. But once Bangladesh had the first position for jute. Though

Bangladesh is not in the first position, the quality of jute of Bangladesh is better than other country. Once Bo one can beat wih Bangladesh in this jute issue. In Bangladesh we call jute the ‘Golden Fiber’. This was a true golden fiber once.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: As I said before that in the past, it was gold for Bangladesh. But day by day this position has decreased. It is not that the quality has decreased, it is the production. People are losing interest to cultivate jute in their land. The reason is the low price and other facilities. A farmer can cultivate more than one crop while he cultivates jute. There are very few developments has been occurred in this sector. Skilled manpower is not available in this sector. Behind every development, there is a need for skilled manpower. But we can not see it happen here. If I compare the present situation to the past then I can say that very few changes and development has been happened in this sector.

Production strategy

3. What processing strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute sector is adopting in terms of increasing their production and meeting global jute demand?

Answer: Now a days private sector has come forwards to make their contribution in jute sector. This is a positive sign. Because the government could not do all the development work alone. Now both government and private sector are working together to make some strategies and working hard to ensure its implementation. They are now taking initiative for research work. Because there is no alternative of research work to develop. They are funding research work to create new variants which will produce more jute in a short term time. The government are taking necessary steps now along with the private sectors.

4. What do you think about Bangladesh jute industry in global jute market with such strategies in next 10 years? (Any recommendation)?

Answer: If the government and private sector work like this with the strategies they have made, Bangladesh will reach the top place in the next 10 years again. Actually, every sector need to work together. Otherwise, it is not easy to reach any of the top positions. If we can combine every sector which is related to the jute industry. Nobody can tell where will go in the next 10 years but if we work together we can achieve our goal I think. The private sector of Bangladesh jute industry is contributing huge to increase the production and to hold the position of Bangladesh jute industry in global market

Diversified jute product

5. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with diversified jute product? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their production of diversified jute product?

Answer: Bangladesh is not doing good in diversified jute products. Because this thing is still new to people. And other side, alternative products are cheaper than jute diversified product.

That's why people are not interested in it. Other country like India, Thailand, and China are doing well in this sector. Because they have adapted this diversified product. India is taking huge amounts of raw jute from us and turning them into diversified product and selling them to the west with a high price. We do not have much support to do such things. Besides people of our country is not economically developed. Price of jute made product is very high. So they use alternative product.

6. What is your suggestion about diversified jute products that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?

Answer: Bangladesh jute industry needs to make some plans and policies to improve this condition. They should minimize the product cost. Diversified product with high price will not get the market. There are a lot of alternative product in market. If jute have to take over the market then it need to focus on price. Besides people need to be aware of these things. Then people can get interested in it, like plastic is very harmful for environment but jute is eco friendly. Both government and private sector need to come forward.

Current technology use

7. What is the technological improvement in industrial jute processing?

Answer: Technological improvement means the use of upgraded machinery in this sector. In reality, there is no such thing in this sector. Still, factories are using the old model machinery. Importing updated machinery is not so easy. The financial problem, Permission problem, Logistic problem. There are lots of problems. Besides maintaining updated machineries we need skilled manpower. People are not well-trained to handle the new model machinery. Here in Bangladesh there are huge man power. But there is a lack of skilled man power. The People who go to abroad for higher studies, very few of them involve themselves in this jute industry. After the private sector involving in the jute industry, some technology are updated. But this amount is very few.

8. Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries? How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: No, I don't think there is much development happened in technology from past to present. There is very few amount development has occurred. Not so much to mention.

9. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute sector can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: At first Bangladesh jute sector have to bring new model machinery. Then they have to train people well enough to run it. Day by day we are entering into new era. This is called technological era. The institute or the country whose are much updated in technology, they are more developed than anyone. Today we have to drive into the technology world to be developed. Everything here and there are controlled by development. So if we ignore these things and can not adapt technology then how we can be developed. In the jute industry, technology development is not that much what we need to be. The government now realizes these facts and makes strategies and plans to bring huge development in this jute industry.

10. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Answer: Skilled manpower is the main challenge. There is a lot of manpower but not enough skilled needier. Government also need to focus on this side. There are lots of issue except these. There are financial challenges too. Farmers who are backbone of these industry are not paid enough. This is the reason they are losing interest to cultivate jute in their field. They are driving them into another profitable cultivation. There is no subsidy system for jute. If government arrange some subsidy for this industry then our farmer can turn back themselves in this industry again. There are also pricing problem. We need to set the proper price for jute. There are some challenges for upgrading technology in this sector. Financial and logistic challenge are the main along with skilled man power.

11. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

Answer: If the government help to upgrade the technological part of the jute sector then I think it will do better in next 5 year. Mainly everyone, every department of government need to work together to solve this problem. If we can overcome our all challenges and upgraded technology then this jute will gold again for Bangladesh in next few years.

Involvement of government

12. Is there any support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute sector? What are they?

Answer: Government are making some plan and policies. But there no implementation of these plans. Government already banned poly bag from the market and order to use jute bag but still this is not happening.

Sustainable performance

13. How is Bangladesh jute production working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: Whole jute process is happening in a sustainable manner by nature. There are no use of the chemical. But recently some people are using chemicals to earn more profit. This should be stopped.

Textile is one of the sectors that produce huge amount of waste hazardous for environment. IN the textile mill, when we process jute, we have some waste management plant or treatment that reduces waste and its spread to the environment. However, not all the industries are maintaining such measurements. Since there is not strict regulation from government. Hereby, everyone is trying to take the advantage. They are saving money by not implementing the sustainable plan. They have it just in paper and pen, not in reality. If it is present in reality, it is very less. Few industries are following the measurements.

14. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: May be there are some rules and regulations but I have a very little knowledge about it. But I can say that the whole system of jute sustainable itself. Government need to ban the plastic and synthetic fiber. These are very much harmful for the environment. Actually the government are taking some steps. They are making some strategies but implementing these strategies is very poor. This is happening for the lack of coordination of different departments of government.

15. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?

Answer: Government has to be more friendly. The government needs to arrange some subsidiaries for this jute sector. Some training needs to be held also. Jute is an eco-friendly product. If the government can make aware of people about this term, then the use of jute diversified product will be increased. Besides this the price should be less of diversified products. Many research work needs to be held in an educational institute. Without research, work development does not possible.

PARTICIPANT: JUTE RESEARCHER 3

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: 40-50/ Male

Profession: Jute researcher

Institution: N/A

Job position: Professor

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

20 to 25 years

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: I feel like jute has good opportunity in the today's world because it's a natural fiber and its biodegradable nature. Its very strong fiber and its second in use as vegetable fiber. As I have told you it is natural fiber. You can see around 50's to 60's jute was dominating the world until inventing cheap polyethylene. polyethylene is cheap alternative so world took the advantage but we damage our environments by this cheap polythene. I think people are more concern now about the environment than the past so jute will have great future ahead but need to increase the jute production and need to diverse its use. So lot of research work need to do. I believe very soon you can see jute demand will increase dramatically.

Yeah, Bangladesh is one of the jute producing country in the world. According to growing row jute I think Bangladesh is second after india but in term of processing and technology Bangladesh is third after china and india. It will be very hard to compete china and also india. Because they have their own technology, machine and raw material. Bangladesh has only raw material but not technology and machine. But Bangladesh is better than Pakistan and srilanka. Some recharge work is engaging in different organization but its not sufficient, there is no product development, no technological development and so on. Bangladesh is doing good in raw jute growing. Government and our private sector need to work together to beat the competitor. If they want to beat the competitor the really need to work heard and invest more in research. Which I cannot see yet. As I know, with in last few years there is only jute bio plastic is developed. I think if research work is going in good manner it will have really good prospect in the world.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: Bangladesh had passed its golden time long ago, once it was known as golden fiber of Bangladesh. if we compare to the recent past, yes I think Bangladesh is improving but not as expecting level, It should develop more. Jute growing are increased but not its production, production more or less remain same level, there are some development in diversification of its product but it could have development if we give more attention. Recent era is sustainability so I think its driving the development of Bangladesh jute sector.

Production strategy

3. What processing strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute sector is adopting in terms of increasing their production and meeting global jute demand?

Answer: I think private jute manufacturer are trying to minimizing the cost so that they can reduce price. Actually they are doing the most for development and surviving this sector. some of the factories purchase new machineries to increase production and qualities. I don't think government has any strategy to increase the production or developing this sector. Government shutdown all of the government run factories. As I known Mobarak Hossein recently invent the golden bag, but I don't think its come to the market yet. if government have appropriate strategy to increase production you could have seen more activities. This sector is being ignored from past.

Even though the progression is not much significant. I have heard that some of the industry is trying to use different part of jute plant to make diversified products. Such as recently I heard that they are using jute sticks to make sustainable charcoal. Jute as a sustainable raw material, researchers are now trying to innovate different product from it to propose its efficient use in industrial level.

4. What do you think about Bangladesh jute industry in global jute market with such strategies in next 10 years? (Any recommendation)?

Answer: still I believe Bangladesh jute industries will do good because private sector are holding there position quite good and also developing from there position quitly. Globally jute demand is improving so Bangladesh has quite good chance. As you know Bangladesh has hues labour force and raw materials. We have research centre and appointed peoples, just need to concentrate on research work, monitor properly and appropriate plan. We need to increase the product range or more diversified product, focusing how to develops the technology. Even, you know if we do not consider global market still we have our own consumption. Our market it quite hues. If we follow all of these we can do better than now in next few years.

Questions to get answer related to diversified jute product

5. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with diversified jute product? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their production of diversified jute product?

Answer: Bangladesh's position is not very good in diversified jute product. There is not so much improving also. We have diversified jute product promotion burro, BJRI they are working for jute improvement and new product development. They have some activities and also some researcher working with jute but problem with collaborating the different instate in Bangladesh as well as other countries. its not so easy, really very very complex to work with Bangladesh. But in world demand of diversified product is increasing day by day. We have to focus on this matter. We have some funding difficulties and need to over come it.

6. What is your suggestion about diversified jute products that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?

Answer: first of all need to work both private sector and garment together to develop more DJP. All of the private jute factories should have R&D department. They need to develop diversified jute product, it will be very difficult for today's world to survive without new product and you know future will be more heard. they should have cooperation between them so that they can exchange their learning and technology. Jute mills association can take the initiative and private jute factories should have allocated fund, which fund can be use for research in different universities, they can announce price for asking DJP. So more people will be interested I feel.

Government should have more initiative, which is missing now. Government should have more fund, need to allocation the fund properly and monitor it closely. Government has very little

fund its not use properly either, I mean need to overcome the corruption in government sector need to make more transparent. From Bangladesh lots of student goes to different countries for engaging their Phd or for their research and also different universities are working in jute research, Bangladesh need to focus on implementing this research work, need to collaborates with different university. Which is very hard now, too much beaurracy, people loosing interest. There is no continuation of research need to ensure it by allocating more fond.

We have lots of people but still we have shortage skilled manpower. Need to give training to the people in this both government and private sector should work side by side. I think we do not have proper technology and machineries available to produce the quality DJP. So we need focus all three if we really want to develop DJP. You know off course need more fund. Main problem is funding here.

Current technology use

7. What is the technological improvement in industrial jute processing?

Answer: In jute sector most of Bangladeshi factories are using old machineries and conventional technology. Not that much improvement yet but I think they are realizing they need to upgrade their machineries. Some of the factories they are replacing their old machines to new, which is good sign. Problem is, we don't produce machineries we need to buy from other countries like china and india. Before machines come from England which was really good qualities but they stop making jute machine now. Bangladesh need to develop their own machine manufacturing unite so that we can compete the other countries like china or india. Both india and china they are working on to improving jute machine, last time I was on the machine fair I have noticed they bring some improvement but qualities and production. On the other hand there is no development in DJP both in machineries and technology. Need to do quite lot distance if we really wants survive in this sector.

8. Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries? (Van Der Walt, 2020)? How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: I already have told you Bangladesh mostly using the old machine we don't have that much improvement compare to past but now we are realise we need to do that. Some of factories are importing new machines which is good sign. If compare to the india or china I think they are ahead of us because they are improving their technogly quite some time. We have quite some space to improvement.

9. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute sector can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: now basically Bangladeshi factories produce their product then try to market them I think we need change the marketing strategy. We should do market survey, focussing then we should produce accordingly. Need to do research a lot. If we make only conventional product I do not think it will work. I believe here is lots of scope, we can bland jute with other fiber like cotton, it reduces cost just as example, it can be use for non woven thing as well. We need

to bring diversification in jute, we need bring changes in processing and also in technologically as well.

10. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Answer: first of all I think most of the talented student are not interested in jute sector, we need bring back their interest, if we are able to bring back their interest back we would get strong research work which will help this sector. Again funding is main problem here, government have to give subsidies and also private sector should come forward as well.

We have man power but need to train them appropriate way. Bangladesh has jute research institute. Those people are working they have to find out what changing are happening and what process are people using outside, If we want to make product like them then what procedure we should follow and monitor these things. Jute has some processing challenges to make composite with cotton and other product. We need to find out feasible way to process jute in which we can use in it composite technique. Cheaper and easy process. Researchers use flax, but jute can be cheaper if we know exact processing technology.

11. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

Answer: yes I believe lots of positive changes will come in this sector from irrigation to production. Farmer will use more modern machines than past because we have now water scarcity. Water are not available like before. Lots of water needed in jute retting. We need to ensure farmer getting fair price for their product. In production and DGP I think we will see more upgraded modern machines. If government set the target to fulfil in product development sector, it will help to achieve the success. There is no accountability in this sector. If we establish accountability then people will do their job properly.

Involvement of government

12. Is there any support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute sector? What are they?

Answer: you know we have jute research institute, DJP research centre people are working there, might be not that much fund but still people are there. we need use every little of the fund to improve this sector. All over research budget is very very low in our country we need to increase. Need proper planning and appropriate monitoring. Need to put right people in the right place not every things consider politically.

Sustainable performance

13. How is Bangladesh jute production working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: as I know Jute production and cultivation is mostly sustainable. Only in Retaining process still using the conventional process is not much sustainable. We are still depending on

natural water for retaining. But I think it will change very soon. We are using fertilizer in jute processing. If we use bio fertilizer to process jute then it can be in a full sustainable manner and organic. For factories basically they are using governmental guideline. They need to maintain local resolution and environmental law which is sustainable as well.

14. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: To become sustainable, yes there are some rules and regulations from local as well as international because jute also export to the rest of world. Government is making plans to make it more sustainable. However, the apply of such rules is not satisfactory. Even, it is not present in all case, due to the lack of proper implementation of policies.

15. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?

Answer: Bangladesh live in a global village, if we follow sustainable guideline I think it will be better for jute sector it will bring more customer. Both government and private sector need to work side by side. Government need to provide appropriate support, provide training, allocating sufficient fund and proper monitoring mechanism.

Thank you.

PARTICIPANT: JUTE RESEARCHER 4

PART A

Demographic questions for the participants

Name: N/A

Age: Above 40/ Male

Profession: Jute researcher

Institution: N/A

Job position: assistant Professor

How long are you working in this job field?/ your experience level in this job field:

Around 10 years now

PART B

Current industrial progression/status

1. What do you think about the competitive global jute market and current position of Bangladesh jute industry?

Answer: I think jute is doing good and its bright future are not very far, if we compare the recent past. you know, today's more people are concern about the environment than the past. Lots of organizations working to aware the people about the environmental damage we are making to use the polythene. Jute can be use as polythene substitute. Its very strong natural fiber and its biodegradable. I feel like people are using more jute product than recent past. Around 80's jute lost its market share to cheep and use friendly polythene but I think time has come to take it back. But it will not possible on sudden, need to do lots of things, need engage lots of research. Need to increase product line, diverse use. I think jute demand will increase more not only globally but also nationally as well. Just need appropriate planning, proper implementation and allocating more fund for research. I think all of this we going to see very soon

Yeah Bangladesh is doing ok in jute sector, to be honest with you I did not expect that much from them. This sectors are facing lots of short coming and government have very little involvement still they are doing good its really amazed me. Currently Bangladesh is number one raw jute exporting country which is good in one sense we are earning foreign currency but it is not very good in other sense we should use this jute and make more valuable and diversified product. So that we will able to earn more, create more market for us. For diversified jute product market mostly captured by china and india. Its really hard to compete them, they are really ahead of us in machineries and technologies. Now they are manufacturing there machine and every necessary things where Bangladesh has only good quality jute. We need to invest on it to improve our technology and machine.

2. What do you think about the current progression/development of Bangladesh jute industry comparing to past?

Answer: once jute was known as golden fiber of Bangladesh. Bangladesh earns most of its foreign currency from this sector but lack of supply and cheep alternatives like polythene jute loose majority of its market share. Recently, I think Bangladesh is doing quite well as because its demand is in up tend. In jute growing I have seen cultivation land is decrease but yields are more or less same, so there are some development compare to past. Bangladesh export most the raw jute in the world, hold the first position. But in processing I think there are not that much development happened. Most of the factories are using conventional machineries and technology, not that improvement is visible to me. It could have better position if we give appropriate attention. You know, hemp is same kind of fiber but jute are more stronger, hemp has more attention to the world than jute because lots of research has done, it has more use case than jute. What you have made from hemp you can make from jute as well. World are more concern about sustainability, I believe its demand will increase but we need to satisfy the world supply. I should have proper plan in every sector. As nut shell we can definitely say that Bangladesh is doing quite good than its recent past.

Production strategy

3. What processing strategies (recently adopted strategy) do you think Bangladesh jute sector is adopting in terms of increasing their production and meeting global jute demand?

Answer: most of the factories are trying to minimizing their cost and increasing production, so that they can offer competitive price. Some of the factories also using new machines. so, they getting better quality with production. Government shutdown most of the government run factories; I don't think government has any strategy to increase its production or anything. Private sectors mainly doing every things. We should give them most of the credits. For now on may be the strategy is ok, but I do not think it's a right one. For long run they need to change their overall strategy. They should innovate new product conducting more research, upgrade technology and use different marketing strategy. Government should help them in all aspect.

4. What do you think about Bangladesh jute industry in global jute market with such strategies in next 10 years? (Any recommendation)?

Answer: As i know most of the jute producing factories are trying to minimising their cost and maximising their production to make competitive price comparing their competitors. Its good strategy but i think we need to focus alternatives strategy as well. So that we will get competitive advantage. All of the private factories should have R&D department. This people will develops new product and also continuously improving production process. It would be better if possible to develop network between the factories. Government or BJMC can take necessary step. I think if we want to make this sector work, we need innovative product range, people always pay extra for new product. If we want more profit we need use our brain and also need to use our people. This sector are labour oriented sector, Bangladesh has hues labour market but unfortunately still we have shortage of quality labour. Need to arrange training, which can be done by both grommet and private sector. Most of the textile engineers are not interested to join the jute industry, need to make more attractive for them to join this sector. You know we have every things just need to use properly. Need to put right people in the right place.

Questions to get answer related to diversified jute product

5. What do you think about current position of Bangladesh jute industry with diversified jute product? How is Bangladesh jute industry working towards improving their production of diversified jute product?

Answer: we are still in the beginning stage of the DJP production. Not very positive improvement happened. As i know diversified jute product promotion burro, BJRI are working on it. But i don't think they have done any significant job. Most of the DJP markets are captured by china and india. If really our factories want to profitable they need to work here. Government and private sector need to work together to develop new product and need to find new markets for the products. Its really difficult in Bangladesh, because very difficult to collaborate different organization, need lots of paper work people lose their interest. Government are busy in different activities, not interested to make treat deal with different countries.

6. What is your suggestion about diversified jute products that Bangladesh jute industry can work on to attract global market?

Answer: i already have told you it is under developed in Bangladesh, need to do lots of things. We can follow the path of china and india specially china. Now china maimly dominating in

diversifying jute product market. If we follow properly we can learn, which can help us a lot but problem we have we do not want to learn.

Firstly, we need know how to use our recourse, we have at least two organization (BJRI and Diversified jute product promotion biro) which are build to work with jute. We need use these recourses. Government definitely has less fund, need to allocate more fund in this sector and whatever funds are available we need to use it properly. I think we have shortage of expert researchers as well. We need to develops them and also need to increase more training facilities for developing skilled man power.

Some small private organization are producing DJP in Bangladesh recently. Most of the products are consumed in local market very few are exporting. I think they do not have capability to produce industrial scale and also do not appropriate machineries as well. Currently government has some subsidiary in DJP, need to increase. Government need to provide financial support as well as technical support to produce in industrial scales.

Secondly, need to increase research work, if we want to increase research, you know we need more fund. Need to make easy to collaborate different universities and organization which is very heard now. Encourage more researcher to work in the jute sectors.

Thirdly, private factories need to build R&D department, so that they can develop more product and also in sustainable way. They need to exchange knowledge and expertise between the factories. If we are able to do that, i believe it will beneficiary both factories and Bangladesh as whole.

Current technology use

7. What is the technological improvement in industrial jute processing?

Answer: not that improvement happened most of the factories using old machineries and conventional technology. However, few factories are replacing their old machines with new one. Which is good sign they realise they need to upgrade their machine as well as technology. Basically, Bangladesh do not make machines, need buy from china or india. Some technological improvement happened in DJP and jute growing. Bangladesh need to establish at least one machine manufacturing unit so that we can satisfy our own need and also compete our commentators.

8. Is there any improvement comparing to past and comparing to competitive countries? ? How will these improvements help Bangladesh Jute industry to compete with other jute exporting countries?

Answer: not whole sector has improvement compare to past but has some improvement. Field level has some work has done, we produce around same amount of jute with using less land. Some factories are using same kinds machines like china or india because they upgraded it. So if we compare to competitive country, technology will be almost same. But lots of factories are still leave behind because they are still using old machineries. Government need to arrange easy and long term loans for them.

9. What is your suggestion about technological improvements that Bangladesh Jute sector can adopt to improve their current position?

Answer: i think we need to upgrade all of our machines first then continuously upgrade our machine otherwise we will left behind. Need to do lots of work. Need do lots of research in technological improvement as well as processing upgrade.

10. What challenges do you think is there in upgrading technology and how can we overcome it?

Answer: first challenge will be fund here. Most of the factories don't have that much fund to upgrade their machines and technology. Then need skilled man power, we have hues man power but still we have shortage of skilled man power in every sectors. We need to change our self as well, some people do not wants upgrade them self.

Government need to allocate more fund, encourage more fresh textile graduate to join this sector and need to do more research. Without research will not about to survive.

11. What do you think about technological upgrades in Bangladesh Jute industry in next 5 years?

Answer: i am not sure about time frame but very soon i think most of the factories will upgrade their technology. So that they will use more competitive technology and labour market will be more technologically sound. Demand is increasing gradually, tend showing it will have more demand in the recent future. I think it will be the driving force behind our improvement.

Involvement of government

12. Is there any support from government in improving current status of Bangladesh jute sector? What are they?

Answer: in this moment government provide some incentive to the factories who are exporting their product. Also provide some subsidiaries to the DJP producer. But you know funding are very low, need to increase more both in factories and also in education and research. Whatever fund are available need to ensure appropriate use of it.

Sustainable performance

13. How is Bangladesh jute production working in a sustainable manner? What steps are they adopting to represent them as sustainable industry?

Answer: jute growing and processing are mostly sustainable. Most of the factories need to follow the local law and also international laws if they wants to exports their product. In field level farmer need lots of water in retting process, where need to work basically for sustainability. Recently some machines develops and also developing for retting, hopefully we will able to reduce water consumption. Jute dyeing and printing process factories should have ETP, need effectives one as well.

14. What policies/performance measure/rules and regulation do you follow to become sustainable?

Answer: you know now lots of the jute factories are export oriented. They need to follow local, environmental law as well as international law. We have laws and its upgrade as well but we have problem with implementation. Government need to force them to implement it.

15. What is your suggestion in this term to improve such performance in future?

Answer: jute is natural fiber and it has diverse use case. If we can understand its potentials and give appropriate value, our bright future will not very far. It's already sustainable now we can make it organic. People are more concern about environment than the past. I believe jute golden time again is coming back very soon.

APPENDIX II

30/07/24

School of Business
and Creative Industries
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Scotland

Tel +44 (0)141 848 3932

Dear Md Touhidul Islam B00359701

ANALYSING CURRENT STATUS OF BANGLADESH JUTE INDUSTRY: ASSESSING PERFORMANCE FROM FIELD TO EXPORT

The School Academic Integrity & Ethics Committee (SAIEC) has been made aware that you have not made an application for ethical approval via the Ethical Review Manager (ERM) system for the research involving human participants gathered as part of the above project.

The SAIEC understand that there are mitigating factors at play in this omission:

1. Your supervisor was unable to access core UWS systems, including ERM, and was therefore unable to assist you in making an application to the SAIEC.
2. The data collected is low risk and anonymised.
3. The data collection processes described in your thesis would appear to be 'otherwise approvable' and involved the gathering of informed consent.

As such, the data you have collected for the above project has been deemed admissible for assessment.

The SAIEC is providing you with this letter in lieu of ethical approval.

We would like to remind you that you should ensure that you have full ethical approval before beginning any future programme of research involving human participants, personal data or risk to the researcher. This includes informing the SAIEC where changes have been made to an existing approved programme of research. Failing to do so is a breach of the UWS Code of Ethics and could result in the data you collected being inadmissible for assessment.

Kind regards,

 Personal details withheld.

Dr John Quinn, Chair of the School Academic Integrity & Ethics Committee
On behalf of Prof. Kasim N Sheik, Dean of School.

Professor Dr Kasim N Sheikh, LL.M, PH.D, FHEA, CMgr FCMl
Dean of School